

EarthCube

ROADMAP

PREPARED BY

CROSS-DOMAIN

INTEROPERABILITY

TEST BED GROUP

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SUMMARY

The rationale for cross-domain interoperability is to facilitate more accurate modeling and understanding of the Earth System, which requires integration of information about the solid earth, hydrosphere, atmosphere, biosphere, and interactions between these domains. Interdisciplinary research requires utilization of datasets that have been collected and compiled by various researchers at different times and places. Often data are applied to analyses different from those for which they were originally collected.

Enabling sound scientific application of such cross-domain datasets requires that they are well documented, that they can be found, and that the information contained in them can be transformed into a form that can be used. Fostering cross-domain interoperability thus requires support for dataset documentation and curation from the beginning of its life cycle; development of discovery mechanisms that operate in a federated system of catalogs with different domain contexts; tools to support data exploration and manipulation to extract the desired information; a social framework for cross-domain networking between researchers needing to understand each other's data; and a governance system to provide direction, decision-making, and authority for prioritizing and developing the necessary specifications and tools. In this document we present a roadmap for developing these capabilities in the context of the larger EarthCube framework.

The current version of the roadmap and supporting materials are maintained at <http://earthcube.ning.com/group/interop/page/roadmap>

KEY MILESTONES ON THE ROADMAP:

- Development of a cross-domain interoperability readiness assessment procedure
- Application of the assessment to the current NSF geoinformatics portfolio
- Collection and documentation of cross-domain use cases
- Gap analysis: development of requirements and comparison with current capabilities
- Specification and demonstration of cyberinfrastructure (CI) components supporting cross-domain interoperability, including fitness-for-use assessment
- Iterative implementation of the CI components, including community validation and testing
- Organization of a continuous cross-domain interoperability testbed process that bridges needs of geoscience users with advanced technical solutions
- Development, management and curation of a cross-domain interoperability platform and content supporting the platform
- Validation of the platform and its content in a series of research scenarios
- Ongoing collaboration with other EarthCube groups to avoid duplication of effort and assure a system of interoperable components to implement EarthCube function

One of the key recommendations of the roadmap is the creation of a Geosciences Interoperability Institute (GII). Its functions would be similar to those of a domain data center, but its main scope will be management of cross-domain resources, including inventories and registries, federated resources and cross-walks, linked datasets, service brokers and other software tools that enable cross-domain integration and provide the core of the interoperability platform. Key functions and governance arrangements of the envisioned GII are described and justified.

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1. PURPOSE

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The technological revolution in data acquisition, management and access enabled by digital computer and communication technology allows previously unimaginable accessibility to large volumes of data. Data are being collected at increasingly larger ranges of temporal and spatial scales, so that different domains are increasingly likely to find data at matching spatial and temporal resolutions, which can be used to instantiate or validate integrated models. This access presents opportunities to use existing datasets to explore scientific hypotheses that may be related to completely different problems than the data were originally intended to address. Reuse is most common in related scientific domains, but other cross-domain applications may include business or economic analyses, sociological studies, and educational materials.

This document presents a roadmap to advance cross-domain interoperability in the EarthCube framework. Although physical processes are not confined to disciplinary or jurisdictional boundaries, scientific research has become increasingly specialized in modern times. This trend has been promoted by the disciplinary organization of scientific publications, the educational system, funding streams, and other institutional arrangements. There is a pressing need to develop the technical and organizational framework to facilitate cross-disciplinary research at a massive scale without sacrificing intellectual depth or domain-specific accomplishments.

From the perspective of cross-domain interoperability, we envision EarthCube as an innovative socio-technical environment that supports scientific research by broad communities of geoscientists without impediment from artificial or organizational boundaries on data or model formulation. This is a central requirement of an integrated geoscience that explores and models the Earth as a single system. EarthCube is well positioned to invigorate and transform cross-discipline information integration and analysis in the geosciences, capitalizing on accomplishments in individual disciplines as well as the growing understanding of environmental interconnectedness, and technological developments that enable interoperability in geoscience research scenarios.

The National Science Foundation (NSF) has made significant investments in the development of cyberinfrastructure for specific disciplines. While the need for more integrated approaches has been widely recognized, progress has been challenging. We believe there are at least three key components to increasing interoperability:

1. Enable researchers and students to combine information from different domains via a system of shared standards-based software environments that facilitate discovery, interpretation, access and integration of data. This system should be community-governed and designed to evolve, adapting to new technological capabilities and progress in understanding of the Earth system.
2. Facilitate and promote the formation of cross-domain teams, and foster better understanding and communication within such teams.
3. Educate new Renaissance-type scientists for whom cross-disciplinary research is the norm, supported by a reward system for such scientists.

1.2 THE CENTRAL ROLE OF CROSS-DOMAIN INTEROPERABILITY

One clear outcome of the June 2012 EarthCube Charrette is that every concept group requires some strong notion of cross-domain interoperability. We argue that this central need should be met centrally, rather than from independent efforts of each concept group. The centrality of this issue is illustrated in Figure 1.1, which is a consensus EarthCube diagram that concept groups have converged on at the July 10, 2012, post-Charrette workshop. A cross-domain interoperability layer is crucial to integrating the now separate domain-specific data services, through techniques including standardization, semantic mediation, and general notions of “data fitness for use” that we develop later in this document. Data is “fit for use” if the use of the data is scientifically valid and produces credible scientific results. Thus cross-domain interoperability is required so that:

1. **Layered architectures** and **brokering** provide meaningful and useful data with a minimum burden on the user and provider within and across domains.
2. **Semantic mediation** helps researchers to discover data that is valid for use in their context(s) and also enables collaboration with the ability to map terms.
3. **Web services** provide data that is scientifically meaningful and valid.
4. **Scientific workflows** utilize data that is meaningful in context.
5. **Data discovery** leads to accessible data that is usable in context.
6. **Earth system modeling** utilizes data – at each modeling scale – that is fit for use at that scale.

Thus we argue that a Geosciences Interoperability Institute should be created to study interoperability in all of its forms according to the methods outlined in the roadmap. This institute will benefit every EarthCube effort and its success is crucial to the success of EarthCube as a whole.

Figure 1.1: Centrality of cross-domain interoperability to EarthCube goals

1.3 PURPOSE AND KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ROADMAP

The purpose of this roadmap is primarily to address cross-domain discovery and integration issues in a comprehensive manner (the first of the three components listed in section 1.1). Support for the social aspects of cross-domain interactions is a secondary consideration. Education-focused activities are not discussed in depth because they are being explored by other groups within this phase of EarthCube planning.

The intention of cross-domain interoperability is to enable reuse of data and models outside of the original context in which these are collected and used. A key issue we are addressing is secondary or derivative use of data, in which data collected for one purpose is applied to study a new problem. Derivative use builds on pre-existing information resources by extracting information from them to create a new resource that can be used for the same, similar, or an entirely different purpose (Zimmerman, 2007, p.7). Cross-domain readiness encompasses the capabilities that need to be in place for such secondary or derivative use of information (data or knowledge) to be both scientifically sound and technically feasible.

In this document, the term “domain” (or “scientific domain”) denotes the community of users who are intimately familiar with a particular range of datasets, analysis and modeling procedures, and applications. This includes an understanding of the data acquisition process involving instruments, measurement protocols, data processing, assumptions and background knowledge, typical problems that arise in the acquisition and processing workflow,

and interpretation procedures. Such knowledge is typically considered a prerequisite for scientifically reliable use of the data and the development of sound conclusions based on it.

The concept of ‘cross-domain’ can be thought of in terms of a conceptual knowledge distance. This distance is measured relative to some ‘local’ (familiar) sphere of activity. Conceptual distance arises from:

- Differences between research intents, assumptions and methods in different disciplines
- Differences between practitioners, or between scientists and the public
- Changes in assumptions and methods over time, even within a single discipline.

The original parties that acquired, processed or modeled the data may forget details over time, or retire from the community. Scientific methods and theories change with time as well, resulting in some loss of understanding between the original data acquisition and reuse (Zimmerman, 2007; Michener et al., 1997; Bower, 1986).

Mitigating such losses over time requires defining processes and infrastructure to minimize this conceptual distance, in particular for domains that need to exchange data often, or providing tools for quickly closing the gap when required. Different strategies would be needed to accommodate integration across different conceptual distances.

Therefore, **key action items of this roadmap** to address cross-domain interoperability in the EarthCube include:

- **Formulate evaluation metrics** for interoperability readiness, and identify gaps, development priorities, and risks for cross-domain infrastructure development.
- **Identify tools and workflows** necessary to capture a high percentage of data, use cases, and innovative ideas produced by modestly funded research projects that constitute “the long tail of science.”
- **Enable and demonstrate relevant, community-supported, standards-based interoperability models** for selected aspects of catalogs, vocabularies, services and information models.
- **Create a prototype data integration platform** designed to bridge user needs with advanced standards-based technologies to enable data reuse for new applications.
- **Articulate differences** in research paradigms, accepted norms of scientific explanation, patterns of organization, data collection and sharing practices, and the interrelated technological strategies and governance arrangements these dictate.
- **Establish a community-guided process** to identify cross-domain use cases, capability gaps, and development priorities that integrates technological advances with community adoption and broad engagement.

Activities in the roadmap will rely on continuous communication within and beyond EarthCube to provide guidance and feedback to the project, and at the same time encouraging active involvement of members of core EarthCube communities through discussions, use case work, testing and adoption of standards-based technologies.

1.4 COMMUNITIES TO BE SERVED

Precise identification of the communities to be served is one key for developing targeted and tailored solutions. While there are common cyberinfrastructure issues that different domain information systems need to address, different research designs, data collection and management practices, processing and analysis routines result in different user needs across groups and domains. We identify the following groups to be served by EarthCube:

- **By discipline:**
 - Geoscientists: researchers, educators and students representing multiple geoscience domains that differ in the types of data being collected, traditions of data sharing, standardization approaches, community cyberinfrastructure components developed to date, and other

characteristics that indicate domains' levels of maturity for data and model reuse. This discipline is the primary focus of this roadmap.

- Researchers, educators and students in other closely-related fields outside the geosciences, which are likely to include geoscience information in their research (social sciences, biology, etc.). For them, standards-based interoperability approaches in the geosciences may provide a model for organizing their infrastructures and for supporting EarthCube interoperability models.
- **By organization:**
 - Researchers in NSF-supported projects and universities.
 - Government researchers in various state and federal agencies, in particular those closely related to geosciences (such as USGS, EPA, NOAA, NASA, DOE, USDA.)
 - General public, including citizen scientists. They represent an increasingly important group, as both data publishers and data consumers, and have specific challenges, in particular related to data quality, transparency of access and use of data, motivation and governance. While this is not the core target group for this roadmap, we address its needs in the discussion of the readiness model and communication and management strategies.
- **By role in information lifecycle:**
 - data publishers; data curators, integrators and other intermediaries; data consumers; data preservation specialists, etc. These specific roles are described in more detail in the cross-domain readiness model.
- **By stakeholder role:**
 - Decision-makers and managers, science researchers, technology researchers and developers, end-users, sponsoring agencies.

We expect that EarthCube will foster various **communities of practice** that bring together groups of researchers who share interests spanning these disciplinary, organizational, and role-based boundaries. We envision the cross-domain interoperability platform mentioned above as a key instrument to nucleate and motivate such communities of practice, as it would provide an environment for sharing information about issues and best practices of cross-domain interoperability solutions. We also recognize that EarthCube is just the US-based component among an emergent web of international scientists and other stakeholders. While NSF funding would not extend to cover international contributions to EarthCube, any such coordination is encouraged to strengthen global interoperability readiness.

1.5 KEY TECHNICAL AREAS

The key technical areas we consider are:

- Requirements to assess cross-domain usability and determine fitness for use of various domain cyberinfrastructure components.
- Development of a reference architecture for EarthCube that supports cross-domain research designs. The architecture will need to account for:
 - the role of brokering and mediation supporting discovery and access;
 - the role of modular services and layered architecture concepts; and
 - the role of semantics, workflows, and data discovery approaches.
- Development of community registries of use cases, models, infrastructure components and other resources to support continuous monitoring of community needs, interests, and functional requirements.
- Design and prototype implementation of a cross-domain interoperability platform enabling data publication, discovery and integration for complex scenarios.

- Usability and limitations of standards-based federated catalogs, vocabulary cross-walks, services and information model profiles to support the varying research needs of the geoscience community.

The interoperability platform we outline is intended as a bridge between novel cross-domain research scenarios and applications, and advanced computing technology explored by other EarthCube teams. As such, the agenda and technical approaches considered by this roadmap are expected to be complementary to the technological foci pursued by other groups (names of these partner EarthCube groups are in bold in the subsequent sentences). Our emphasis is on opportunistic data reuse enabled by standards-based solutions, including information model profiles that support data integration based on common encodings of time, space and observable properties. **Data discovery and access** is central to cross-domain use cases. We emphasize those layers in a **layered architecture** stack that are specifically needed to support cross-domain integration, especially catalogs that can be federated for cross-domain search and middleware **brokering** services that provide mappings between common protocols and encodings. **Semantic** technology for mediating vocabularies between domains will play a major role in these components. The cross-domain interoperability agenda is also strongly connected with the exploration of **web services**, particularly vocabulary services that can support interpretation of measurements across domains, and data access services working across datasets from different domains. Input from the **Earth System Models** group will be vital, since earth systems models often represent materialized and well thought out cross-domain use cases. **Governance** is a key foundation for cross-domain interoperability, as mediation between different domain data systems and community-guided interaction between data providers, consumers and intermediaries require specialized governance arrangements. **Workflows** are envisioned as a key component in the analysis of domain readiness, using replicable and repeatable processing chains to assess and document fitness for use. A cross-domain interoperability platform would provide shared expertise and an environment where these technologies can be further explored, adapted and applied in cross-domain research scenarios.

1.6 TARGETED USE CASES

This roadmap targets scenarios involving secondary users who had no part in the original production of a given knowledge base. One of the foundations in the roadmap process will be to develop research scenarios to illustrate cross-domain data discovery and integration challenges and derive user requirements. These scenarios should highlight common technical issues in cross-domain interoperability including: federated data discovery using domain catalogs with different metadata profiles, matching terms in different domain vocabularies, managing data accessed via different protocols, and integrating differently encoded and formatted information by extracting and matching key characteristics of measurement sampling frames like time, space and observable properties. We are specifically interested in situations where a new data source from another domain is included in an established model, which may require explicit representation of the semantics of the new source, gap-filling, interpolation, and upscaling/downscaling. A number of use cases were reviewed at the Concept group PI workshop in July 2012, and ten were identified covering a broad range of disciplines and cross domain activities. In the Challenges section, we provide examples of a subset of these, including analysis and modeling of hypoxia in the Gulf of Mexico, the use of weather radar data in hydrologic modeling, and analysis of global biogeochemical cycling in the context of the Global Rivers Observatory.

1.7 CROSS-DOMAIN INTEROPERABILITY READINESS IN THE DATA LIFECYCLE

Scientists' ability to reuse data or models from their own or other domains depends on how the data was acquired, described and published and whether they can be easily discovered, accessed and interpreted. The lifecycle of a typical scientific data set progresses from original collection to eventual retirement. Similar lifecycle descriptions

would apply to modeling and processing routines. The location of a dataset in this life cycle has implications for cross-domain usage of the data. Data lifecycle milestones include:

- **Original data acquisition**, in which processing and maintenance occur in a local, potentially unmanaged environment in the context of an individual research project objective. It would be unlikely that other researchers would find the data useful without considerable effort.
- **Ad hoc sharing and evaluation of new products for fitness of use.** Cutting-edge researchers evaluate new data products and models and communicate this information through presentations and publications. Such evaluations usually happen before packaging for a specific community.
- **Packaging for *strategic reuse*** makes data available in a more structured, edited, and documented form to address anticipated scientific applications. This kind of repackaging is done at the request of and intended use by specific scientific communities and/or fields of study, and might support reuse within close domain proximity
- **Enabling discovery** entails documenting information resources and making the descriptions (metadata) accessible so that other can obtain knowledge about the availability and meaning of reusable data sources. This is a prerequisite for utilizing a dataset outside of the immediate word-of-mouth community in which it originated.
- **Packaging for *opportunistic reuse*** entails creating standardized and documented versions of existing data sources that are likely to be useful in a variety of contexts. This lifecycle stage may require a significant commitment of effort by the data originator, value-added developer or curator, and supports the widest reuse of a dataset in conceptually distant domains.
- **Retirement** entails deprecating standardized data sources that are no longer considered valuable and are no longer being updated with new data values. The determining value judgment may be subjective, so the rationale for retirement should be documented and clearly communicated. Data produced should no longer be seen in catalogs, but need to be archived, if utilized in an analysis.

Only a small percentage of data resources are optimized for domain reuse, or for specifically anticipated cross-domain uses, complete with metadata designed to make them discoverable via some mechanism. A large number of data resources never make it beyond original acquisition; these are referred to as “dark data” or the “long tail of science.”

Cross-domain readiness concerns the fourth and fifth step in the data lifecycle: documenting and packaging data for unforeseen and opportunistic discovery and reuse. This involves providing both packaging and discovery mechanisms that support use by scientists outside the original domain for which data were intended. Assessment of cross-domain interoperability readiness requires development of a better understanding of requirements for such opportunistic cross-domain reuse. Support for cross-domain reuse will require improved workflows to facilitate creation of documentation and archiving of resources, improved discovery mechanisms, and tools to support semantic and spatio-temporal integration of datasets.

1.8 VALUE PROPOSITIONS AND IMPROVEMENTS BEYOND THE CURRENT STATE-OF-THE-ART

There are several value propositions for motivating cross-domain data use:

- Data are expensive to obtain, and may be impossible to acquire again.
- Cross-domain use enables new kinds of science that are technically or financially impractical within a single scientific domain.
- Cross-domain use allows development of cross-validation techniques whereby domain data can be tested for accuracy, quality, and other factors.
- Cross-domain use increases the return on initial data collection investments.

Goals of this cross domain interoperability roadmap will advance various improvements in the state-of-the-art. Geoscience data available via a community-governed, standards-based infrastructure will enable wider reuse. An open-standards-based approach precludes a single group controlling the standard, facilitates competition, stimulates innovation, avoids vendor lock, and fosters long-term sustainability and the availability of 3rd party tools.

Research scenarios described in this roadmap provide examples of how specific technical interoperability advances can lead to better scientific solutions. EarthCube is being designed for the long term and must be adaptable for emerging research scenarios, use cases and technical capabilities. The cross-domain interoperability evaluation and governance processes we propose are intended to support an evolving EarthCube infrastructure process. Achieving scientifically sound and transparent opportunistic reuse of large volumes of scientific data across disciplinary boundaries and creating supporting management mechanisms has potential to transform how cross-disciplinary research is conducted in the geosciences and open new research pathways.

The cross-domain interoperability plan is designed to address a number of grand challenges related to the geosciences, including climate change prediction, water sustainability, analysis and management of hazards, and CO₂ sequestration (NSF 2011). Each of these problems transcends disciplinary, organizational, political and other boundaries. Developing solutions to overcome domain barriers, as outlined in this roadmap, has the potential to transform how these and similar challenges are addressed. In particular, improved capabilities for data reuse across domains, and increased reliance on standards for data discovery, retrieval, interpretation and integration will make scientific analysis and modeling more open, transparent and collaborative. It will become easier to re-generate simulation results, independently validate modeling conclusions, or re-run models with new data obtained from different geoscience domains. New solutions and approaches are especially needed in the context of exponentially increasing data volumes and numbers and variety of data users and stakeholders. This includes the large groups of geoscience researchers who are involved in relatively small projects – the so-called “long tail of science.” In other words, we envision that:

- A hydrology student needing climate data to run her model will be able to find, understand, evaluate the fitness of, and retrieve the data quickly, in a suitable format;
- A biologist needing stream discharge and precipitation data will be able to find these data or data products in the appropriate spatial and temporal resolution and for the needed spatial feature (e.g. watershed), or use simple tools to convert it to the needed resolution;
- A hydrologist will finally trust precipitation products generated by others. They will be able to trace and interpret the provenance of the data in understandable terms;

- Geo-located data will be available based upon “ellipsoidal” and “spherical” earth models, as required by the researcher.

The above scenarios appear mundane, yet the tasks take a lot of time to accomplish *every time they are done*. It is especially difficult to create an environment and infrastructure that would meet community data and processing requirements where such requirements are science-driven and tailored to suit the nature of scientific enterprise. Yet this is the ultimate purpose of cross-domain interoperability agenda in EarthCube.

2. COMMUNICATIONS

Developing effective communications mechanisms is critical to the success of the cross-domain interoperability within EarthCube. In this section, two facets of the communications plan will be described. First, the communication means currently used by the funded Interoperability concept award are detailed, as well as plans for the remainder of 2012. Secondly, the future communications approaches needed for an interoperability effort of a scale that has the potential to transform geoinformatics approaches on the 5+ year timeframe are described. Finally, we present a communications view of cross-domain readiness, reflecting our recognition that, ultimately, enabling smooth information flows connecting information providers, users and intermediaries is the key in achieving interoperability.

2.1 CURRENT COMMUNICATIONS

This communications plan has two components: internal communications for those already affiliated with the project, and outreach to wider communities. Internal communications are handled through posting project documents on the Earthcube ning site and a linked DropBox site, emails sent through the associated group mailing list, and weekly organizational conference calls (all minutes and slide sets are linked from the ning site). As of June 1st, the Cross-domain Interoperability Test Bed group has 64 members.

Outreach efforts to date have focused on the larger EarthCube community. A Webinar on May 8th was held to present the Interoperability scope and purpose, to outline the current reference models and use case progress, and to solicit feedback. 61 people participated, and the discussion lasted for over an hour, providing valuable input for refining the Interoperability roadmap.

A key aspect of the communications plan has been to ensure close coordination with the other EarthCube Community and Concept groups. To this end, the Cross-domain Interoperability group has designated at least one liaison to each of the other EarthCube efforts. The current liaisons are:

- Brokering - Ben Domenico
- Web Services - Ilya Zaslavsky, Dave Valentine
- Layered Architecture - Ilkay Altintas, David Arctur
- Earth Systems Modeling - Rick Hooper
- Governance - David Arctur, Erin Robinson
- Workflows - Ilkay Altintas
- Data Discovery Mining and Access - Chaitan Baru
- Semantics - Karen Stocks

In addition to the EarthCube community, we have communicated with several federal agencies, in particular USGS, EPA, NOAA and NASA, the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), and the Federation of Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP). These communications are necessary to understand common interests and plan synergistic projects that leverage agency efforts (in particular, in data organization and modeling) including leveraging their existing communication mechanisms.

As the first face-to-face project meeting was co-located with an OGC Technical Committee meeting (Austin, end of March 2012), several OGC members participated and have since joined the project team. Project members made presentations on EarthCube topics to their respective communities, including CUASHI and CZO, effectively leveraging communication arrangements established in these closely related projects.

Going forward, the regular internal communications will continue to provide project coordination. Additional outreach plans after the June 2012 Charrette through the end of 2012 include:

- Discussions at the OGC Hydrology Domain Working Group workshop (June) and a joint meeting with the UK's Environmental Virtual Observatory Pilot (EVOp) Project (June).
- Additional demonstration project/use case development to create strong links with additional data providers and researchers.
- Participation in the cross-EAGER meeting planned for July in Boulder, CO.
- Participation in and presentations at the ESIP Federation Summer meeting 17-20 July in Madison, WI.
- Presentations at the Microsoft eScience workshop, at the 8th IEEE International Conference on eScience October in Chicago, IL (a panel discussion focused on cross-domain interoperability is being planned).
- Presenting interoperability-focused papers at the American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting, December in San Francisco, CA.
- Participation in a planned NSF-organized workshop for end users.

In addition to the common communication channels described above, the Cross-domain Interoperability group is developing several new channels of communication, in particular focused on the "long tail of science." They include online interactive catalogs of environmental models, use case templates and inventories of domain cyberinfrastructure components. These are primarily designed to support monitoring community requirements (described in more detail in Section 4).

2.2 FUTURE COMMUNICATIONS ROADMAP

In the course of developing cross-domain interoperability capabilities within the future EarthCube framework, several key communication channels are necessary. The development team will need an ongoing conversation with the user community to establish use cases and priorities, extending the mechanisms mentioned above. Communication with other EarthCube development groups will be necessary to leverage efforts and avoid duplication of effort. During implementation of tools and workflows to support cross-domain data discovery, access and utilization, iterative cycles of user interaction testing will ensure usability and maintain focus on key functionality. Development of vocabulary mappings for cross domain semantic mediation is another arena where broadly based community input requires easily accessible communication channels. Specifications for service protocols and interchange formats, as well as instructions for system operation and maintenance must be communicated in a user-friendly fashion to the community. Prototyping and production deployment will need to be accompanied by communication channels for users to get help and report bugs. Rather than the single group approach that is presently being utilized, where groups are segregated into separate areas on the Earthcube site, we need to develop an aggregated approach where communications can be shared by several working groups, both established, and ad hoc.

This communication may take place through a variety of channels. Different groups will require different approaches, and the Interoperability project will tailor its outreach to each community appropriately. Some examples include:

- Person to person spoken communication in real time. This may be face to face in a formal setting, or informal social situation, by telephone, or online audio/video conferencing.
- Written messages between individuals, ranging from postal correspondence, to e-mail, text messaging, or interactive online chat.

- Formal help desk or ticketing systems that generally involve written problem statements and written interaction with a potentially anonymous problem solver.
- Online forums, wikis or other collaborative environments that involve written communication between users who are typically registered in some fashion as part of a community.
- Documentation written for intended users with no specific recipient in mind. Such documentation may describe interchange formats, service protocols, or specific data.
- Example data or code in files, possibly accessed via the internet or obtained on some sort of media.

Determination of the best approaches to communication will be based on a variety of considerations. Communication channels may need to provide access controls to honor privacy concerns, or may need to be publicly accessible to honor transparency and accountability concerns. Design discussions and user feedback that are edited and archived may be useful to inform future design decisions. Interactive discussion (either written or oral) is most useful for developing emergent ideas and concepts. Face to face meetings are vital to establishing personal relationships between team members that is an essential ingredient to a community development effort.

Cross-domain interoperability presents special challenges because of the distance (physical, temporal, or conceptual) between the data originator and data consumer. The EarthCube will require a communication framework in which scientists working across domains can effectively express their needs and get them met. We anticipate that this communication framework for cross-domain scientists will be part of a larger EarthCube communication framework, and will work with Governance and other technical groups to integrate communication cross-domain requirements with the larger framework.

The cross-domain communications plan focuses on three elements. The first is engagement to raise awareness of the effort, and engender participation and community support. The second is the ongoing assessment of needs and progress, based on effective expression of relevant constraints, problems, issues, and concerns in the area of interoperability. The third is encouraging adoption of interoperability practices – i.e. the adoption technical governance outputs.

Within the EarthCube community, there will be a spectrum of size, maturity and organizational level. On one end of the spectrum, for example, are the major earth science data projects and programs, such as IOOS, OGC, and WMO. On the other, are individual scientists and small lab groups. Similarly, data access points range from major Data Assembly Centers and groups such as CUAHSI and IEDA, to single-project portals. And cross-domain users can span from scientists with sophisticated technical skills operating complex coupled ocean-atmosphere climate models to a high school student looking for geological and biological data about her local area. Different approaches will be employed to reach these different audiences.

The following communications mechanisms will be employed, with different mechanisms targeting different groups and goals.

- **Conference participation.** To reach those data providers, intermediaries, and data users that are not well-represented by existing major community groups, the Interoperability effort will use participation in and presentations at domain conferences to raise awareness, promote engagement, and solicit feedback.
- **Committee representation.** The Interoperability effort will have scientific and technical committees composed of representatives from key data providers, intermediaries, and data users, as well as of major scientific and technical governance bodies (see section 9, Management, for details). The committees will be in close communication with the Geoscience Commons group, to design communication strategies

specifically tailored for the “long tail of science” users. In addition, it will coordinate the EarthCube interoperability agenda with standards development bodies, such as the Open Geospatial Consortium, acting to organize community input to standard development processes, and validate proposed standards.

- **Designated liaisons.** It will not be feasible to offer committee representation to every project or effort that is relevant to geosciences interoperability. Cross-domain Interoperability participants will be named as liaisons to additional efforts, to provide direct communication between that group and Interoperability governance. In particular, there will be a liaison named to each major EarthCube project. These liaisons will recognize and respond to the interoperability-related requirements of the other EarthCube efforts, as well as provide strategic cross-linking to and from the websites.
- **Website.** A web presence will be a substantial component of the outreach plan, and will have several facets: news features highlighting opportunities for community members to become involved in EarthCube, webex announcements, opportunities to review documentation, etc.
- **Wikis and blogs.** Online collaboration tools will provide avenues for both educating the community on best practices, and soliciting input and feedback on EarthCube priorities and activities.
- **Help desk.** This will be part of a larger EarthCube help desk system to provide users with assistance.
- **Catalog.** We anticipate that a major core component of the EarthCube will be a catalog/register of resources, including not only data but tools, technical specifications, example code, etc. The cross-domain team will assure that resources of interest from their communities are registered and discoverable, and will engage with the design of the catalog system to insure that cross-domain requirements are accounted for. An important aspect of the catalog is that it will allow the annotation and rating of resources (with appropriate controls), to provide a “crowdsourcing” approach to scalability and maintenance of the catalog over time.
- **Documentation.** A series of best practice and other guidance documentation will facilitate the adoption of interoperability practices, and will be particularly aimed at those who have less technical expertise (i.e. domain scientists and data managers without advanced informatics training.)
- **Use Case development.** Use cases have an important function in testing technology approaches for interoperability, and assessing requirements. They also serve an important communication role. By presenting an end-to-end story, framed in domain science outcomes, use case documents can highlight the importance of interoperability to reaching important science outcomes.
- **Workshops and consensus meetings.** Face to face meetings will be important early in the development process to establish the community and to agree on priorities. As technology is developed, workshops will provide an important tool for educating new users, and gathering user feedback to evaluate user interface designs and component functionality. Exploring technologies to address discovered needs and building consensus about standard communication interfaces will be expected outcomes of the workshops.
- **Surveys.** To reach a wider audience than can participate in workshops or use cases, surveys will be employed to assess needs, priorities, and readiness across different communities.
- **Outreach.** In addition to the ‘pull’ approaches outlined above, we propose an active outreach program to contact and engage the small data collectors and providers in the EarthCube process, demonstrating how their data can be curated and registered for cross-domain interoperability, or how they can use the cross-domain tools to acquire data for research interests.

A cross-domain interoperability test bed effort will encompass several of these communication channels and act as a center of expertise where geoscientists learn about new technologies, meet agency and corporate sponsors,

present their use cases, participate in workshops and hackathons, become members of agile development teams, and advance best interoperability practices for data publication, discovery and re-use.

We also believe that the participation of social scientists to provide ongoing assessments of communication effectiveness for different project audiences, and to help design survey and inventory instruments, is critical for the success of the EarthCube initiative. The project team has been in communication with the authors of the EarthCube stakeholder survey exploring the possibilities of triangulating survey results with our inventory analysis, in particular concerning connectivity between different geoscience domains.

We also argue that just a compendium of loosely connected communication activities and channels – essentially replicating communication channels developed within domain information systems - will not be sufficient to meet the stated vision of EarthCube as a community-guided cyberinfrastructure for the entire geosciences. Information systems developed within science domains, often maintain user support and community feedback mechanisms – however these systems:

a) are typically disconnected from each other, e.g. user wikis, questions and answers (Q&As), discussion forums, mailing lists, use case inventories, resource registries or annotations represent isolated information collections that are difficult to search jointly or integrate;

b) are disconnected from the rest of the infrastructure, e.g. annotations, Q&As, or other forms of user feedback potentially related to catalogued datasets or data access services are managed separately from discovery catalogs or services and don't provide an API for integration with the latter;;

c) do not facilitate accessing and integrating user support information from multiple sources, and across domains, e.g. Q&A systems, discussion forums, wikis, and other feedback channels are not developed to support integration of community knowledge across domains.

Meeting EarthCube communication challenges, and in particular enabling integration of user experiences with respect to data re-use across domains, requires placing an integrated communication system in the center of EarthCube CI design rather than treating it as an afterthought compared to more traditional data integration technologies. Enabling such a comprehensive communication system that integrates different types of community feedback across domain systems is one of the key functions of the Geosciences Interoperability Institute outlined later in this document.

Well-organized communication between project partners is especially important for cross-domain interoperability readiness assessment. Broadly defined, the quality of the communications paths between information users, providers and intermediaries is a measure of cross-domain readiness, as described in the following section.

2.3 CROSS-DOMAIN READINESS AS COMMUNICATION

At the very highest level, readiness for cross-domain interoperability requires defining and enabling a communication process between the people who measure the data, people who package data for reuse, and people who use the repackaged data. In our current situation, the people who measure and repackage the data are often the same, but adding an explicit “intermediary” role may be necessary in the future. Thus we have the following simple model of information flow between people:

Figure 2.1: Communication paths toward Cross-Domain Interoperability. Blue arrows represent primary communication paths; white arrows represent response and feedback mechanisms.

There are two separate kinds of governance that are needed in providing cross-domain interoperability:

- **Scientific governance** that determines needs and priorities.
- **Technical governance** that decides upon implementation plans, including standards for data format, services, and discovery services.

Scientific governance provides accountability to scientists that scientific needs are being met, while technical governance gives data providers guidance on how to meet needs.

In the communications point of view, the needs of people create information flows, and the readiness of the flows is characterized as the effectiveness of communications along the arrows above:

- Do scientists communicate effectively with scientific governance?
- Does scientific governance communicate effectively with technical governance?
- Does technical governance communicate effectively with data providers and intermediaries?

At the second level, we can ask whether communication accomplishes the appropriate loop closings:

- Do intermediaries understand the needs of cross-domain scientists?
- Do intermediaries translate these needs into appropriate instructions for data providers?
- Do intermediaries appropriately communicate resource shortfalls (both of themselves, and of data providers) and needs for decisions to technical governance?
- Does technical governance report these shortfalls to scientific governance?
- Does scientific governance respond with implementable priorities and directives?
- Do data providers respond with data products that satisfy the needs of the intermediaries?
- Do intermediaries translate these products into those that satisfy the needs of scientist/consumers?

In terms of communication, EarthCube readiness can be defined as the state in which all communication paths are functional and in which cross-domain scientists are effectively expressing their needs and getting their needs met according to the above communication paths. This in turn requires that EarthCube make intelligent choices about which communication paths to use, including the following:

- When is it appropriate to use verbal communications?
- When is it appropriate to use documents?
- When is it appropriate to use services?
- When is it appropriate to use tools?

These choices are evaluated via the following quality questions:

- Are the choices for communication sufficiently expressive and unambiguous that needs are clearly expressed?
- Are the choices for communication sufficiently robust that messages do not get lost?
- Are the choices for particular kinds of communication economical and affordable at scale?
- Are the choices for communication transparent, accountable, and auditable?
- Does the overall pattern of communication advance science?

In the “product” view of EarthCube – documented in later sections – it is easy to forget that the so-called products are actually forms of communication, and that the so-called “support” is comprised of communication, not simply documents. This roadmap focuses on the complete range of communication elements required for EarthCube, not simply the physical artifacts.

3. CHALLENGES

3.1 TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

The premise of EarthCube is that scientists can assemble data from various disciplines to explore the integrated Earth system. Technical solutions have been developed and partially implemented that enable this to be done to some extent, including:

- Specifications of basic metadata content requirements
- Standards for encoding basic metadata,
- Services for cataloging and transmitting metadata,
- Services for transmitting data, and
- Semantic interoperability of names for variables, data entities, properties, and terminological values for data.

These solutions, when fully implemented, will allow scientists to discover what data and other resources are available for a given location and time slice. To make data and models equally available across the geosciences, much implementation is needed and some technical challenges must be addressed. However, the greater challenge is social: resources and community engagement and awareness are needed to assemble and to maintain the catalogs, to implement standards, and to govern the operation of such services. In addition, as stated in the previous section, we contend that a number of often overlooked infrastructure components are needed to support communication and integration of user feedback across domains to support a comprehensive assessment of fitness for cross-domain re-use.

3.1.1 SHALLOW AND DEEP RESOURCE DESCRIPTION

There are two distinct levels of data discovery supported by different levels of resource description:

- Shallow matching is based on the presence or usage of measurements of appropriate variables, expressed in appropriate units and at an appropriate resolution.
- Deep matching requires in-depth description with information sufficient to determine if a resource is suitable for use in a specific scientific context or model. Deep matching is typically accomplished by consulting domain experts or referring to scientific literature that documents the provenance of data sources in detail. Deep matching is necessary to assess the fitness of a data set for new applications outside of the original context in which it was collected.

Resources that meet deep match criteria will also meet shallow match criteria, but in general the converse is not true. Data are generally not collected with the idea or purpose of use beyond that of a discipline. Data are provided in forms that best enable answering scientific questions of the originating discipline. Data providers have differing assumptions about many data attributes, including how data are sampled in time and space, data quality factors, and many others. These enabling assumptions are specific to the particular discipline, the state of knowledge in that discipline and the models for which the data were originally gathered. In most cases, these assumptions are not formally expressed in either human-readable or machine-readable form. It is difficult, though not impossible, to capture the salient aspects of a resource in structured metadata. The system must also be capable of referencing narrative text descriptions or providing links to knowledgeable domain experts. In cases where the original data collectors are no longer available, it may be impossible to reconstruct a complete understanding of a dataset.

A scientist attempting to use cross-domain data may need to transform data using information from several sources so that the results are somehow commensurate, comparable, and applicable. The specific definitions of commensurability, comparability, and applicability arise from the scientific question under study. Choices for data and data transformation methods are driven by scientific questions, the state of scientific knowledge, and the sensitivity of scientific models to data properties and assumptions. Deep matching involves making these choices intelligently. By providing sufficient metadata, these choices can be richly supported, and fitness for use can be effectively evaluated, as described in the next section.

3.1.2 METADATA CONTENT AND DATA QUALITY IN THE CROSS-DOMAIN CONTEXT

While discovery, access and semantic interoperability of datasets are necessary for cross-domain interoperability, they are not sufficient for sound scientific use of the data. The ultimate challenge for cross-domain interoperability is **assessing whether data are fit for an intended use** by the scientist discovering the data, a challenge that is particularly acute when the scientist is gathering data from outside his or her primary area of expertise.

Thus, the central question is whether there can be a metadata specification that is sufficient to assess suitability. Broadly, this means understanding the context and quality of the data: its intended use, preparation (e.g. sampling protocol, storage, use of preservatives), precision, accuracy, calibration, outlier identification, and any limitations inherent to the measurement technique. For data with geospatial location, it would be very often useful for researchers to know the Spatial Reference System and scale of data capture. These two aspects would enable a quick assessment of a given dataset's fitness for many purposes. Furthermore, these quality indicators must be conveyed to scientists who may not be specialists in measuring these properties.

Aspects of metadata content and data quality, from the perspective of readiness for use across scientific domains, can be illustrated by considering several case studies. Two examples highlight the interoperability challenges of large scale, interdisciplinary geosciences undertakings: The Global Rivers Observatory and Critical Zone Observatories. Both efforts are conceived to address interdisciplinary scientific challenges and both efforts seek to make data available to the broader community of scientists, as envisioned by EarthCube.

The Global Rivers Observatory (Figure 3.1) seeks to understand how global biogeochemical cycles are affected by environmental changes in drainage basins, and to quantify export from the continents to the world oceans. Calculating riverine fluxes requires combining two very different data types: 1) point observations of concentrations and isotope compositions usually derived from laboratory analysis of samples; and 2) continuous measurements of stream discharge obtained from in situ sensors. Various subtle aspects influence data suitability. For example, were water samples collected using channel-integrated samples or a simple surface-grab sample? Such information is seldom recorded in metadata, yet is critical if fluxes are to be accurately calculated.

Conversely, in assessing a river reach for fish habitat, or for correlating satellite color data with concentrations of colored dissolved organic matter, a surface-grab sample may be adequate. Observations like concentrations derived from samples are typically of low frequency (e.g. monthly or bi-weekly) and may not accurately represent the underlying dynamics of the concentration signal. For instance, freshet signals in Arctic watersheds can be as short as a few weeks. Can sufficient metadata ever be recorded to anticipate the different uses? Is it adequate (to some extent, at least) to record the intended purpose of the data, or previous uses of the data? Can data be certified for re-use?

Figure 3.1 The Global Rivers Observatory provides an example of challenges of cross-domain interoperability.

A second example is provided by Critical Zone Observatories (CZOs), a recent initiative of the NSF Geosciences Directorate that has established field sites to study the interactions of biological, hydrologic, geologic and human processes in the surficial Earth, extending from bedrock to forest canopy. Driving questions (Figure 3.2) for this program focus on the interactions among the underlying disciplines and often at the interface of these disciplines. Many insights have been gained from the development of a data management and publication system for CZOs that can inform the EarthCube effort. Progress has been made in linking in situ and ex situ data, and in geospatial information models (e.g. the recent hydrologic feature model work within the OGC/WMO Hydrology Domain Working Group¹, by Dornblut and others). Significant challenges remain in more effectively linking subsurface geologic structural data, and deeper-time data in general, with data describing present-day variability.

These two case studies illustrate the importance of supporting a **model-centric view of interoperability**. Data may be applicable to different conceptual or computational models, and characterizing the viable modeling contexts for the data are an important contribution to discovery, especially when using data from other domains with different semantics and research questions. The models for whose benefit data were gathered, the models in which they have been used, and the success or failure of those applications, would be important metadata that have largely been undocumented. The question that arises is how this original measurement intent and conceptual context for

¹ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/projects/groups/hydrologydwg>

the collection of data can be adequately captured and communicated to a cross-disciplinary audience. The challenge of capturing measurement intent parallels similar challenges of inferring intents in search and discovery, and it is especially severe in using data from different disciplines.

3.1.3 SPECIFIC CHALLENGES TO ACTUALLY USING DATA FROM ANOTHER DISCIPLINE

Different disciplines employ different conceptual data models to manage scientific feature types. Formally expressing such domain models and understanding commonalities and differences between them is fundamental to developing mappings between models and implementing them in standards-based brokers. The challenge has many components; several key ones are listed below. For each of these specific challenges, interoperability requires several measures, including: complete and standardized documentation of the original data with respect to the described characteristics; reference materials that describe the nature and importance of the characteristic; and techniques and tools to transform the data as needed to overcome the challenge. The first is within our reach but needs further standardization; the second is often available at various locations across the web, but needs indexing in a community reference; and the third is the subject of ongoing tool and best practice development, which can be facilitated as part of this community roadmap.

ENCODING FORMATS FOR DIFFERENT ANALYSIS AND DISPLAY TOOLS

A frequently-cited EarthCube challenge is the fact that researchers reusing data spend 80% of their time getting the data into the proper form for their research analysis. This difficulty is compounded because different tools are commonly used by practitioners in different disciplines, so a researcher using data from another discipline has to get it into a form compatible with her domain tools. The alternative is to use a different analysis and display tool that can integrate data from different disciplinary sources, which would still involve a large expenditure of effort.

An example of this challenge exists between water-related disciplines. The atmospheric science and physical oceanography communities are familiar with the tools available for analysis of data in binary netCDF format whereas the hydrology community has traditionally used GIS-based analysis tools and XML-based encodings such as WaterML.

SCALE

Traditionally, practitioners in the solid Earth and hydrology realms deal with research areas that are relatively small and can be isolated as sub-systems with defined boundaries. Subsystems in the ocean and atmosphere cannot be as clearly defined, so oceanography and atmospheric sciences typically use a more global approach to research. For example, a research project involving a river basin where the spatial resolution is in the 10-100 meter range may need to use data from global weather models where the resolution may be in degrees of latitude and longitude (~110 km). In this case, increasing resolution in weather models and observation systems (e.g. ground-based radar) are bringing the research communities together with data and models in the kilometer range. The challenge in many cases is to determine scientifically sound approaches to integrating data that may have significantly different spatial resolution.

SAMPLING GEOMETRIES

A “sampling geometry” specifies an arrangement of parameter measurements or model results used to represent what are typically continuously varying properties of the Earth system. In solid Earth studies, physical samples are taken from specific locations on (or in) the Earth, taken to the lab and analyzed. Hydrologists use measurements from gaging stations at intervals along rivers. The atmospheric and ocean sciences also use station-based observations, but remotely sensed data commonly requires more complex 3-D grid geometries (e.g. spherical), for example pixels in satellite or radar data. The (more or less) regular grids used in prediction models have yet another geometry. Coastal ocean models use grids as well but they are not regularly spaced. Moreover, in cases where there are collections of such datasets, there can be different values for the same parameter at the same point in space-time (e.g. radar reflectivity for two different ground-based radars whose ranges overlap). Likewise weather forecast models are typically run at 3 to 6 hour intervals, so there are different predictions from the different model runs for temperature, pressure, etc. for the same point in space and time in the future. It is important to be aware of this and to develop and share mechanisms for documenting these issues and resolving them.

DIFFERENT MODELS FOR THE SHAPE OF THE EARTH: “DATUMS AND MAP PROJECTIONS”

As noted in the section above on “Scale,” increasing resolution in the observational and forecast systems in the ocean and atmospheric sciences have brought them to the point where the model used for the shape of the Earth makes a difference. When the global weather forecast models were run at resolutions of hundreds of kilometers, the detailed ellipsoidal shape of the Earth was not a concern. However, with observing systems and models getting into the resolution range of a few kilometers, the mapping between observations at points in geodetic space and models run with a spherical Earth can result in a locational error of ~20 km. This is crucial to understand when integrating these forecast model data into disciplines such as hydrology that work at much

higher resolutions. This is a deceptively complicated area because the differences in datums may not be taken into account during the observational data assimilation (initialization) phase of the model run, so the problem can be compounded if one tries an adjustment on the output of these models. Spatial information from a data source often has a specific map projection, which is implicit to users of that data source. All calculations in a system utilize that projection. Calculations can be effected by analyses not properly utilizing the datum information.

3.2 CULTURAL CHALLENGES

In moving towards improved cross-domain interoperability, we must realize that our community is composed of free agents who decide whether to use tools or to record metadata largely based on perceived costs and benefits. Will learning a new data system enable access to data important enough to justify the time required? Will I get sufficient credit by documenting my data to justify the time it requires? Requirements for data management plans and similar measures can have an impact. But a more robust system would include incentives to participate in a community data system or use newly developed cyberinfrastructure. The consideration of costs and benefits to the individual scientist is important in evaluating the utility of data systems and other cyberinfrastructure. A few examples illustrate this issue.

A major obstacle in facilitating data interoperability and reuse, particularly in the long-tail science realm, is that **scientists have traditionally had a strong motivation not to share data**. This is primarily in order to protect one's right to mine a dataset and publish results first, particularly after expending valuable time and effort to create a given dataset. Countering this right is the question of ownership of data acquired using public funding, and under what conditions it is ethical for such data to be withheld. The solution to this problem is to create incentives for data creators to document and share their data, or at least metadata describing the data. One approach is to implement policies that require publication of metadata after moratorium period, and also require direct collaboration with the primary data creators for reuse of the data. This would serve to increase the motivation for data sharing, and may be an appropriate early step, but would not lead to the free and open access and reuse of data that is the ultimate goal. Another approach is to foster better professional rewards for data sharing by improving data citation mechanisms, and the tracking of data citations in an approach similar to publication citation tracking. Other approaches exist, but it is critical that the path forward include appropriate consideration of the motivations and professional requirements of the data creators.

The creation of metadata to sufficiently document datasets for cross-domain reuse presents cultural challenges as well. Although necessary for use by others, time spent on documentation is a dead-weight loss to the scientist collecting the data, at least in the short run; they already know the metadata and derive no benefit from recording it (until they forget it!). As rules and guidelines become more onerous, many data creators (particularly in the long-tail of science) may determine that data sharing is not worth the cost (or in our case, being involved in or contributing to EarthCube). Institutional changes can provide the motivation to document data by giving more credit for publication of well documented datasets, and by making adequate documentation of datasets a specific requirement to publish results in scientific journals. One solution is to identify resources or motivations that can be used to compensate data providers for their additional work to accommodate the EarthCube rules and regulations. Another solution is to develop software tools that minimize researchers' efforts of data documentation, especially in the long tail of science, by largely automating metadata capture from data acquisition to data analysis to data publication.

The long tail of science clearly presents the primary cultural challenges for building successful cross-domain interoperable systems. The needs and wishes of the individual researcher will have to be addressed and fulfilled in order to achieve the full potential of cross-domain data exchange and use.

3.3 ADDITIONAL EXAMPLES FROM USE CASES

To clarify challenges and requirements of cross-domain use, we considered two additional use cases besides the Global Rivers Observatory and Coastal Zone Observatories mentioned above. One of the use cases focuses on modeling hypoxia in the Gulf of Mexico, and the other on the use of weather radar data in flood forecasting. The weather radar use case provides a valuable perspective on the challenges of integrating data; the hypoxia use case is more illustrative of the current barriers to data access.

3.3.1 GULF OF MEXICO HYPOXIA

Hypoxia refers to low levels of dissolved oxygen in the water. In the northern Gulf of Mexico, a hypoxic region measuring from hundreds to tens of thousands of km² has been present during the summer months for several decades (Turner et al. 2005). The primary cause of this hypoxia is riverine and groundwater inputs of anthropogenic nutrients, primarily nitrogen compounds. The nutrients cause coastal algal blooms, which then die off and their decomposition removes oxygen from the water column². The temperature, stratification, and currents of the coastal waters impact the persistence, strength and geographic extent of the hypoxia, as do additional aspects such as biological factors and solar irradiance. The Gulf of Mexico hypoxia is of substantial management concern because it causes high mortality of animals on the seafloor and in the water column, including commercially-important finfish and shellfish resources.

The Gulf of Mexico hypoxia was selected as a use case because modeling and predicting the hypoxia requires the integration of data from several disciplines – terrestrial hydrology, physical and biological oceanography, and potentially meteorology and satellite sensing – as well as data with different encoding formats, scales, and sampling geometries. To launch the use case work, we first wanted to identify a set of representative data sources to integrate for a hypothetical hypoxia model.

Carrying out this first step of finding appropriate example data to use became an instructive example in the real-world challenges of scientific data access. A recent paper describing a Gulf of Mexico hypoxia model and its outputs was found through a search in Web of Science; the paper is published in an established, peer-reviewed journal. Seven data sets are cited in the paper: the output of the model, one data set that was used for context, and five that were either direct inputs into the model or were used to tune the model or prune the input data.

The team tried to access each data set cited in the paper. The web location given for the output data of the model was examined, but no data were found. The web location for the cited context dataset resolved to a gif image presenting a graph of data with very minimal supporting metadata; the data behind the graph did not appear to be accessible. Of the five datasets used to run the model, one was cited as unpublished data with only the producer's last name and a very vague description. Because the last name was very common, these data were effectively untrackable. The remaining four data sets were cited with web pages. One url did not resolve to a web page, presumably indicating a page that was either moved or deleted. One resolved to a set of directories holding data, but the temporal coverage of the data in the directories did not overlap that cited in the paper. One url resolved

² http://oceanservice.noaa.gov/products/pubs_hypox.html

to a project website, but no data could be found on that website, only a jpeg of a map made from the data. And one resolved to a webpage where, after navigating through several layers of links, a set of Excel data files was found. In summary, of the 7 data sources cited in the paper, only one was available as downloadable data.

An examination of the one accessible data source, the Excel files, indicated that it had a very low readiness for utility based on the metrics defined in Sections 5 and 6. Parameter names did not follow any common controlled vocabulary that was cited. No standard set of metadata was presented. Though information on uncertainty/accuracy was given which is critical to data-reuse, other critical metadata were presented only in a dense, human-readable, linked report. From the webpage given it was difficult to assess whether the data set was available for discovery via any catalogs, or accessible via any standard data access system, though a quick evaluation of the larger program homepage did not advertise these services in any prominent or logical place in the top-level menus.

This example highlights several challenges for the effective interoperability of scientific data, and also challenges to basic data access. With respect to interoperability, not one source was available in a standard format, nor via data catalog or access services (as far as we could assess). With respect to data access challenges, the results indicate a reliance on often-ephemeral project websites instead of established repositories, and a lack of complete data citations to uniquely identify resources: a link to a webpage that holds multiple data sets, and may change through time, is a common practice but is clearly not sufficient.

3.3.1 WEATHER RADAR DATA FOR FLOOD FORECASTING

The second use case example focuses on the reuse of weather radar data in hydrology modeling for flood forecasting. A plethora of new observing systems recently have been added to the national atmosphere observing infrastructure, which not only improves our ability to analyze the current state of the atmosphere but also allows for more intensive cross-domain data reuse in other domains such as hydrology.

Weather radar data are a critical resource in atmospheric science, and we showcase its use in hydrology modeling to present the challenges that cross-domain reuse presents. First, there is a **wide range of radar types and capabilities** across the community which complicates how radar data are applied. For example, radar types can be grouped into mobile, airborne and fixed; from the perspective of usage, radars can be categorized as military, aviation, weather, and multi-use.

Second, there is **no standard data format** common to the various radar types. As an example, we consider three different radar systems- the FAA Terminal Doppler Weather Radar (TDWR), the NWS WSR-88D network (NEXRAD), and a local research radar network (operated by the NSF Engineering Research Center for Collaborative Adaptive Sensing of the Atmosphere, CASA). Data from all three systems are stored in different formats: CASA data are stored in a NetCDF format whereas WSR-88D data are stored in a native format known as msg3. These various radar types and data formats complicate usage when dealing with multiple radar data sets and exacerbate interoperability issues between different radar data sets.

Third, **the complexity of radar vocabularies** inhibits radar data use. While radar terms are easily understood by domain experts, such vocabulary is obtuse to non-domain domain scientists. However, to apply the proper quality control and use radar data appropriately requires a high degree of knowledge about the data. Thus, radar metadata must be comprehensive and thorough for proper reuse by non-radar experts.

Fourth, there is **no common community metadata standard** for radar metadata. Each individual radar system includes its own unique information within its metadata. For example, while radar metadata for the WSD-88D is rather extensive, less commonly used radar systems such as the TDWR and CASA include only relatively limited information despite the richer capability of the research radars like CASA.

A final difficulty lies in the **access and availability** of radar data. Access to some systems may require payment to a third party vendor, or may simply be prohibited. For example, the WSR-88D radar data are available in real-time and archived through Unidata LDM feeds. TDWR data provides restricted real-time access with no archival, while CASA provides both real-time and archived data but only by special request or to collaborators.

Table 3.1 lists possible problems, as well as their causes and potential solutions, for facilitating cross-domain use of radar data. Level II radar data that are widely available (such as through LDM) have not been “cleaned” of the effects of clean air echoes, hail, undersampling, and melting layer contamination. Hail contamination provides an instructive example. Hail creates high reflectivity readings which can be misinterpreted as high rainfall. Meteorologists can detect hail easily by eyeballing a visual plot of reflectivity or by applying data mining algorithms, and then can go back to Level II data and process it by removing hail contamination. However, hydrologists, untrained in the use of radar data, face the problem of correctly using this cross-domain data.

Problem	Cause	Potential Solution
Hail contamination	Assumes high rainfall rate	Use of dual-pol, QC
Bright band	Ice at mid-levels biases dBZ	Real-time QC, 2 radar beams
Ground clutter	Wind farms, blockage	Use of Neural Net, velocity
Radar attenuation	High-frequency radars	Real-time QC model, fix
Anomalous propagation	High stable environment	Use of Level 1, velocity
Velocity de-aliasing	High velocity returns	Real-time QC
Radar calibration	Poor maintenance	Post QC
Over/under estimation below beam	Radar too far from area of interest; undersampled	Improved radar sampling; additional surface input
Poor time sampling	Radar 5-min volume sampling	Improved temporal sampling
Evapotranspiration under beam	Lack of surface information	Additional surface data
Spatial interpolation	Polar to Cartesian coordinates	Interpolation algorithm
Use of Reflectivity	Does not measure rain directly	Calibration against surface data

Table 3.1. Issues for flood forecasting when using radar data

The hail contamination scenario shows the importance of understanding data context and quality (as mentioned in section 3.1.1). Quality control can be a possible solution to the issues and challenges in the cross-domain use of radar data. Before actually processing the raw data for cross-domain analysis, a quality control process (in the middle of Figure 3.3) could be performed on the raw data to ensure the correct cross-domain data use. Some automatic examination and correction such as clutter removal, radar calibration, hail contamination removal, etc., could be applied to the raw data. To simplify the process for non-domain scientists, a complete end-to-end workflow could be designed to perform work on the corrected raw data from the quality control process to interpolating the data from a polar to a common Cartesian grid, merging radar data sets, converting radar reflectivity, and integrating radar data with other data on to a grid (Figure 3.3).

The radar use case demonstrates the difficulties and challenges in discovering and using radar data in cross-domain research. Many common yet significant problems may exist with the radar data sets for which the non-domain scientist may simply not be aware. The hail contamination example shows that understanding metadata quality and data context is critical to the correct use of radar data, and that the ultimate goal of cross-domain usage is conveying enough critical information to non-domain experts such that the data are not misused.

Figure 3.3. An example workflow that could be used to make radar data more useful for cross-domain research

3.4 TRENDS AND DRIVERS

We believe that the technical and social challenges described above are fundamental and are likely to persist for many years. Integrating data and computations across domains at the level of conceptual models, given different intents and contexts of data collection and analysis, may not be completely solvable, but approaching it iteratively will provide valuable insights. We are dealing with a highly dynamic evolving situation influenced by both rapid technological advances and generally more conservative socio-cultural patterns of research enterprise and technology adoption.

The key technical drives and trends include: growth of data volumes and complexity of information; proliferation of new scientific data; higher degrees of data availability; proliferation of cloud-based solutions; smart sensors; increasing availability and reliance on real time data streams; and accelerating development and acceptance of formal domain models and semantic descriptions. Scalability will be a central issue as the data volumes and diversity of applications and users increase, exacerbating metadata challenges described above and requiring efficient automated tools for publishing, discovering and accessing different resources. Compliance with community-adopted standard information models and services as well as efficient use of cloud resources are the key pre-requisites of our ability to manage scalability issues in EarthCube.

On the social side, the key shifts are to more open and transparent information management; use of open source software; crowdsourcing of both data collection and data management and analysis; citizen science and community engagement; and increased diversity in adoption culture and technologies. The rapidly increasing scale of community involvement also underscores the need for community consensus on standards for data and model interchange and for automated standards-based interoperability solutions, which are the focus of this roadmap.

4. REQUIREMENTS

A number of methodologies have been developed for gathering and communicating requirements for complex systems, at conceptual, technical and engineering levels. One widely-used system within OGC is called the Reference Model for Open Distributed Processing (RM-ODP), also known as ISO/IEC 10746 (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RM-ODP>). Such an approach is helpful in separating out levels of scope and detail into multiple viewpoints: the *Enterprise* viewpoint describing purpose, scope and policies of the system; the *Information* viewpoint describing information sources and models; the *Computational* viewpoint describing types of services and protocols; and the two implementation layer viewpoints: *Engineering* (describing architecture and interactions between system components) and *Technology* (describing hardware and software.) The 10-section structure of EarthCube roadmap template aligns with the main components of RM-ODP, with sections 1-4 representing the Enterprise viewpoint, and section 5 representing the information and computational viewpoints, and subsequent sections extending into the design of EarthCube processes.

This section lays out our overall approach to requirements gathering in EarthCube, in particular requirements for effective cross-domain communication. It presents several specific processes for continuous requirements analysis based on inventories of use cases, environmental model catalogs, and domain systems components, and also discussed requirements generation for a number of coupled models. It concludes by outlining a community consensus process for requirements gathering, in particular in the context of developing standards for data and model interoperability.

4.1 BOTTOM-UP AND TOP-DOWN APPROACHES TO DETERMINING CROSS-DOMAIN READINESS REQUIREMENTS

We view cross-domain interoperability as a process of enabling effective communication between within-domain and cross-domain researchers. Thus, requirements do not define a product, but rather, a process. That process has no defined end point; it is expected to be a continual process of matching developing needs with appropriate responses. Focusing on the process is important given the long-term expectations of EarthCube and the rapid changes in the technological and organizational landscape of geoinformatics.

There are two distinct but comingled processes for determining EarthCube cross-domain interoperability requirements, based upon bottom-up and top-down approaches:

- **The bottom-up approach** is to study existing stories of cross-domain data use: success stories, in an effort to determine what strategies are effective and what requirements would enable *similar and foreseen data reuse*, and failure stories, in an effort to determine what circumstances block effective data reuse.
- **The top down approach** is to consider and determine the qualities of data that – independent of the specifics of use – seem to best enable *unforeseen data reuse*.

These processes inform each other. The bottom-up study of success stories identifies recurring approaches and themes that have been successful in enabling data reuse and are thus candidates for enabling “foreseen” data reuse. The top-down study of the reuse-enabling attributes of data creates a catalog of approaches and data quality factors that can be used to craft new data sources that best enable unforeseen success stories, that in turn inform the bottom-up studies.

The following diagram depicts the primary deliverables that pass between principals to this process, where each arrow represents a responsibility to provide information:

Figure 4.1: Requirements gathering and fulfillment for cross-domain interoperability.

In the figure, blue arrows represent primary directions of communication while grey arrows represent feedback. Scientists contribute success stories and successful strategies to the bottom-up studies, which in turn catalogue trends and common approaches among cross-domain uses. These inform top-down studies, along with feasibility considerations for what is possible and reasonable to expect from data providers. Top-down studies recommend best practices to scientific governance, which relays priorities to technical governance, which in turn relays strategies to data providers for implementation. Finally, the loop closes when scientists use new data to generate new success stories.

4.2 ACHIEVING AND DOCUMENTING SUCCESS

Cross-domain interoperability is a moving target; advances in cross-domain interoperability require a mix of data products that satisfy a spectrum of needs between **lowest common denominator** needs common to large populations of scientists, and **highest common denominator** needs of a select few scientists who elect to push the limits of existing data and methods.

Successes of “highest common denominator” approaches inform scientific governance and naturally lead to changes in the definition of what constitute the “lowest common denominator” approaches. Thus, there is a need for scientific governance to balance the needs of the few with the needs of the many, by:

1. Supporting bold experiments that might lead to generally reusable data products, and
2. Using results of those experiments to redefine the baseline or “lowest common denominator” data products available to all researchers.

The community consensus process for cross-domain interoperability is based upon the idea that the “lowest common denominator” approaches are scientifically justifiable via direct evidence. It is the consensus of our group that this process never ends, and that the “end-product” for “interoperability” is a process of communication that determines new requirements and solutions, rather than a solution in itself.

4.3 DERIVING REQUIREMENTS FROM USE CASES: THE PROCESS

The proposed processes for understanding requirements include solicitation and analysis of use case descriptions that follow use case templates, developing inventories of community resources, and exploration of model catalogs as proxies for use cases.

Use cases are a key source for deriving community requirements and development priorities in the bottom-up approach. As shown in Figure 1, continuous analysis of cross-domain use cases and finding common patterns among them is a central process that supports development and steering of the cross-domain agenda in EarthCube. However, use cases are difficult to collect, and their descriptions are typically unstructured and difficult to analyze and derive requirements from. Our team has analyzed the initial survey of use cases solicited by NSF prior to the November Charrette. Open-ended formulation of most questions and lack of focus on specific cross-domain interoperability issues made it difficult to distill user requirements; as a result, the wealth of information in the survey remained underutilized. While use case surveys remains a key instrument for communicating requirements, they can be more effective if: a) the input is solicited in a more structured form, b) use case surveys are integrated with inventories of cross-domain models, and c) the survey is organized such that information entered by previous respondents (or filled out by survey authors) is available for review and annotation by subsequent respondents. Therefore, in this EAGER project we are adopting strategies for continuous use case acquisition and elaboration with engagement of a wide user community, in particular cataloguing and exploring use cases previously developed in OGC and ESIP Federation interoperability experiments and testbeds, by federal agency partners (e.g. USGS), and in large multidisciplinary projects such as the Critical Zone Observatory and the Global Rivers Observatory. In addition, we propose the following processes to derive community requirements during EarthCube development and maturation.

4.3.1 FORMULATION OF USE CASE TEMPLATES AND SOLICITING USE CASES IN THESE TEMPLATES.

The templates reflect typical situations distilled from research practice in many geoscience domains. Users would characterize interoperability challenges that are important to resolve for their applications, and elaborate with specifics/examples based on their experience. A non-exhaustive list, emphasizing cross-domain research situations, includes:

- Data discovery across multiple catalogs (of data, models, etc.), in which catalog organization, levels of granularity, and metadata profiles are different across domains
- Interpretation of terms and concepts from an unfamiliar domain; this may be in a search context requiring mapping of keywords, or in a data utilization context to understand the meaning of

resource content. The situation requires accessing vocabulary resources, and matching terms from differently organized domain vocabularies. The vocabularies may follow a range of knowledge organization conventions, from flat lists of terms in ASCII files and spreadsheets to domain thesauri expressed in SKOS and providing a limited set of relationships between terms, to domain or trans-domain semantics expressed in various versions of OWL/RDF that cover a wide spectrum from “shallow” to “deep semantics” ontology languages

- Retrieving data or running code or workflows from different domains, when the query and processing interfaces differ. Such interfaces may comply with OGC service interface specifications (reviewed in Section 5), with other community standards, or be ad hoc and tuned to specific sources, which may severely limiting the ease or scalability of integration
- Information from different domain systems is obtained in different formats and encodings, even when observational data or model outputs are expected to be compatible. While it is expected that different scientific feature types are described using different domain model semantics, following community encoding standards (such as OGC’s Observations and Measurements) improves chances for opportunistic integration as different datasets follow shared conventions for encoding temporal, spatial and thematic components of measurements. In reality, researchers encounter many ad hoc encodings, formats and protocols, and different conceptual models, most of them non-standard and not ready for opportunistic re-use
- A new data source (e.g. a source of precipitation data, such as weather radar) becomes available for a model; it has many attractive characteristics (timeliness, better coverage and spatial resolution, etc.) but may also have characteristics not usually taken into account by modelers from other domains because the semantics of the previous source of this data was different
- To instantiate or calibrate a model, a researcher needs data at an extent and spatio-temporal resolution that differs from the extent and resolution of the source; validity of upscaling or downscaling data from an unfamiliar domain is often unclear and challenging to evaluate
- Data from another domain contains blanks or outliers, which must be respectively gap-filled or removed if sufficient metadata and guidance is provided from the domain on whether such gap-filling or removal would be valid

These and similar challenges are explicitly included in the use case templates we are proposing to employ in use case inventory creation. Sample use case templates, with preliminary entries for the hypoxia and the flood forecasting use cases, are available in the project’s Dropbox (see <http://earthcube.ning.com/group/interop/page/project-synopsis> for accessing Dropbox content.)

The research situations listed above highlight specific interoperability challenges and form the lower level in the three-tier use case model adopted at the July 10th post-Charrette consensus workshop of Concept award PIs (Figure 4.2). This purpose of this layer is to explore technical infrastructure components offered as solutions to specific interoperability challenges. At the next level, “large use cases”, or “use case themes” (e.g. “Hypoxia in the Gulf” described earlier; 10 of such themes have been identified at the post-Charrette workshop), may include several specific use cases, integrating them in a richer research scenario. We expect that pilot development for each of such use case themes will rely on a number of interconnected technological solutions explored at the lower level: the focus of the pilots would be on exploring interoperability between these individual components, to support one or more lines of research within a use case theme. To be successful the pilots should be implemented in conjunction with ongoing cross-disciplinary projects such as the CZO and GRO described in the previous section: these provide an environment where such pilots would be defined, developed and validated with respect to

science requirements, and eventually adopted. The scope of the pilots would be different depending on the set of geoscience research domains engaged, on the number of specific use cases / interoperability challenges being addressed within the pilot, and on science questions and lines of research developed by the partner science projects and the larger science research community.

Figure 4.2. The three-tier use case model adopted at the July 10th EarthCube consensus workshop

Once the way to elicit and represent cross-domain use cases becomes more structured with use case templates (while at the same time allowing scientists to express their needs not fitting in the templates as well), it would become easier to distill requirements, identify needed capabilities, develop solutions and validate them in real world applications, in particularly in the world of the “long tail of science.” Additional work is needed to develop the situations above into concise templates that can be used during community workshops or in online use case surveys.

4.3.2. A CURATED INVENTORY OF DOMAIN SYSTEM COMPONENTS.

This process has been started within the current EAGER grant, with the initial focus on CI components that support discovery, interpretation, access and integration of information from different domain information systems (available from <http://earthcube.ning.com/group/interop/page/community-inventories>). Assessment of such components from the perspective of the readiness model would help point to common and unique components of each system, and degree of their compliance with standard protocols, including service interface standards and encodings. Some results of this approach are reviewed in Section 5.

4.3.3. ANALYSIS OF MODEL CATALOGS

An additional way to elicit requirements and priorities from use cases is by exploring catalogs of environmental models and model components. Development of realistic use cases depends on significant domain knowledge and

experience, and ultimately requires real datasets for validation, analysis, and application. Assembling these ingredients can be a time-consuming and *resource-constrained* process. Given these challenges, eliciting and prioritizing requirements from collections of models is an attractive alternative. In a sense, models are algorithmic representations of formally described real-world use cases. Many are in active use for developing forecasts, risk analyses, and other socially beneficial applications; others are essential research tools in their respective domains. Models provide a rich body of information that could help reveal the relationships among the subdomains of earth system science, and how they can or might be traversed – in a sense indicating the “most traveled” pathways in the EarthCube, which in turn would point to the need of having robust interfaces between these pairs of domain systems. The next subsection discusses a preliminary study.

4.4 PATHWAYS THROUGH EARTHCUBE: A PROCESS FOR EVALUATING DEVELOPMENT PRIORITIES

Models are highly heterogeneous entities, and in order to analyze them uniformly, they must be described by consistent metadata. An initial goal is simply to characterize the knowledge domains treated by or incorporated into each model. Visualization and further analysis of the compiled metadata should provide a window into the relative extent to which various domains have been treated or bridged by computational models and their corresponding use cases, and may point the way to the most immediate opportunities for exploring and refining conceptual as well as computational pathways through the Earth Cube.

Catalogs of models for the earth system sciences provide a relevant and accessible source of data for use in the analyses described above. We have begun to examine a few such collections, and can offer some preliminary observations.

Not all catalogs provide metadata that explicitly identify the domains treated by the models they contain. For a subset of the CSDMS model catalog (see e.g. http://csdms.colorado.edu/wiki/Model_download_protal), we selected a simple vocabulary for designating domains, and used it to create a matrix showing which individual models address or incorporate which knowledge domains. This process entailed human review and parsing of the English-language descriptions included in model metadata. Results to date are compiled at <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheet/ccc?key=0AgBcElb5y58vdFVvQXdxWE11aXE1cHdVMkZVN2RrcHc#gid=0>.

We have experimented with visualizing the metadata of some collections, using the SilverLight Pivot application. This effort to date has included models from the European TESS project (<http://maxim.ucsd.edu/tessmodels3/>), a set of ESMF coupled models (<http://maxim.ucsd.edu/esmfmodels/>), and a collection of OpenMI, CSDMS, and ESMF compliant model components cataloged by NOAA (<http://maxim.ucsd.edu/NoaaModelsList/>). By selecting the histogram view in these depictions, and sorting on “domain,” “realm,” or a similar designation, it is possible to view the distribution of models with respect to domains of scientific knowledge.

These initial explorations indicate that the coverage is uneven: there are many more models for some knowledge domains than there are for others. They also indicate that metadata are inconsistent across catalogs, and that the semantics for the vocabularies used to enumerate domains are not well defined.

The online visualization application for model catalogs allows users to annotate models, edit their descriptions, and specify which disciplines they draw data from. Once models are annotated with domains from which they draw data, it is possible to represent connectivity between different domains in EarthCube. This would point to pairs of domains that have consistent and intense data exchanges, and would therefore require robust data

exchange interfaces. An example of such an online connectivity map (“a map of EarthCube pathways”), built from annotated models in (<http://maxim.ucsd.edu/tessmodels3/>), is shown in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 A snapshot of an online interactive visualization showing connections between domains as derived from about 200 annotated environmental models in the TESS model catalog. Sector sizes reflect the number of models in each domain, and connections show relative numbers of “data pathways” between the domains (<http://maxim.ucsd.edu/crossdomain>)

We anticipate that such a connectivity analysis and visualization, when triangulated with other user surveys and use case inventories, would a) support requirements and priorities generation, and b) encourage researchers, educators and students to explore and contribute to model catalogs which would become an EarthCube community resource.

4.5 ANALYSIS OF PRE-MODEL WORKFLOWS TO GENERATE REQUIREMENTS

In addition to exploring environmental models as proxies of use cases to identify cross-domain pathways in the EarthCube, we describe an additional continual process to generate requirements: by examining pre-processing workflows of coupled models. The following example couple model categories highlight common challenges and requirements.

4.5.1 ATMOSPHERIC FORECAST MODELS:

Global Weather Forecast Models

Data from a wide variety of sources (weather station and buoy obs, radars, satellites, GPSmet systems, and other sources) are gathered into a process called data assimilation which is a physics and statistics based model in itself. The assimilation process results in a gridded representation of the state of the atmosphere at a given time. This gridded representation of the atmosphere is used as an initial condition for a forecast model that extrapolates the state of the atmosphere into the future. Hence we get the global forecast models from NCEP in the US, ECMWF in Europe, CPTEC in Brazil, CMC in Canada.

Making the assimilation process available to researchers is a major undertaking. Having assimilation, downscaling and upscaling, and the models themselves available via web services is another challenging objective.

Regional forecast models:

For regional models (e.g., North American, European, etc.), a separate assimilation process can be run to put the observational data from that region onto a higher resolution grid or the global model output can be downscaled to higher resolution and used as initial conditions and boundary conditions for a regional forecast model such as the North American Model (NAM).

Local forecast models:

Very high resolution local forecast models can be run using the output of the regional model for initial and boundary conditions. Of course, higher resolution DEM representations of the local terrain are also needed in each case. Many university and other research groups as well as commercial weather services run such models.

Having these models available as web services with access to downscaled data from regional and global models is a challenge.

4.5.2 COUPLED ATMOSPHERIC/OCEAN MODELS

The oceanography community has its own equivalent set of modeling processes, the details of which will have to be filled in by experts in that field. But, for the cross-domain discussion, it is important to note that there exist coupled atmospheric / ocean models. The [COAMPS](#) (Coupled Ocean/Atmosphere Mesoscale Prediction System) and [NOGAPS](#) (Navy Operational Global Atmospheric Prediction System) are examples of such models run at the Fleet Numerical Meteorology and Oceanography Center.

4.5.3 COUPLED ATMOSPHERIC/HYDROLOGICAL MODELS

Some research groups and river forecast centers use the output of regional and local weather forecast models as input to hydrological models. In this case, one of the challenges is to get the gridded data from the weather model into a form that fits the irregular shape of a drainage basin. Of course additional data from other sources come into play. Detailed information about the land surface, including permeability and saturation are needed.

Getting the data from the atmospheric models into a form useful in the hydro models presents many challenges. Having the hydro models as web services is another.

4.5.4 COUPLED ATMOSPHERIC/HYDRO/STORM SURGE MODELS

In the case of hurricane landfall, models that take into account modeling of storm surge in addition to weather and hydrological conditions are important. This brings into play a number of additional challenges such as the irregular grids that are used in models of the coastal oceans. Developing standard representations of these grids has been a difficult challenge for several years now.

Transformations among the atmospheric and hydro model output forms into the irregular grids and back is a challenge faced in this area of research.

4.6. COMMUNITY REQUIREMENTS: THE CONSENSUS PROCESS

Establishing community consensus about data publication and exchange protocols, both domain-specific and cross-domain, is a key requirement for successful communication outlined in the readiness model. Experience of successful standard bodies has shown that, to be successful, this process should be formal, open and transparent, with a well-defined sequence of steps and broad community involvement. In the geosciences, such standard and specification development bodies have included the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) Federation. We believe that the EarthCube initiative would benefit from leveraging these existing structures, rather than attempting to replace them with similar bodies. There are several reasons for this approach: (1) over the years, the geoscience-oriented standard and specification development bodies have established working relationships with other computing standards organizations, such as W3C and OASIS, as well as with the International Standards Organization (ISO), (2) the rigorous standardization process that involves sufficient testing, validation and compliance testing, made thus developed standards attractive for US federal and other national agencies, as well as international initiatives such as INSPIRE and GEOSS and UN organizations such as WMO; they in turn provide large volumes of federally collected geoscience data to academic researchers; (3) development of standards and specifications is an open process driven by respective communities of practice that include members of academia, industry and governments; (4) standards developed by these communities of practice must rely on baseline information standards which supports commonality and interoperability between datasets exposed in such standard forms; (5) the established standards bodies provide infrastructure for ongoing management and evolution of standards responding to new requirements and implementation experiences. NSF-funded projects have played an important role in developing such standards. For example, the joint OGC/WMO Hydrology Domain Working Group is developing a standard for exchanging water information (WaterML 2.0, which is about to be voted as an OGC standard in June 2012): this standard is based both on earlier work within the NSF-funded CUAHSI HIS project (WaterML 1.0) and on previous work of CSIRO and OGC on the Observations and Measurements specification and the Water Data Transfer Format (WDTF). Similarly, the de-facto standard for multi-dimensional observational and model grids (NetCDF) was developed originally by NSF-funded UNIDATA and UCAR, but recently approved as an OGC international standard. Besides the broad international impact of this work, it provides an ultimate degree of validation of concepts used in the standard development. To leverage this established infrastructure in EarthCube, we envision an ongoing EarthCube activity focused on assessment of applicability of existing standards, and collecting and organizing cross-domain use cases and gathering requirements to present them to the standards bodies for consideration in the development of new versions of standards.

The timeline presented in section 8 proposes that one of the first steps in developing cross-domain interoperability support is the compilation of requirement based on collecting and elaborating use cases from the community, and the inventory and analysis of models, and the readiness assessment. Compiled requirements will be reviewed

through online forums, and finally in a face to face meeting that will be used to establish community priorities. We anticipate that requirements and priorities will evolve as the EarthCube becomes operational, and through the normal progression of scientific and technological development. Updating of cross-domain interoperability requirements will need to take place in the framework of the larger EarthCube governance scheme, informed by ongoing community input to evaluate existing infrastructure and newly developed components. Regularly scheduled (biannual) community meetings to review progress and update milestones should be part of an operational system.

5. STATUS

5.1 THE INITIAL REFERENCE MODEL, AND KEY CI COMPONENTS CONSIDERED IN THE ROADMAP

This section describes the current status of domain infrastructures and general development trends in both the geosciences and cyberinfrastructure development, following specific challenges and requirements described in the previous sections. From the perspective of cross-domain interoperability, we organize the presentation by key types of CI resources that enable discovery, interpretation, data access, data integration and processing across geoscience domains.

Our experience in several disciplinary data system, and the collection of domain architectures we have been assembling, suggests that these functions are typically represented in the following basic infrastructure components which need to be present to enable cross-domain interoperability in the geosciences: metadata catalogs, at the appropriate community defined granularity, that provide standard discovery services over datasets, data access services and other resources of the domain; vocabularies that support unambiguous interpretation of domain resources and metadata; services used to access data repositories and other resources including models, visualizations and workflows, and support data processing, modeling and visualization; and formal information models that define structure and semantics of the information returned on service requests.

A general vision of EarthCube logical organization (

Figure 5.1) is of an integrated information system (or a “system of systems”) that includes research observatories generating large volumes of observations and analytical/simulation results, domain systems that publish the information according to community conventions about data models, vocabularies and protocols, and a cross-domain knowledge layer that includes federated catalogs, normalized and curated datasets integrating data from domain systems and observatories, cross-linked vocabularies, service brokers, as well as social networking, governance and compute infrastructure. This conceptual diagram is consistent with the consensus EarthCube diagram presented earlier (Figure 1.1) and emphasizes the central role of the cross-domain interoperability layer enabling discovery, interpretation, data access and integration across domain infrastructures: the component named “EC Infrastructure” in Figure 1.1 has similar content and functionality to the upper layer in Figure 5.1, while “domain clouds” in Figure 1.1 emphasize the same functions of cross-domain systems as the vertical “domain boxes” in Figure 5.1.

Domain infrastructures have been the focus of NSF investment in geoscience cyberinfrastructure over many years, and need to be leveraged within EarthCube. Presently, the interoperability of the domain infrastructures is limited. Several social and technical challenges contributing to this limitation have been reviewed in earlier sections. One of the central issues is lack of a separately governed cross-domain interoperability layer. Another central issue is lack of standardization of the infrastructure components listed above. General standards for these components have been proposed, e.g. Open Geospatial Consortium’s (OGC) Catalog Services for the Web (CSW) for interoperable catalogs, Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) for vocabularies, OGC Sensor Observation Service (SOS) for requesting observational data, and OGC Observations and Measurements as a general information model and encoding schema, with emerging domain specifications such as the OGC WaterML 2.0, GeoSciML or CSML.

By utilizing these or similar standards, EarthCube-enabled research designs can take advantage of data discovery across disciplines using the commonality in key data characteristics related to shared models of spatial features, time measurements, and observations. Data can be discovered via federated catalogs and linked nomenclatures from neighboring domains, while standard data services can be used to transparently compile composite data products.

Both standardization of key interfaces supporting discovery, interpretation, access and integration of domain resources, and development of cross-domain mappings and brokering solutions, are critical components of EarthCube CI. A mature cross-domain CI needs a combination of the both approaches. There is a strong trend towards development of standards-compliant software components, as support for community standards is added to mainstream software and a growing number of data and other resources are becoming available via standard service interfaces. For government data providers, this trend has been recently highlighted in the Digital Government Strategy (Executive Office of the President, 2012). At the same time, new scientific feature types are being constantly introduced by research practice and may initially lack standardization: for these cases information mapping and brokering solutions are required. The two approaches are complementary and strongly interrelated.

Figure 5.1 Initial model of an EarthCube logical organization

5.2 GENERALIZED ARCHITECTURE

The inventory of domain information system architectures that we compiled (<http://earthcube.ning.com/group/interop/page/community-inventories>) demonstrates a wide variety of approaches. On the one side of the spectrum is a fully standardized architecture, based on OGC services and focused on delivering spatial information. On the other side is a generalized data distribution architecture targeted at mashups and desktop applications. Neither architecture guarantees that delivered data are documented at a level needed for reuse/repurposing, as it may expose a fully documented data source, or a poorly documented source. Reliable data reuse may require a user's interaction to interpret the information. Exemplar architectures of the two types are presented below.

5.2.1 SPATIAL INFORMATION DELIVERY

In the first approach, system components are exposed via standardized service interfaces and domain specifications; a catalog of data, services and other resources is maintained, and data semantics is conveyed through community standards. AUSCOPE has developed a Spatial Information Services Stack (SISS) using open standard services (**Figure 5.3**). This stack includes all the components of a node to be a standalone information services stack that utilizes OGC and other information standards. An architecture like SSIS can target different levels of standards use. The lowest common denominator approach uses generic standards (e.g. Simple features GML, Dublin Core Metadata) which do not necessarily communicate community semantics. Such standards are extensible in an ad hoc manner. This approach lacks the richness of a community standard. By contrast, approaches which use domain-specific profiles of the common standards (e.g. GroundwaterML, GeosciML, INSPIRE or EOS metadata), allow for semantics of a domain to be encapsulated. In general, this is a high barrier to entry because the output of the services is customized for specific community semantics. These standards may be more complex for the novice to understand.

The lowest common denominator approach targets generic geospatial clients, such as desktop GIS applications. This enables a variety of clients to visualize the basic information exposed in the SSIS architecture. By contrast, community standards require that custom client applications or client plug-ins be created to access services and

take advantage of richer domain semantics.

Figure 5.3. Spatial Information Services Stack.

The SISS is an example of generalized architecture. It is implemented as a set of standardized services using Open Geospatial Consortium specifications, and other standards, such as W3C for SKOS vocabularies.

5.2.2 GENERALIZED DATA ACCESS

The Environmental Informatics Framework (EIF), initiated by Microsoft Research, is an exemplar framework of the second type (Figure 5.3). The EIF is basically a conceptual data bus that applications can access. Data sources are exposed using the Open Data Protocol (OData), which transports information using XML ATOM and JSON formats. OData feeds utilize a consistent pattern in their URI's. The formats and the URL's simplify implementation of both servers and clients. OData has a low barrier for entry, but data semantics are not maintained. Such a system would represent a high barrier to cross domain use, since there isn't sufficient information for interpreting and integrating information at the middleware. Such a system is targeted at desktop and mashup use of data, where data are interpreted and integrated at the application level by desktop user or mashup creator.

Google's GData is a similar approach. Various Google API's expose Google data feeds, or can consume feeds in documented GData formats.

Current State of Data Ecosystem

Figure 5.4. Environmental Informatics Framework

5.3 STANDARDS-COMPLIANCE OF KEY CI COMPONENTS ACROSS DISCIPLINES

In our review of existing domain data systems, they appear to exhibit different levels of community convergence to standards for interoperability components, including catalogs, vocabularies, services and information models – which in turn is a key indicator of domain system readiness for cross-domain data discovery and re-use. At the general level, these services are listed in Table 5.1. Implementations of these basic themes differ. In some information communities, like the NASA DAAC's, data centers collect, catalog, and distribute data products. They may also provide basic processing service to subset the data delivered to the user. In other communities, such as CUAHSI, infrastructure (software and/or specifications) are provided to individual organizations, and a central organization may provide some cataloging services. In other communities, there may be no common cyber-infrastructure. Our initial inventory of domain system components, compiled with contributions from many domain system experts (available from <http://earthcube.ning.com/group/interop/page/community-inventories>) organizes domain systems by these components, and also indicates whether a community supports a consensus effort focused on standardizing domain information models and data access protocols. The initial inventory (in web-accessible and openly-editable Google spreadsheets) currently contains information on approximately 90 data sources from over 50 organizations; the information accessible from the data source is categorized by groups of services (**Table 5.1**; see Readiness Measures below), and by domains (**Table 5.2**). The same domains were used in characterizing model inputs for models and model components listed in catalogs that we use as part of requirements gathering process (as described in Section 4).

Table 5.1. Generalized Categories of Services

	Description
Catalogs	A register of resources with some mechanism for searching
Vocabularies	A listing of terminology utilized by their community
Data Services	Services for accessing data in a structured format, provides some filtering capabilities and formatting options. Not just http or ftp file downloads
Modeling Services	Services for processing of data
Visualization Services	online visualization tools, such as a web portal or a web map service
Information Models	Documented models for content, structure, and encoding of information used in the managing of exchange of data
Consensus Effort	Organized activity that manages information models, service profiles, catalog, vocabularies and other governance activities
Identifiers	System to maintain permanent identifiers and bindings to representations for identified resources

Analysis of this inventory reveals that the API's and the formats to access data vary across domains. When data are collected for a model run, a great deal of effort is required to understand, collect, and reformat data. As a result, when models are run the data are moved to the modeling system. The data collection and evaluation are not automated processes for most models. It is not unexpected that data collection process requires the most effort, because most models do not start out attempting to solve large problems, they start out addressing issues of a particular researcher, or research group, and over time they gain acceptance and wider usage. As they gain acceptance, tools to automate the data preparation and validation are created. Over time, the original data source may provide a data product(s) targeted at specific communities or domains.

In communities such as CUAHSI, a great effort may be spent on creating common formats and services, and getting data into these formats. But less effort is spent on validating this transformation for a range of domain measurement types and contexts. Improvement of this transformation is an incremental process.

Table 5.2. Generalized Thematic Categories

Atmosphere	Biological Species	Ecology
Climatology	Climate Records	Digital Elevation Model/topography
Environment	Extreme Events	Geochemistry
Geospatial	Geology	Glaciology
Geodesy	Hydrology	Meteorology
Oceanography	Sedimentology	Seismology
Soils	Tectonics	Subsurface Models

5.4 READINESS MEASURES FOR CI COMPONENTS

For each community we evaluated the readiness by assessing the status of cyberinfrastructure elements listed in **Table 5.1**. For each of the systems, we evaluated the categories and assigned a numeric value (**Table 5.11** found after the category descriptions). In general, higher values indicate better compliance with standards. Values are not comparable between categories; a 4 in one category is not equivalent to a 4 in a different category. The categories and meaning are described below. The details of the evaluation are in **Table 5.11**.

5.4.1 CATALOGS

For data sources, we looked for a data listing, or a service allowing the querying of metadata about the datasets. Ideally this is a standardized query interface, such as OGC Catalog services for the Web, or Open Search. Often the catalog is a customized search web page. Ideally, a catalog would be based on complete metadata conforming to some documented profile. Catalogs can be available at several granularities: at the levels of data source, data series, observational series. Catalogs can also be utilized to store metadata about web services.

Table 5.3. Catalog ranking

	Catalog Metadata
M1	Has a data listing
M2	Uses minimal metadata standard, such as Dublin Core
M3	Uses metadata standard, such as FGDC, or INSPIRE
	Catalog Search
S1	Search Interface
s2	Search API, not following a standard
S3	Complies with Opensearch API
S4	Complies with OGC CSW API
	Catalog Harvest
H1	Has a harvest API
H2	OAI API
H3	OGC CSW API

5.4.2 VOCABULARIES

Vocabularies are usually exposed as term lists for specific fields in an information model. Usually they are presented as web pages or excel spreadsheets. In many communities, common terminology is stored in ontology formats such as OWL/RDFS, or SKOS. Ideally, vocabulary terms are managed, and have stable URIs assigned that can be dereferenced to obtain definitions or other representations. There are significant differences across geosciences in ways of representing semantic information; the range of approaches is reviewed in the Semantics roadmap. A formal way of representing semantic information is a pre-requisite for developing semantic cross-walks, which may be automated (e.g. using AgreementMaker , <http://agreementmaker.org/>) depending on the amount of semantic information present in the descriptions.

Table 5.4. Vocabulary ranking

	Vocabulary -- Type
V1	Uses controlled terminology
V2	Community Managed Terminology
V3	SPARQL
	Vocabulary -- Terminology
T1	Listing of terminology, such as web pages
T2	Uses ontology or SKOS

5.4.3 SERVICES

The general client services of the layered architecture were examined, and we evaluated the access to the data, the ability of a system to run models, and the ability to create visualizations. The data services we considered included web services (SOAP, OGC, or REST) or data access standards, including OpenDAP. If a data set is available only by http or FTP, we did not consider this source to provide service access.

A data service provides methods to select and get a structured subset of a larger data resource, potentially with options for different encoding schemes or response content, using requests sent using http GET or POST. Data services may offer content in encoding schemes ranging from comma-delimited text, or simple XML to complex data structures encoded in deeply nested XML, like GeoSciML or GroundwaterML. Services may use community-adopted content and encoding specifications, or non-standard schemes.

DATA ACCESS SERVICES

Access to data can be done at several levels. At the first level, the files of data may be made available via FTP or HTTP. At the second level, the system may provide access to data via a URL which follows some pattern. At the top, a data service such as OpenDAP, or SOAP is used to access the data.

In addition to access, the data may be subset. This may use simple filters (e.g. bounding box, time interval) or a more complex query, where properties of the data are utilized to subset. A processing service may also be utilized to subset the data.

Table 5.5. Data Access Ranking

	Data Access API
A1	Bulk download
A2	Static URL
A3	Web Service
	Data Query API
Q1	Simple query subset
Q2	Complex query
Q3	Processing Subset

PROCESSING SERVICES

Processing services range from simple processes such as data transformation to more complex workflows. The processes may be run on a local machine, or execute on a grid or cloud system. Ideally, the process is exposed via a standard interface, such as the OGC Web Processing Service (WPS). This would enable standardized service registration, discovery and service chaining, and also support long-running processing requests.

Table 5.6. Processing Services ranking

	Process Execution-Remote
R1	Grid execution
R2	Standard interface such as OGC WPS
	Process Execution-Local
L1	Local execution

VISUALIZATION SERVICES

There are many options for visualization, from static graphics, dynamic mapping services, to advanced visualizations, such as interactive charts. A simple static graphic of the information is often used, usually as part of a catalog, to help users identify a dataset. At a higher level an image service, such as an OGC Web Map Service provides dynamic access to the data. At the highest level, the system provides charts, or other graphics such as the result from dynamic process output.

Table 5.7. Visualization services ranking

	Visualization
--	----------------------

V1	Thumbnails or static
V2	Web map service
V3	Interactive Visualization service

5.4.4 INFORMATION MODELS

An information model defines the content used to represent some resource of interest in a computer system, typically by specifying a collection of entities (objects, features...), attributes (properties) associated with each entity, and relationships between the entities. The information model determines what data can be communicated. An information model can be encoded (implemented) in various ways; in the interoperability arena, the encodings of interest are designed for serialization, packaging, and electronic transmission. Some example encoding schemes include NetCDF, XML, XML-based application schema like GML, and JSON. Cross – domain interoperability requires well documented information models and community profiles for encoding information. Service endpoints developed for a specific purpose that do not communicate the full details of a data source are evaluated as ad-hoc.

Table 5.8. Information Model Conceptual ranking

	Information Model Conceptual
C0	Unspecified
C1	Domain/Conceptual Model using UML
C2	Domain/Conceptual Model using UML based on OGC or ISO standards
	Information Model as XML
X1	XML Format. Schema may not be specified
X2	Xml Schema
	Information Model as SQL
S1	Provides an SQL Schema

5.4.5 COMMUNITY CONSENSUS EFFORTS

This characteristic indicates whether a community has a continual governed process to develop a consensus about data exchange standards, or has developed some consensus products. Examples of consensus are best practice documents, or standards process to develop OGC profiles.

Table 5.9. Consensus Effort ranking

	Consensus Effort
C1	Small Community effort with best practices
C2	Large community effort with governance structure, and open standards practices

5.4.6 IDENTIFIERS

Identifiers allow for unique identification of a piece of information. Such identification can occur at a data source, organization, or global level. The most common global infrastructure is a Handle server which is used as the basis for Digital Object Identifiers. Internal and local identifiers are problematic, because organizational standards change, so local identifiers are regularly redone to meet new organizational requirements.

Table 5.10. Identifier Persistence ranking

	Identifier- Persistence
P0	Internal Identifiers, such as row numbers
P1	Local identifiers

P2	Global identifiers
P3	Shared global identifiers utilized, such as handles, DOI, or DataCite

5.4.7 CI COMPONENTS NOT EVALUATED IN THE INITIAL READINESS ASSESSMENT

We did not evaluate data publication mechanisms. Data could be published at different levels of granularity, then aggregated into different types of products, cross-linked and annotated with journal article publications. Cross-domain issues of data publication are discussed later in the chapter.

At this stage, we also have not evaluated management of usage information, authentication-authorization schemes, reporting subsystems, and similar components which, while important, are not critical for supporting the core cross-domain needs of data discovery, interpretation, access and integration. Usage measures were not evaluated either, because there is no standard method of tracking usage. Architectures, such as DataOne, provide a mechanism for logging distributed usage by providing an endpoint to collect usage data from a member node.

Table 5.11. Cross-domain readiness measures for selected information systems

	Catalog			Vocabulary		Data Access		Processing Services		Visualization Services	Information Model			Identifiers	Consensus Effort
	Metadata	Search	Harvest	Vocabulary	Terminology	Access	Query	Remote Execution	Local Execution	Visualization Services	Conceptual	XML	SQL	Persistence	
GEOSS-- <i>Global Earth Observation System of Systems</i>	3	4	3	3	2	3	3	1,2		2	2	2		1	2
GEON -- <i>GEOsciences Network</i>	3	2,4		2,3	2	1	2	1		3	0	1		1	
SONET-- <i>Scientific Observations Network</i>	3			3	2	3	2				2	2			1
EOSDIS -- <i>Earth Observing System Data and Information System</i>	3	3	1		1	3	2	1			2	2		3	2
CZO-- <i>Critical Zone Observatory</i>		2	1		2	3	1				1	1	1	0.1	1
SSIS -- <i>Spatial Information Services Stack</i>	3	4	3	3	2	3	3	1		3	2	2	1	2	1
USGS WaterSmart				3	3	3	2			3	2	2		1	
CUAHSI HIS -- <i>CUAHSI Hydrologic Information System</i>		2	1		2	3	1				1	1	1	0,1	1
USGIN -- <i>United States Geoscience Information Network</i>	3	4	3			3	1			2	2	2		1	

	Catalog			Vocabulary		Data Access		Processing Services		Visualization Services	Information Model			Identifiers	Consensus Effort
	Metadata	Search	Harvest	Vocabulary	Terminology	Access	Query	Remote Execution	Local Execution	Visualization Services	Conceptual	XML	SQL	Persistence	
DataOne	3	2	1			3	1			3	0			2	1
OpenTopograhya	3	1				1	2	1	1	3				3	
OOI -- Ocean Observatories Initiative	2	2	1		2	1,2,3	2	1	1		1	1		2	2
VOEIS -- Virtual Observatory and Ecological Informatics System	2	2		2	1	3	1	1	1	3	1			1	

5.5 READINESS EVALUATION WITH RESPECT TO STANDARDS

There are many standards in use by the earth science communities. Some standards are ubiquitous, such as HTML, XML, and XML schema, while others are specific to a community, such as a specific SOAP API. We have categorized common standards (**Table 5.12**) by type of standard (Service, Foundation, Community and Ad-Hoc), and by general category that they address. We categorized information models and encodings in use by the communities (**Table 5.14**), specifying their types and the formats used. The formats have been simplified to basic types. UML, XML, binary, SQL, and ASCII are self-explanatory. File formats identified with a type of UML utilize a conceptual domain model developed as part of the OGC profiling process. This conceptual domain model is usually expressed for data exchange as an XML schema. A list of acronyms for organizations is show in **Table 5.13**.

Table 5.12. Standards in use. Organization prefix abbreviations are shown in Table 5.13

Standard	Type	Category	Applicability to Cross Domain		
			Sharing and access	Discovery and semantics	Visualization
OGC Web Map Service	Service	Visualization			X
OGC Web Map Tile Service	Service	Visualization			X
OGC Web Feature Service	Service	Visualization, Data	X	X	X
OGC Filter Encoding	Information		X		
OGC Style Layer Descriptor	Information				X
OGC Geography Markup Language	Information Foundation	Information Model	X	X	
OGC Catalogue Service 2.0 HTTP protocol binding (CS-W)	Service	Catalog		X	
FGDC Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata	Information	Information Model		X	
INSPIRE Metadata Standards		Information Model			
OGC Web Coverage Service	Service	Visualization, Data	X		X
OGC Sensor Observation Service	Service	Data	X	X	
OGC SensorML	Information Foundation	Information Model	X	X	
OGC Observations and Measurements	Information Foundation	Information Model	X	X	
OGC WaterML	Information	Information Model	X	X	
OGC Gazetteer Profile of WFS	Information		X	X	
OGC Web Processing Service	Service	Data, Modeling	X		X

Standard	Type	Category	Applicability to Cross Domain		
			Sharing and access	Discovery and semantics	Visualization
OGC Web Service Common (aka "GetCapabilities")	Information	Information Model		X	
W3C XML	Foundation		X		
W3C XMI Schema	Foundation		X		
W3C Web Services Description Language (WSDL)	Service Foundation			X	
W3C Web Application Description Language (WADL)	Service Foundation			X	
W3C Resource Description Formation	Foundation			X	
W3C Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS)	Information	Information Model	X	X	
Representational state transfer (REST)	Service Foundation	Visualization, Data	X	X	X
ITEF JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)	Information		X	X	X
ITEF ATOM			X		
OAI Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)	Service	Catalog	X		
OpenSearch	Service	Catalog			
OData	Foundation Service	Data	X		
GData	Foundation Service	Data	X		
ESIP Federated Search (OpenSearch)	Service	Catalog		X	
ESIP Subset	Service	Data	X		
Collection Casting	Service	Data	X		
Structured Modeling Markup Language (SMML)	Information	Information Model		X	

Table 5.13. Standards Organizations

Acronym	Name	Website
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium	http://www.w3.org/
ISO	International Organization for Standardization	http://www.iso.org/
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium	http://www.opengeospatial.org/
WMO	World Meteorological Organization	http://www.wmo.int/
ITEF	Internet Engineering Task Force	http://www.ietf.org/
OAI	Open Archives Initiative	http://www.openarchives.org/
FGDC	Federal Geographic Data Committee	http://www.fgdc.gov/
INSPIRE	infrastructure for spatial information in	http://inspire.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

	Europe	
Exchange Network	Exchange Network	http://www.exchangenetwork.net/
ADAGUC	Atmospheric data access for the geospatial user community	http://adaguc.knmi.nl/

5.5.1 SERVICE DESCRIPTIONS

5.5.1.1 KEY OPEN GEOSPATIAL CONSORTIUM STANDARDS

These are base interface standards which follow a set of OGC design patterns. They implement a capabilities description, that describes the available services and content in a standard manner. In addition to the capabilities, each interface standard describes a set of methods that are used to implement the service. Methods can be required or optional. The interface standards are often generic, and may not specify a standard other than saying GML, or a specific GML type such as Metadata.

Additional common issues with utilizing OGC specs include:

- Complexity
- Size/Performance
- Interoperability

Complexity: There is a high perceived barrier to entry to implementing GML as a content returned on service requests, because of the size of the GML3.x specification. The GML 3.x specification is meant to be profiled by communities. This has led to simplified common specifications for geospatial content, such as Simple GML. Over time, communities such as EOS, Geosciences and Hydrology have developed specification profiles of GML. These profiles communicate the semantic content of the information, and how this information is sent over services.

Size/Performance: XML explodes the content so sending uncompressed XML can lead to server performance issues. Parsing of large XML documents requires different techniques, e.g. an entire document should not be read into memory. Compression can address the size issue.

Interoperability: Many specifications do not fully specify the content, which has led to development of simplified GML profiles. Simple profiles allow for clients to access a wide variety of data, at the expense of domain expressiveness. Most GIS systems cannot handle multiple geospatial types (points, lines, and polygons) in a data stream. One of the consequences of the proliferation of simple GML profiles is that most client applications cannot handle complex data types included in GML. The solution to this is specification of domain profiles, which is supported by OGC standardization process. Such standard profiles support interoperation at the semantic level. Clients will need brokers to translate complex data into formats they can understand.

Below we list common OGC service interface standards.

OGC Catalogue Service specification CS-W: The OGC Catalog Service for the Web specification provides interfaces to enable discovery of geospatial resources. The services are not limited to spatial information. Catalogs contain some form of metadata (searchable descriptive information) and a query interface (for returning the metadata properties to the requestor). A common metadata model is needed to insure best discovery and retrieval of information.

OGC Web Map Service: The most widely implemented of the OGC geospatial standards, the OGC Web Map Service (WMS) supports the request and display of maps derived from data accessed by the service. Maps are delivered as graphical images (GIF, JPEG, TIFF, etc.) may be requested from one or more WMSs overlaid in browsers or client applications.

OGC Web Map Service: The OGC Web Map Tile Service (WMTS) improves the speed of WMS services by building up caches of images that are delivered as “tiles” Most internet map servers utilize tiles, but they do not expose the services in a standard manner.

OGC Web Feature Service: According to the OGC adopted-specifications page, “the OGC Web Feature Service allows a client to retrieve and update geospatial data encoded in Geography Markup Language (GML) ... from multiple Web Feature Services. The ... interfaces must be defined in XML ... GML must be used to express features within the interface ... the predicate or filter language will be defined in XML and be derived from CQL [Common Query Language] as defined in the OpenGIS Catalogue Interface Implementation Specification.” The WFS provides an abstraction of the underlying data store, expressed in GML, as defined through GML application schemas referenced by the service.

OGC Web Coverage Service: The OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) “...extends the Web Map Server (WMS) interface to allow access to geospatial ‘coverages’ that represent values or properties of geographic locations, rather than WMS generated maps (pictures),” according to the OGC adopted-specifications page. WCS can return different representations of continuous data surfaces (coverages) for any location: grids, triangulated irregular networks (TINs), point sets. Most commonly, however, the form of coverage most often returned is a grid in a declared coordinate reference system and common format such as GeoTIFF.”

OGC Sensor Observation Service: An OGC Sensor Observation Service (SOS) “...defines a Web service interface which allows querying observations, sensor metadata, as well as representations of observed features. “ The service provides an interface to make sensors and sensor data archives accessible via an interoperable web based interface [52 north].

OGC Web Processing Service (WPS): The OGC Web Processing Service (WPS) “...provides rules for standardizing how inputs and outputs (requests and responses) for invoking geospatial processing services, such as polygon overlay, as a Web service. The WPS standard defines how a client can request the execution of a process, and how the output from the process is handled. It defines an interface that facilitates the publishing of geospatial processes and clients’ discovery of and binding to those processes. The data required by the WPS can be delivered across a network or they can be available at the server. WPS can describe any calculation (i.e. process) including all of its inputs and outputs, and trigger its execution as a Web service.” It can return information in an XML format, or a binary format, and supports long running processes.

5.5.1.2 SEARCH STANDARDS

Open Search. OpenSearch is a specification from the Amazon A9 subsidiary, which provides a way for clients such as web browsers, to search a web site. OpenSearch allows web sites to expose search APIs using a standard OpenSearch template document which informs the client of the available search parameters. The responses are returned in RSS or Atom. The specification is extendable so standard parameters for text, temporal, spatial, and relevance, in addition to a standard text search parameter.

One major issue is that the OpenSearch document must be at the root of the server, and not just within a directory.

Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) OAI-PMH is a low barrier specification developed by the Digital library community. It provides a standard extensible mechanism to allow for harvesting of metadata that may exist in a data source such as a database or library catalog. This harvest mechanism is used to build catalogs like the Digital Library for Earth Science Education (DLESE). OAI-PMH provides a simple mechanism for repository interoperability. Data Providers are repositories that expose structured metadata via OAI-PMH. Service Providers then make OAI-PMH service requests to harvest that metadata over HTTP.

Figure 5.5. Basic architecture of OAI-PMH

5.5.1.3 REMOTE PROCEDURE METHODS (WEB SERVICE STANDARDS)

Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP). SOAP is a protocol to call remote resources, usually over HTTP, but not restricted to HTTP. SOAP relies upon XML for its messaging and service description. A service can expose rich semantic method names, using terminology like GetVariables, GetSites, and GetValues (as implemented in CUAHSI water data services). A SOAP web service is described with a Web Services Description Language (WSDL), which not only describe the methods, but also the semantics of the information return by each method. A rich ecosystem of tools has been developed to utilize SOAP web services.

Figure 5.6. SOAP messaging (from Apache, 2012)

Figure 5.6 shows SOAP messaging functions. The sending application creates the original SOAP message, an XML message that consists of headers and a body. Once the message is ready, it is sent via a particular transport such as HTTP, JMS, and so on.

The Transport listener receives the message. Finally, a dispatcher determines the specific application (or other component, such as a Java method) for which the message was intended, and sends it to that component. That component is part of an overall application designed to work with the data being sent back and forth.

Representational state transfer (REST). REST is a distributed architecture based on HTTP, and URL. There is no official specification of REST architecture, as it is rather a software development pattern. Each organization determines its own RESTful pattern for its resources. Ideally, these use a clean URL design (see http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Clean_URL) The terminology for REST is HTTP verbs: GET, PUT, POST,

and DELETE. The methods are determined by the URL pattern of the service. REST services and the information returned can be described with a WADL file, but more often than not, a simple HTML page describes the service.

Cloud API's of most services are REST based. The patterns of the URL's and the inputs and outputs are documented. Microsoft's OData specification is an example of a RESTful service specification. Companies like Oracle, and Microsoft are incorporating REST frameworks into their products.

5.5.1.4 DATA ACCESS PROTOCOLS

OPeNDAP. OPeNDAP is a framework that simplifies all aspects of scientific data networking. It provides software which makes local data accessible to remote locations regardless of local storage format. It is widely used in the oceanographic and meteorological communities. OPeNDAP also provides tools for transforming existing applications into OPeNDAP clients (i.e., enabling them to remotely access OPeNDAP served data). OpenDAP URLs function as persistent URL's for resources, and can follow a RESTful pattern.

Figure 5.7. The Architecture of a Data Analysis Package Using OPeNDAP (from OpenDAP, 2008)

OData. From the Open Data Protocol web site: “The Open Data Protocol (OData) is a web protocol for querying and updating data. OData applies web technologies such as HTTP, Atom Publishing Protocol (AtomPub) and JSON to provide access to information from a variety of applications, services, and stores. OData emerged organically based on the experiences implementing AtomPub clients and servers in a variety of products over the past several years. OData is being used to expose and access information from a variety of sources, including but not limited to relational databases, file systems, content management systems, and traditional web sites.”

GData: The Google Data Protocol “provides a simple protocol for reading and writing data on the Internet, designed by Google. GData combines common XML-based syndication formats (Atom and RSS) with a feed-publishing system based on the Atom Publishing Protocol, plus some extensions for handling queries. It relies on XML or JSON as a data format.”

5.5.2. INFORMATION CONTENT STANDARDS

The following standards apply to information content. These standards are used to exchange information between services, or build community profiles. The early metadata standard FGDC was used to describe

datasets. The more recent INSPIRE metadata standard uses ISO 19115 as their framework. Another example of profiling is the Observations and Measures standard. O&M uses GML. WaterML2 uses O&M. The profiling of standards should allow some of the common semantics about data to be automatically determined.

ISO19115 metadata standard: Metadata standard ISO 19115:2003 contains an abstract model represented in UML depicting the content and relationships of descriptions of geographic data and services. It provides a detailed conceptual model and framework for developing metadata for data sets and services.

INSPIRE Metadata: infrastructure for spatial information in Europe provide guidance in the form of legislation on how to describe a spatial data set, a spatial data set series or a spatial data service compliant with the standards ISO 19115:2003 (corrigendum 2003/Cor.1:2006) and ISO 19119:2005.

FGDC Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata: The U.S. Federal Geographic Data Committee (FGDC) approved version 1.0 of the Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata (CSDGM) in 1994 and version 2.0 in 1998. The standard includes only an abstract model of content, relationships, obligation, and repeatability of properties that describe geospatial data. The FGDC has published schemata (XML document type declaration and XML schema documents) on its Web site to facilitate the validation and processing of metadata according to the standard.

OGC Geography Markup Language: The OGC Geography Markup Language (GML), also an ISO International Standard (19136 and OGC GML 3.2.1), provides a means of encoding geographic features and their properties using XML. GML is the expected packaging for features requested from an OGC Web Feature Server (WFS). Communities are encouraged to profile GML to create GML documents that confer the semantics of the community. **GeoSciML** and **WXXM** are two examples of GML profiles.

OGC Observations and Measurements: Observations and Measurements (O&M) is an International Standard which defines a conceptual schema encoding for observations, and for features involved in sampling when making observations. Communities are encouraged to profile GML to create GML documents that confer the semantics of the community. **CSML** (Climate Science Modeling Language) and **WaterML 2** are two examples of O&M profiles.

OGC Filter Encoding specification: The OGC Filter Encoding (FE) specification is used to express a query, or filter, using a predicate language or terms and operators that are stored in XML elements. FE is used in the request messaging sent to WFS and in the query sent to the OGC Catalogue Service CS-W.

OGC Styled Layer Descriptor: A Styled Layer Descriptor (SLD) is an XML schema for describing the appearance of map layers. A typical use is how to tell a WMS on how to render a map layer.

Structured Modeling Markup Language SA-SMML. SMML is designed to represent a large class of computational models in XML. The formulation is based on structured modeling and support model-data and model-independence, i.e., models can be re-used with different data sets and solved using a variety of solver platforms. We are very interested in exploring possibilities for using, adapting or extending SMML to computational models in the geosciences (El-Gayar and Tandekar, 2007). A semantic annotation of computational models and extended SMML is also available (SA-SMML)

5.5.3 EARTH SCIENCE FORMAT STANDARDS

Many data formats have been developed in the geosciences for exchanging information. While a binary format of a file is important for a program to utilize the data in the file, semantic descriptions are equally important for the exchange. Base standards, such as the NetCDF, shapefiles, and core OGC standards, do not convey semantics by default. In order to convey semantics, communities have created conceptual standards that enable a deeper semantic exchange. These may be contained in a binary file, such as the NetCDF Climate Forecast conventions, in a database schema such as CUAHSI ODM, in XML schemas such as CUAHSI WaterML, or in GML application schemas such as GeoSciML and OGC WaterML 2.0.

In **Table 5.14** we outline many Earth Science formats, and describe them as Ad Hoc, Community Standard, or Standard. An Ad Hoc standard was created by a project or group. It may have been adopted by other groups, but there is no process for maintaining the standard. A community standard may be developed for a community, and is documented. One such standard is CUAHSI WaterML 1.x, where an XML schema has been adopted, and vetted by a number of partners. A standard is one that goes through a formal standards process and has a governance to maintain the standard. We also specify if a standard is designed to convey data semantics.

Table 5.14. Earth Science Formats

	Type: Standard, Community Standard or AdHoc	Format	Conveys Semantics	Community
OGC Simple GML	Standard	UML, XML	No	Geospatial
OGC Simple Features	Standard	XML	No	Geospatial
SQL	Standard	ASCII	No	All
OGC SQL Simple Features	Standard	SQL	No	Geospatial
ESRI Shape	Community	Binary	No	Geospatial
OGC KML	Standard	Xml	No	All
OGC NetCDF	Standard	Binary		Meteorology, Climatology, Hydrology and many others
NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention	Community	Binary	Yes	Meteorology, Climatology
HDF			No	Meteorology, Climatology
WaterML	AdHoc	XML	Yes	Hydrology
WaterML 2	Standard	UML, XML	Yes	Hydrology
Hydrologic Features	AdHoc	UML	Yes	Hydrology
GeoSciML	Standard	UML, XML	Yes	Geosciences
Soil ML	AdHoc	XML	Yes	Soil
SoterML	AdHoc	Xml	Yes	Soils
Digital Weather Markup Language	AdHoc	XML	Yes	Meteorology, Climatology
Numerical Model Metadata	AdHoc	XML	Yes	Model Sharing
Metadata Objects for Linking Environmental	AdHoc	UML, XML	Yes	Metadata

	Type: Standard, Community Standard or AdHoc	Format	Conveys Semantics	Community
Sciences (MOLES)				
Weather Information Exchange Model (WXXM)	Community	UML, XML	Yes	Aeronautical Meteorology
iRIS MiniSeed	Community	Binary	No	Seismology
iRIS StationML	Community	XML	Yes	Seismology
iRIS QuakeML	Community	XML	Yes	Seismology
Exchange Network Water Quality Exchange	Standard	XML	Yes	Water Quality
Earth Science Markup Language ESML	Community	XML	Yes	
EarthChemXML	Community	XML	Yes	
CUAHSI Observations Data Model	Community	SQL	Yes	Hydrologic Observations
Open Earth Framework	Community		No	
ADAGUC Data Products Standard	Community	ASCII, Binary (HDF5)	Yes	Geospatial

OGC Simple GML (Geography Markup Language) – GML, which uses XML grammar, serves as a modeling language for geographic systems as well as an open interchange format for geographic transactions on the Internet. It contains a GML Schema that allows users and developers to describe generic geographic data sets that contain points, lines and polygons, with a goal for community to agree on specific schemas leading to easier data exchange.

OGC Simple Features – It supports 3-dimensional coordinates (location and elevation) on feature geometry and it also supports metadata (a means of referencing local or remote resources which could be used for primary/foreign key references and dynamic codelists).

SQL – Standard Query Language. A language to access relational databases.

OGC SQL Simple Features— A schema that supports storage, retrieval, query and update of feature collections via the SQL Call-Level Interface (SQL/CLI) (ISO/IEC 9075-3:2003). A feature has both spatial and non-spatial attributes. Spatial attributes are geometry valued, and simple features are based on two-or-fewer dimensional geometric (point, curve and surface) entities in 2 or 3 spatial dimensions with linear or planar interpolation between vertices.

ESRI (Environment System Research Institute) shapefiles – A vector format that can support point, multi-point, polygon, polyline and multi-patches. This file format has a much faster drawing speed and more editing capabilities than other data sources.

OGC KML(Keyhole Markup Language)— KML is an XML language focused on geographic visualization, including annotation of maps and images. Geographic visualization includes not only the presentation of graphical data on the globe, but also the control of the user's navigation in the sense of where to go and where to look.

OGC NetCDF (Network Common Data Form)— The OGC netCDF encoding supports electronic encoding of geospatial data, specifically digital geospatial information representing space and time-varying phenomena. NetCDF is a data model for array-oriented scientific data. A freely distributed collection of access libraries implementing support for that data model, and a machine-independent format are available. Together, the interfaces, libraries, and format support the creation, access, and sharing of multi-dimensional scientific data.

NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention— This netCDF interface enables but does not require the creation of self-describing datasets. The purpose of the CF conventions is to require conforming datasets to contain sufficient metadata, being self-describing in the sense that each variable in the file has an associated description of what it represents, including physical units if appropriate, and that each value can be located in space (relative to earth-based coordinates) and time.

HDF(Hierarchical Data Format)— the name of a set of file formats and libraries designed to store and organize large amounts of **numerical data**; there currently exist two major versions of HDF, HDF4 and HDF5, which differ significantly in design and API. HDF is supported by many commercial and non-commercial software platforms, including Java, MATLAB, IDL, and Python.

WaterML—an XML language for water observations data - streamflow, water quality, groundwater levels, climate, precipitation and aquatic biology data, recorded at fixed, point locations as a function of time.

WaterML2— supports the encoding of hydrological and hydrogeological observation data in a variety of exchange scenarios (e.g. exchange of data for operational monitoring and forecasting programs or supporting operation of infrastructure); provides the framework under which time series data can be exchanged with appropriate metadata to allow correct machine interpretation and thus correct use for further analysis.

Hydrologic Features— features connected with hydrology and are based on characteristics of oceans, seas, rivers and other natural water bodies. All hydrological features are connected and are in relation to each other. Each hydrological feature carries a unique hydrological feature code, as well as codes of the hydrological features to which it is related as foreign key.

GeoSciML— a GML application scheme, which is defined by a collection of XML schemas that utilize and extend elements from GML to represent standard geologic observations and descriptions in a geospatial context. GeoSciML defines a format for data interchange and does not define a database structure. Agencies can provide a GeoSciML interface onto their existing data base systems, with no restructuring of internal databases required

Soil ML—an abstract UML information model for soil, which considers existing information standards such as ISO, Observations & Measurements, GML, GeoSciML, etc. to be used as an International Standard for soil data transfer and collation.

SoterML(Soil and Terrain Markup Language)— a developing markup language to be used to store and exchange soil and terrain related data. SoTerML is as an extension of GeoSciML for SOTER model compliant with ISO/TC190/SC 1 N140 "Recording and Exchange of Soil-Related Data". SoTerML development is being done within the e-SOTER Platform—

Digital Weather Markup Language— A GML profile targeted for delivery of weather station=information over OGC WFS services

Digital Weather Geography Markup Language— contains forecasts for any combination of the meteorological parameters found in the database

Numerical Model Metadata— an **EVOLVING** international metadata standard intended for the exchange of information about numerical model codebases, the associated components and the models/simulations done using them.

Metadata Objects for Linking Environmental Sciences (MOLES) — documents which either provide descriptions of some key features of environmental data and their context or provide links to those descriptions.

Weather Information Exchange Model (WXXM)— the Weather Data Model, is a UML-based structural definition for the exchange of information by users of and contributors to the 4-D Wx Data Cube; WXXM is not a piece of software, nor does it have any function on its own. It defines a common vocabulary for exchanging weather information between organizations, but it does not inherently provide any sort of functionality to facilitate that exchange. It is, fundamentally, a set of guidelines for how to think about weather data.

iRIS MinSeed— MiniSEED data is a stripped down version of SEED data which only contains waveform data. There is no station and channel metadata included.

iRIS StationML— [can't find]

iRIS QuakeML— QuakeML is a flexible, extensible and modular XML representation of seismological data which is intended to cover a broad range of fields of application in modern seismology.

Exchange Network Water Quality Exchange— The Exchange Network developed a conceptual model for water quality observations. The US EPA implemented this model as Water Quality Exchange (WQX) where it is utilized in the EPAs' STORET services. Consensus between the USGS and EPA led to the development of a revision of WQX, which is used to distribute water quality information in the US.

Earth Science Markup Language (ESML)— a specialized markup language for Earth Science metadata based on XML, not another data format, that is a machine-readable and interpretable representation of the structure, semantic and content of any data file and ESML complements and extends data catalogs and provides the benefits of a standard, self-describing data format (e.g. HDF, netCDF, etc.).

EarthChemXML— includes metadata such as location, reference, etc., for geochemical and related data, and controlled vocabularies (ontologies) for validation

CUAHSI Observations Data Model—a relational database at the single observation level (atomic level); stores observation data made at points; metadata for unambiguous interpretation; traceable heritage from raw measurements to usable information; standard format for data sharing; cross dimension retrieval and analysis

Open Earth Framework(OEF)— a visual analytics suite of software libraries and applications that assist in the analysis, visualization, and integration of large multi-dimensional multi-disciplinary geophysical and geologic data sets; the suite's collection of interactive visual techniques are designed to help scientists derive insight from complex, ambiguous, and often conflicting Earth science data. The OEF includes interactive 3D visualization applications, batch processing tools, web service support, file format parsing, data model management, and programming APIs for building your own tools.

5.6 CROSS DOMAIN INTEGRATION INITIATIVES

Several initiatives and projects focused on cross-domain integration in the geosciences have been conducted by various research groups. Integration strategies have been explored at several levels: from generation of integrated data products to application-level or portal-level integration. On the other side, a community infrastructure brings together resources and allows users to do analyses for a specific topic. We use the USGS Water Smart as an example. In the middle is an infrastructure to provide tools and discovery of information. For this we use UNIDATA and the THREDDS stack. Each of these infrastructures use different tool sets, underlying layers, and approaches, but they address the needs of a community, and pull in resources from outside the community.

For the long tail of science, information needs to be easily published to a cloud system. The Polar Information Commons is one example of such as system.

5.6.1. GENERATION OF DATA PRODUCTS- EARTH OBSERVING SYSTEM (EOS) DATA AND INFORMATION SYSTEM (EOSDIS)

From the Earth Observing System Data and Information System (EOSDIS) website, it "... is a key core capability in NASA's Earth Science Data Systems Program. It provides end-to-end capabilities for managing NASA's Earth science data from various sources – satellites, aircraft, field measurements, and various other programs. For the EOS satellite missions, EOSDIS provides capabilities for command and control, scheduling, data capture and initial (Level 0) processing. These capabilities, constituting the EOSDIS Mission Operations, are managed by the Earth Science Mission Operations (ESMO) Project. NASA network capabilities transport the data to the science operations facilities.

The remaining capabilities of EOSDIS constitute the EOSDIS Science Operations, which are managed by the Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) Project. These capabilities include: generation of higher level (Level 1-4) science data products for EOS missions; archiving and distribution of data products from EOS and other satellite missions, as well as aircraft and field measurement campaigns. The EOSDIS science operations are performed within a distributed system of many interconnected nodes (Science Investigator-led Processing Systems and distributed, discipline-specific, Earth science data centers) with specific responsibilities for production, archiving, and distribution of Earth science data products. The distributed data centers serve a large and diverse user community (as indicated by EOSDIS performance metrics) by providing capabilities to search and access science data products and specialized services."

Figure 5.8. EOSDIS

5.6.2 APPLICATION-LEVEL INTEGRATION—UNIDATA

Unidata provide data, tools, and community leadership for enhanced Earth-system education and research. The system has no central data center, but instead relies on users computers. Data of interest is pushed to users systems who participate in the Unidata infrastructure; then the users run analyses locally. Clients and applications access data through Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Servers (THREDDS), which provides an abstraction layer (Figure 5.9).

Data does not need to be held locally to be utilized in analyses. Figure 5.10 shows components of LEAD that are already in operation at several universities. We estimate that about 30 sites are already running local models using output from national models at NCEP for initialization. Local models are not set up to interact with one another.

Figure 5.9. THREDDS server

Figure 5.10. The use of Unidata infrastructure in the LEAD project

5.6.3 TARGETED PORTAL- USGS WATERSMART

The USGS WaterSmart is a portal targeted at allowing users to produce water census information (Figure 5.11). The lower level infrastructure is OGC standards based, like the SISS (Table 5.15. WaterSmart). Datasets are prepared for use in the systems modeling by using mediators (Figure 5.12).

Table 5.15. WaterSmart Interfaces

Name	Abbrev.	Purpose
Catalog Service for the Web using ISO Encoded Metadata	CSW/ISO	Discovery metadata and data service information
Web Map Service	WMS	Provides screen resolution visualizations of geographic data.
Web Coverage Service	WCS	Provides arbitrary resolution gridded* data
OpenSource Project for a Network Data Access Protocol	OPeNDAP	Provides access to any explicitly indexed data esp. multidimensional data.
Web Feature Service	WFS	Allows query of and access to entities - (their geometry and attributes)
Sensor Observation Service	SOS	Provides query mechanisms unique to the needs of time-series data access
Web Processing Service	WPS	Provides a mechanism to describe and execute processing algorithms via a web based API

Figure 5.11. WaterSmart Portal

Example: WaterSmart National Water Census portal proposed architecture

Figure 5.12. USGS WaterSmart infrastructure

5.6.4 INTERMEDIARIES SOLUTIONS—EUROGEOSS BROKERING FRAMEWORK

The EuroGEOSS FP7 project³ developed a brokering framework which implements discovery, access, and semantic brokers: intermediary components implementing both proxy and gateway services for Clients and Servers components, respectively. It also implement dynamic interoperability at a certain extent, This framework was recently adopted by the GEOSS Common Infrastructure (GCI). The framework is empowered by the GI-cat and GI-axe technology developed by the CNR (National Research Council of Italy).

The EuroGEOSS project implemented a Brokering-oriented architecture to develop a multi-disciplinary cyber(e)-infrastructure and interconnect different disciplinary capacities, including: Forestry, Biodiversity, Drought, and Climatology.

The EuroGEOSS brokering architecture provides three brokers: the discovery, access, and semantic brokers. They are available at: www.eurogeoss-broker.eu. These brokers provide the following functionalities to facilitate discovery, evaluation, access, and use of multidisciplinary resources:

³ www.eurogeoss.eu

Discovery:

- Discovery brokerage;
- Semantic augmentation of discovery request;
- Discovery of Web 2.0 resources;
- Results ranking according to a given "significance" metrics.

Evaluation

- Resource common description (using ISO 19115-part 1 and 2);
- Descriptions common encoding (using ISO 19139);
- Support of extensions for disciplinary descriptions (e.g. ebRIM, O&M, Darwin-core, CF, etc.).

Access

- Data access brokerage (for both Feature and Coverage based resources as well as pictorial Maps).
- User definition of a Common Environment for data access (i.e. access data according to a common: CRS, spatial & temporal resolution, subsetting, data format).

Use

- Use of a Common Environment for data overlay;
- Support of multiple clients/tools for data discovery, access, processing, and visualization.

The EuroGEOSS Brokering framework is depicted in **Figure 5.13**. The Brokering CA roadmap provides an expanded description of this approach.

Figure 5.13. EuroGEOSS Brokering Framework

5.7 COMMUNITIES AND PROJECTS

Within the geosciences community there have been several projects that focused on developing cyberinfrastructures for communities (some examples are listed in **Table 5.16. Cyberinfrastructure systems**

and communities). For the initial assessment, we grouped the systems into two categories, modeling, and data. We categorized EOSDIS and CUAHSI projects in the domain system readiness table (**Table 5.11. Cross-domain readiness measures for selected information systems**), and the CSDMS system is described in section 6.

Table 5.16. Cyberinfrastructure systems and communities

System	Category	Community
Community Surface Dynamics Modeling System (CSDMS)	Modeling	Earth Surface Processes
SCS Community Modeling Environment (CME)	Modeling	Seismology
Earth System Curator	Modeling	Climate Models
CUAHSI Hydrologic Information System	Data	Hydrology
IRIS Data Management System	Data	Seismology
USGS National Water Information System	Data	Hydrology
NASA EOSDIS Distributed Active Archive Center	Data	ESIP Partners
National Map	Data, Catalog	Geoscience

From the view of the Earth Science Modeling Group, there are five modeling framework projects that have attracted the most interest over the past 5 years or so are (1) the Community Surface Dynamics Modeling System (CSDMS), funded by NSF, (2) the Common Component Architecture (CCA), funded by DOE, (3) the Earth Surface Modeling Framework (ESMF), funded by the Dept. of Defense, NASA, NOAA, and NSF, (4) the Open Model Interface (OpenMI) project, funded by the European Commission and (5) the Object Modeling System (OMS), funded by USDA-ARS.

These communities provide a unique focus with distinct capabilities and have different community standards (**Table 5.17**). The EOSDIS community has the broadest reach, and focuses on moving data products from satellites to processing facilities to community portals. The community portals provide points of aggregation of different data sources. The IRIS community focused on seismological issues, and both pre- and post-earthquake analyses. Following a seismic event, instruments are deployed, and processing of seismological events and data validation are/were a shared task. Because of this, the seismological community has a long history of data management, targeted at the preservation of seismologic event data. While this data has traditionally been shared via standard methods, newer services from IRIS are focused on sharing via web services. CUAHSI HIS provides a data for the hydrologic community. It does this by defining standardized web service infrastructure and a centralized catalog. The web services for many organizations were initially proxies/brokers for the originators of data like the USGS, and distributed services from the community over data source specified to a community standard (CUAHSI Observations Data Model). Over time organizations that were proxies added native web services. An organization like the National Map provides base map services, and additional layers based on information added to the system.

Table 5.17. Capabilities and focus for several communities

System	Community	Distinct Capabilities	Unique Focus
CUAHSI	Hydrology	Distributed standard web services	Individual investigator running

System	Community	Distinct Capabilities	Unique Focus
Hydrologic Information System		and data exchange specifications.	models locally or models managed locally.
IRIS Data Management System	Seismology	Long history of data management and migration of information to new formats	Shared community resources (instruments, manual processing, processing applications)
NASA EOSDIS Distributed Active Archive Center	ESIP Partners	Movement and processing of data. Thematic portals.	Shared Infrastructure
National Map	Geoscience	Spatial Data infrastructure.	Distributing National Geospatial Datasets

5.8 CROSS DOMAIN DATASETS

As part of the inventory of system components, we also provide an example description of a system generating common datasets that are utilized by many communities. Topography is a common component, and a large number of base geospatial datasets are available

5.8.1 OPEN TOPOGRAPHY

OpenTopography facilitates access to high resolution topographic information, and provides tools for access. LiDAR data for a region has to be loaded into the system prior to data production. There is a growing catalog of LiDAR data available for the nation. While OpenTopography can do customized processing, and provide subsets of LiDAR point clouds, it has been noted the over 80% of the usage is a standard product, digital elevation models and Google Earth files. Data products can address the needs of a large number of users. Infrastructure can address the needs of the advanced users.

Figure 5.14. Open Topography infrastructure and data products

5.8.2 GEOSPATIAL DATASETS

National and local scale geospatial datasets form the basis for many spatial analyses. The infrastructure should host datasets for communities in forms that communities can utilize not only for visualization, but also for analysis.

- USGS National Map
- National Hydrography Maps
- Ocean Bathymetry

- Open Street Map
- Global Basemaps

5.9 DATA PUBLICATION ISSUES

5.9.1 COMMON ERRORS

There may be errors in commonly used procedures and methods. The USGS CIDA group recently documented an issue with commonly used method of calculating evapotranspiration. The calculation of evaporation is dependent upon the slope orientation. The calculation of the orientation is dependent on the coordinate system, and the farther north the location, the larger the error in the orientation calculation. Utilizing a national, instead of a local coordinate system to calculate the orientation may have up to an 11% error.

5.9.2 COMMON DATA REFERENCE AND SHARING

Geospatial datasets provide a common framework. Where one researcher/organization may extend or manage a base datasets, other communities would like to utilize such base datasets. Usually such changes are not published to outside organizations, because the base dataset is available.

Projects like OpenStreetMap have shown that collaborative creation and management of data sources is possible. We need to work with researchers to identify candidates for such collaborative datasets, and create management organizations to create such datasets. Targets may be hydrologic networks, and natural hazard events.

CORRECTIONS TO DATA

Where datasets are used by scientists, errors and corrections to datasets are not often propagated back to the organizations. Often, it is because such changes are time sensitive. Once the time of normal use has passed, a dataset is no longer utilized but more often that there is no mechanism for sharing corrections. But often it is because there is no mechanism for sharing such corrections.

Researchers may process and correct a dataset for their own use, but do not propagate the changes back to the original source, or make the corrected dataset. This could be addressed with infrastructures like DAAC where products in the infrastructure are easily published. This will better enable cross-domain use because a domain scientist will have verified datasets.

As another example, The USGS real time data are collected approximately every 15 minutes at 14,000 locations. These are processed into daily products, and the 'raw' data were made available for 90 days. Errors and corrections are done to produce the daily values product and are noted on that product, but were not noted on the raw data. With new cyberinfrastructure, 5 years of real-time data are available in a database with 5 billion points. Use of the raw data still requires careful use, but the data are available, and the daily values products are corrected if an issue is found.

5.9.3 DOMAIN STANDARDS

Domain standards may be perceived as complex and unnecessary. A users client may be able to access the standard interfaces system, such as OGC Web Feature Services, but these may not fully present

information from services that use domain specifications. The inability to utilize standard services may be why some standards are perceived as complex. Using services that are customized to a specific domain is an education issue about the use of appropriate tools. Data Brokers are also a way to reduce the complexity and enable use by other domains.

5.9.4 DATA CITATION

Receiving publication credit for is an important part of the research process. The growing availability of online publications indicates that the ancillary analysis and data products associated with such publications should be online. Data that is used in a publication needs to be citable and preserved in an archived. Published data products need to be citable and have a shared identifier, like a DOI from DataCite, but not all data needs to be citable. Data that are not publically exposed may not need a citable reference. Raw data (not checked for quality) at local nodes or intermediate model/simulation products are examples of information that does not need to be cited in a publications. “Not electronically citable” is different than having data that has no reference. All data needs to be able to be referenced.

Table 5.18. Levels of citation

Level	Types of data
Reference	All data and analysis code
Citable	Public data, often with quality-controlled data products
Archived	Data products and analyses that are utilized in publications, or are used for evaluation of new tools.

5.9.5 METADATA COLLECTION

As mentioned in the Challenges section, creating metadata about datasets and/or specific observations is often problematic. The INSPIRE project has noted that even when datasets have “metadata” it may not pass quality control tests 60% of the time. Metadata creation from analyses and aggregated datasets is still not automated, is compiled by researchers without quality control, and is often left to the end of the project when the data are required to be submitted to a data repository. The creation of metadata needs to be less onerous, with the potential of some reward.

Presently metadata are expected to be created fully upfront of when the data are loaded. Because of the complexity, and time required, users only input minimal metadata, and leave in default (often incorrect or not applicable) information just to get data into the system. We refer to this publication pattern as metadata upfront.

METADATA UPFRONT

Approaches to publishing metadata in this manner include:

- Relying on instruments to provide as much metadata as possible in an automatic fashion
- Using servers that require specific metadata standards and provide tools for publishing data and metadata in these standards (e.g. OpenDAP, CUAHSI HydroServer)
- Filling out standard forms (often online forms), to manually provide metadata information in FGDC or other formats
- Publishing metadata and data as ASCII files generated from local data systems, in some agreed upon format, to be subsequently harvested, with metadata validated and enhanced as needed. The data are then re-published as standard services and registered in an online catalog (this procedure is implemented, for example, in the CZOData prototype)

METADATA ASAP, METADATA EVENTUALLY, OR METADATA ON DEMAND.

This is an alternative to publishing metadata upfront. Metadata description starts with a bare minimum set of values (e.g. Dublin core, or even file attributes), but over time users improve metadata incrementally through annotations. Examples of approaches of this type include NSIDC's Libre project, AirNow and DataSpaces (described below).

Any of the approaches would allow subsequent community update/annotation, though metadata upfront would be more useful and might apply to workflows in the EarthCube ecosystem. But not all communities or data users will take the time to provide full metadata. So the lighter metadata approaches need to be tested to determine what works for different communities and different data types. Those where data are expensive to collect and require extensive metadata – may need to be described upfront, and a community may implement some crowd sourced metadata curation.

A third model that has some promise is “metadata on demand”, in which we support an infrastructure in which users can ask that certain metadata be specified for specific data products. This model biases toward short-tail uses (i.e., scientists in the mainstream) but has the advantage of serving as a needs elicitation mechanism for metadata.

DATASPACEs

While it is useful to consider various mechanisms for mandating the creation and publication of metadata by data providers for their collections of data, it will also be valuable to think in terms of empowering the users of datasets to publish information about what they have learned from the use of the data. This approach can range from systems that allow a user to associate comments about the dataset from her perspective in a place that is linked to the data in some way. Such comments might be simple notes about how the data can be used effectively in a cross-disciplinary classroom exercise or a pointer to a python library or web service that transforms the data into a form that can be conveniently used in an analysis and display tool of choice. Or it could be a more sophisticated comparison or mapping between the conceptual models employed in different communities. The important this is to make it convenient for the user of the datasets to publish comments about them that are clearly linked back to the datasets in such a way that they become a part of the metadata in addition to that supplied by the data provider.

An example of such a “third-party” annotation system called dataspace is being developed in the air quality community. Using mediawiki they have brought together basic structured, data-provider metadata for discovery with the user feedback and other contextual metadata (potentially related papers, tools, suggested datasets, etc.). There is an example for AirNow at <http://datafedwiki.wustl.edu/index.php/AIRNOW>.

A long term EarthCube goal (presented in one of the original whitepapers) might be to develop a system that makes it possible for authors to create online publications that enable the reader to access the datasets and run the processes involved in the research. In this way, scientific publications, online educational materials and even articles meant for the public can become an important part of the metadata about the datasets and the processes used to analyze and display them. An important advantage of this approach is that it takes advantage of the reward systems already in place. Scientists get credit for and take personal pride in publications. Likewise it is the job of curriculum developers to create science education modules. So the incentive is there for authoring such documents. The trick is

to provide the tools that make them an important part of the metadata for the datasets and the processing services.

[Expression of Interest 1073 “Catalyzing EarthCube participation via an open repository for Earth Science Information”](#) discussed Dataspaces for Earth Cube.

5.9.6 METADATA AGGREGATION

Catalogs aggregate metadata, and catalogs in the OGC CSW and OAI-PHM can harvest metadata from multiple other catalogs, and exposed those results to other servers. There may be a round tripping issue where the fidelity of the metadata is lost as information is transformed from one format or system to another. Catalogs may transform the harvested metadata into internal models, and when they do some semantics may be lost, and identifiers may be changed. The major issue with metadata aggregation is identifiers: if a catalog re-harvests records from a source, it may not recognize the records as being the same. In our cross-domain interoperability model we rely on multiple interlinked and cross-harvested catalogs, and work to improve communication and fidelity of metadata within the system.

5.9.7 MODEL DESCRIPTION

As we assembled several model catalogs we realized that there is little consistency or standard elements in model descriptions. But many models are customized to a purpose, or a single run. For these models there is little incentive to describe them. At the same time, these models are not usually done in a vacuum, they derive or extend existing models. So in order to document models, a starting point to get the user to identify an existing model.

Presently, model documentation may be treated like a black box, and the present approaches do little to improve that state. Web processing services provide a limited description that enables use and focuses on the inputs and outputs.

Structured Modeling Markup Language (SMML) (El-Gayar and Tandekar, 2007) focuses on representing the internal structure of models, to expose them as a ‘white box’. SMML representations are not executable. In essence, models need to be compiled (or translated to a modeling language that can be executed). The advantage of a ‘white box’ representation is that it can serve as a meta-model allowing further reasoning, e.g., for archiving, discovery or composition/integration of models. SMML can potentially be used to represent the internal workings of these components (not just inputs and outputs). Ideally, this can be a step to facilitate (or automate) the integration of these components. SMML can play a similar role for modules in the CSDMAS model repository.

6. SOLUTIONS

6.1 OVERALL GOALS AND CRITERIA

The approach here is to use the previously articulated goals of the cross domain interoperability program to establish criteria that will provide insight into whether a solution is moving towards that goal, and to define measurable metrics for solutions against those criteria. In the sections below, we first look at how to measure the success of individual interoperability solutions, then how to measure the effectiveness of communication processes that need to occur if intra- and cross-domain efforts are to result in cross-domain interoperable solutions.

6.2 EVALUATING INTEROPERABILITY SOLUTIONS

This section outlines criteria for evaluating interoperability solutions in terms of capability, openness, and impact on community sustainability. These metrics can be used to evaluate interoperability solutions conceptually and in the context of use cases, particularly in the context of an interoperability test bed. The exact details of the metrics are not described here, only a sense of what the metric would be. Providing complete metrics would be part of the ongoing mission of this workgroup (see 7. Maturation Process.)

6.2.1 INTEROPERABILITY CAPABILITY

A lot of work has been done already on assessing the completeness of designs –implemented systems or conceptual models or a mixture of both – for interoperability. Wang-Tolk- Wang (2003) proposed a *Levels of Conceptual Interoperability Model* (LCIM) to evaluate the Capacity of Interoperability for a system/framework/conceptual design. The LCIM had 6 levels, starting with basic networked systems (L1) and rising, cumulatively to interoperating systems that are “aware” of each other’s underlying conceptual model - their objectives, inputs, outputs, content, assumptions, and simplifications. [Wang-Tolk-Wang 2008].

LCIM Levels	Description of Interoperability at this level
L6 (Conceptual)	Interoperating systems at this level are completely aware of each others information, processes, contexts, and modeling assumptions.
L5 (Dynamic)	Interoperating systems are able to re-orient information production and consumption based on understood changes to meaning, due to changing context as time increases.
L4 (Pragmatic)	Interoperating systems will be aware of the context (system states and processes) and meaning of information being exchanged.
L3 (Semantic)	Interoperating systems are exchanging a set of terms that they can semantically parse.
L2 (Syntactic)	Have an agreed protocol to exchange the right forms of data in the right order, but the meaning of data elements is not established.
L1 (Technical)	Have technical connection(s) and can exchange data between systems
L0 (No)	NA

The authors point out that L5 and L6 are the prerequisites for auto-composition and execution, and for now lie beyond the scope for this roadmap. Conversely as we are only looking at systems that at least can communicate with each other, we take L1 as a given.

The relevant levels for assessing interoperability are thus Pragmatic, Semantic and Syntactic. These can be treated as separate criteria. For example the Community Surface Dynamics Modeling System may not have a full semantic layer, but has achieved some measure of Pragmatic Interoperability.

Following Wang-Told-Wang, general metrics for levels L2-L4 are in terms of how clearly the content passed between the systems are defined. For instance the metric for degree of semantic descriptions exchanged might range from Low = none > ..> Med =controlled vocabulary > ..> High: ontological services.

Criteria Name	Level	Premise	Information defined	Metric – To what degree is the:
Pragmatic Interoperability	L4	Common workflow model	Use of data	Context of information exchanged
Semantic Interoperability	L3	Common reference model	Meaning of data	Content of information exchanged
Syntactic Interoperability	L2	Common data structure	Structured data	Format of information exchanged

6.2.2 TECHNOLOGY OPENNESS

Given the diversity of researchers and consumers, solutions that provide the greatest flexibility and are subject to the broadest governance are preferred. Such solution encourage competition and long term sustainability

- standards based – solutions based on standards with strong governance are likely to be more stable. See 5. Status for a discussion of standards for Interoperability Solutions
- no vendor lock on solution – solutions that lock the community to a single vendor (for their Interoperability solution) carry higher risk of stifling progress, and a higher risk of an eventual financial dead end.

- availability of 3rd party tools – want solutions that support an ecology of tools and vendors
- seamless – the end user should not need to be a master of the infrastructure that supports interoperability

Open source based solutions have an advantage here -- no single group controls a standard. However commercial solutions that are widely available, that encourage development by 3rd party vendors through API and have community governance structures are also viable.

Criteria	Metric [Low > High>
Use of Standards	All custom protocols, Mix of custom and standard, All based on standards
Community Solutions	Single source, collaboration, open source
Encourages 3rd party providers	Self as only provider, 3 rd parties can participate, actively supports 3 rd party ecosystem
Seamless for end user	Coding Required, System expertise Required, Full User Interface Provided

6.2.3 INTEGRATION WITH CYBERINFRASTRUCTURE PLATFORMS

Broad CI compatibility is important for adoption, use and sustainability. Interoperability solutions that are compatible with many, broadly deployed applications will have fewer barriers to adoption and are more likely to survive over time. Solutions that run on widely supported cloud systems reduce vulnerability to single machine, cluster failures. Metrics should encompass solutions such as CSDMS that runs a single dedicated super computer cluster to solutions that are fully cloud based.

Criteria	Description	Metrics[Low > High]
Platform Availability	Is the CI Platform on which the Interoperability Solution runs widely available to scientists and government?	Dedicated, Shared, Widespread
Cloud- based	Is the (primary) Platform cloud-based?	No, Soon, Yes
Multi-platform	Does the Solution run on multiple CI platforms?	Single, Few [1-5], Many

6.2.4 IMPACT ON COMMUNITY SUSTAINABILITY

For large scale interoperable systems – say on the scale of EarthCube – to be sustainable, process and technology alone are not sufficient. Incentives must be put in place to motivate data creators to publish data with at least enough metadata that intermediaries can successfully add additional information, e.g. semantics. There have to be incentives for software/tool developers to wrap their components in a standard manner that can be used by many interoperability solutions, not force them to wrap them many times. It is clear why consumer of x-disciplinary data and cross-domain tools/models are motivated – for instance decision support systems need to solve human scale problems. But as many have discussed, motivation/support for intermediaries and particular data producers is much less obvious. The Evaluating

Readiness process description and metrics in the next section can indicate if the overall community is starting to fail, but solutions should be evaluated on the demands they place on the different communities. The simple metric for how much a particular interoperability solution reduces the burden on the community is a 5 point qualitative scale of Level of Benefit: [None, Low, Indirect, Considerable, High, Breakthrough].

Community Types	Description	Burdens to participate in Interoperability Solutions	Example Incentives from Interoperability Solution
Data providers	Researchers generating data, and sharing it with the community	Having to republish data or tools to multiple interoperability frameworks	Publish to one aggregator with standardized metadata, where the aggregator supports users of the data writing additional metadata descriptions to enable semantic discovery.
Model/Tools providers	Researchers and tool makers creating models as tools and general modeling components.	Having to republish data or tools to multiple interoperability frameworks	
Solution providers	Groups/community provides a complete Interoperability solution – see the section “6 Communities and projects” in 5. Status	N/A – though most groups working on Interoperability solutions are also members of the other community Types listed here.	Having their Interoperability Solution adopted and funded
Intermediaries	Data brokers and aggregators, providers of simulation and workflow platforms	Providing a full Interoperability Solution beyond their interest funding, yet without such broad solutions, the full value of their contributions is not realized	Not aiming to provide a wall-wall Interoperability solution of their own, and need successful Interoperability Solutions to within which they can contribute
Sponsors/Funders	Agencies, foundations, universities and other organizations that fund projects that use EarthCube related science and technology	Traditional funders (e.g., EBM tools report from Duke) have expressed a reluctance to continue funding isolated tools efforts	Significantly ROI for funding components and research that will shared/used via Interoperability Solutions that are open, widely used, provide significant efficiencies and encourage 3 rd party tool development
Educators	Teaching effective approaches to interoperability and x-disciplinary science	Restricted to showing examples of their own projects or very simple teaching models	Students can be encouraged to take the theory and apply it to creating working x-disciplinary examples with meaningful outputs
Decision	Groups that pull	All landscape planning	The emergence of widely

Makers/Decision Support	together diverse information in support of making landscape level planning decisions that materially affect the state of the EarthCube.	decisions require inputs from multiple scientific disciplines. Too often the silos persist in the decision process – socio economics, ecosystems, water supply, flooding, transportation are treated as separate components of the decisions.	adopted Interoperability Solutions will greatly reduce barriers accessing x-disciplinary data, simulations and modeling across the inextricably interconnected facets of EarthCube.
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6.2.5 EXAMPLE DATA/MODEL SOLUTION ASSESSMENT

This section provides straw-horse ratings of sample of Interoperability Solution categories. A program to systematically refine metrics and objectives for evaluating existing and prospective Interoperability Solutions would be part of the portfolio of this working group going forward.

DATA/MODEL BROKERING/DATA MEDIATION

A broker is a middleware component that provides services for transforming messages between different protocols and content encoding schemes. A broker is intended to enable runtime service components to make and receive requests and responses in a heterogeneous and distributed environment. A brokering service removes requirements for data server developers to implement all protocols and encodings that clients (especially those from other domains) may require. The same can be said for client developers who now need to implement all the protocols and encodings used by services where there are data of interest to client users.

Brokering can be seen as a requirements elicitation step in the interoperability lifecycle. In writing a broker, one discovers what users need and what is lacking in the brokered resource. Brokering thus defines requirements for users and providers. Ideally, eventually, key brokered solutions become hosted by the original data providers.

A brokering layer will contribute to interoperability in several areas where we are now faced with significant challenges because different communities have different systems in place:

- Cataloging and discovery protocols. Much work has already been done on the use of a brokering service layer in the context of the EuroGEOSS (citation) initiative as well as the Digital Divide Experiment (cite recent paper in press). This approach has been shown to be effective in connecting multiple metadata service protocols (e.g., CS/W and OpenSearch) with clients that use a different set of protocols and metadata standard forms. Need a more complete list of protocols
- Access protocols. There is great potential for facilitating interoperability in the area of dealing with the mismatches in protocols between the clients and servers using the plethora of formal and community standard protocols, e.g., OPenDAP, WCS, WFS, SOS, WMS to pull a few out of the alphabet soup. Even within the context of one protocol, there are often significant mismatches among release levels. WCS 1.0, 1.1, and 2.0 are examples where a brokering layer can perform the needed transformations between clients and servers which may employ different release levels of the same protocol. Experimentation is already underway in the EarthCube Brokering

group on brokering service that accesses data from WCS, WFS, and OPeNDAP servers and makes available maps via a WMS interface.

- Encoding formats. Most of the same arguments that apply to access protocol transformations also apply to encoding formats. One example of a specific transformation of interest for interoperability between the hydrology and the meteorology/oceans communities is a conversion between netCDF which is in wide use in MetOceans and WaterML of the hydrology community. Considerable work has already been done on such a conversion (Palmer, 2012). This would be a great candidate for implementation in a brokering layer. Encoding format transformations is mentioned in the Challenges section.
- Processing service protocols. Many of the other issues raised in the Challenges section: differing scales, sampling geometries, and models for the shape of the Earth can be addressed via data processing services. If such processing services are implemented in a brokering layer, they can access data from a wide variety of data servers, perform the transformation in the brokering layer and make the resulting transformed data available in a form useful to a similarly wide variety of clients.

Interoperability Objectives	Criteria	Generic metrics[Low > High]	Strawman Ratings for Brokering*
Interoperability Capability	Pragmatic L4	Degree to which context of information exchanged	
	Semantic L3	Degree to which content of information exchanged	
	Syntactic L2	Degree to which format of information exchanged	
Technology Sustainability	Use of Standards	All custom protocols, Mix of custom and standard, All based on standards	
	Community Solutions	Single source, collaboration, open source	
	Encourages 3 rd party providers	Self as only provider, 3 rd parties can participate, actively supports 3 rd party ecosystem	
	Seamless for end user	Coding Required, System expertise Required, Full User Interface Provided	
Integration with CI	Platform Availability	Dedicated, Shared, Widespread	
	Cloud- based	No, Soon, Yes	
	Multi-platform	Single, Few, Many	
Impact on Community Sustainability	Data Providers	Level of Benefit	
	Model/Tool Providers	Level of Benefit	
	Intermediaries	Level of Benefit	
	Sponsors/Funders	Level of Benefit	
	Educators	Level of Benefit	
	Decision Makers & Decision Support	Level of Benefit	

*Strawman ratings for generic Brokering solution

SIMULATION INTEROPERABILITY FRAMEWORKS

The Community Surface Dynamics Modeling System (CSDMS, <http://csdms.colorado.edu>) is an example of a solution whose primary focus is creating a computational framework where 3rd party tools can be assembled and executed for the purpose of large scale simulations. The system is an interoperable simulation framework that runs on a single computational platform, with user/developers of individual model systems declaring I/O requirements based on a fixed vocabulary.

The CSDMS Modeling Tool (CMT) enables users to run and couple CSDMS model components on the CSDMS supercomputer in a user-friendly software environment. Components in the CMT are based on models, originally submitted to the CSDMS model repository, and now adapted to communicate with other models using a private BMI protocol. The CMT tool is the environment in which end users can link these components together to run new simulations. The CMT software runs on the end users own computer; but it communicates with the CSDMS HPCC, to perform the simulations. Thus, the CMT also offers end users a relatively easy way of using the CSDMS supercomputer for model experiments.

Solution Specific Metrics - in addition to the general metrics here, see the “Communities and Projects” section in 5. Status.

Interoperability Objectives	Criteria	Generic metrics[Low > High]	Strawman Ratings for CSDMS*
Interoperability Capability	Pragmatic L4	Degree to which context of information exchanged	Medium
	Semantic L3	Degree to which content of information exchanged	Medium
	Syntactic L2	Degree to which format of information exchanged	High
Technology Sustainability	Use of Standards	All custom protocols, Mix of custom and standard, All based on standards	Mix of custom and standard
	Community Solutions	Single source, collaboration, open source	Open source
	Encourages 3 rd party providers	Self as only provider, 3 rd parties can participate, actively supports 3 rd party ecosystem	Actively supports 3 rd party ecosystem
	Seamless for end user	Coding Required, System expertise Required, Full User Interface Provided	Full User Interface Provided
Integration with CI	Platform Availability	Dedicated, Shared, Widespread	Dedicated
	Cloud- based	No, Soon, Yes	No
	Multi-platform	Single, Few, Many	Single
Impact on Community Sustainability	Data Providers	Level of Benefit	Indirect
	Model/Tool Providers	Level of Benefit	High
	Intermediaries	Level of Benefit	Indirect
	Sponsors/Funders	Level of Benefit	High
	Educators	Level of Benefit	High
	Decision Makers & Decision Support	Level of Benefit	High

*These ratings of CSDMS are based on a conversation by Philip Murphy with Scott Peckham.

6.3 INTEROPERABILITY READINESS MODEL AND ASSESSMENT

A draft “interoperability readiness model” is presented here to provide a framework for developing evaluation metrics of EarthCube-enabled processes. This readiness model will help identify gaps, inform development of solutions, prioritization of effort, and evaluation of progress. The model and assessment process will be products of the cross-domain interoperability project that are intended to become an integral part of an operational system.

There are two distinct infrastructure capabilities that must be considered:

1. **Data discovery:** can cross-domain researchers find the resources they need?
2. **Data utility:** are data provided in forms that are useful for scientific purposes?

6.3.1 READINESS FOR DISCOVERY

As discussed in section 3. (Challenges), discovery operates at multiple levels. We will consider assessing discovery capabilities for shallow and deep matching separately.

SHALLOW MATCHING

Shallow matching involves algorithms that operate against a body of text—the resource itself or metadata describing the resource. Controlled vocabularies of keywords play a critical role in this application, either as search terms or as terms used to index resources in metadata. For some resources, these keywords may be meaningful across disciplinary and community boundaries, but for others, searching by keywords involves semantic mediation, to enable a researcher in one domain to find resources described by a set of keywords appropriate to another domain.

Readiness for shallow matching is assessed by determining how many of the following questions can be answered in the affirmative:

- 1) **Data indexing:**
 - a) **Indexing:** Are all data indexed according to an appropriately defined set of keywords and/or coordinates?
 - b) **Clarity:** Is each keyword unambiguous, in the sense that the keyword means the same thing across all disciplines and domains?
 - c) **Sufficiency** of metadata: are the metadata sufficient that data with similar metadata have similar uses?
 - d) **Thesauri:** are domain-specific keywords appropriately cross-referenced to representative keywords so that cross-domain discovery is enabled?
 - e) **Standards:** Are practices for indexing standardized to the extent possible?
- 2) **Governance:**
 - a) Are keywords, thesauri, and indexing standards appropriate to community needs?
 - b) Are keywords, thesauri, and indexing standards periodically reviewed and revised by the community?
- 3) **Compliance:**
 - a) Are data providers compliant with governance decisions on keywords?
 - b) Are data source periodically reviewed for compliance?
- 4) **Infrastructure:**
 - a) Are software tools and catalogs available to enable cross-domain data discovery?

- b) Are the tools and catalogs reliable, robust, and supported?

DEEP MATCHING

In practice, shallow matching does not automatically guarantee scientific usefulness. Deep matching is mostly accomplished by people. Scientists first find shallow matches and then carefully assess applicability of each resource through reference to the scientific literature and other documentation of how sources have been used in the past, or by consultation with domain experts. Deep matching is enabled by knowledge of prior successful uses, or through a full understanding of the data acquisition and processing history. The exact format in which the resource is made available can either impede or enable cross-domain use. Thus assessment of resource readiness for deep matching involves the following additional criteria:

1) Reusability:

- a) Are data stored at the maximum available resolution (to enable maximum flexibility and accuracy in sampling at lower resolutions)?
- b) Are data quality factors documented, sufficiently explained, and discoverable?
- c) Is the lineage/provenance of the resource fully described?
- d) Are current uses of data sources documented, comprehensive, curated, and discoverable?
- e) For models, are the algorithms and implementations of those algorithms fully documented?

2) Governance:

- a) Does the community consider data resolution and reusability sufficient for their needs?
- b) Does the community consider data quality factors to be sufficiently and compellingly documented?
- c) Does the community consider current uses of data sources to be scientifically valid?

Often applicability of a data source is determined by unforeseen factors that only appear in the literature. It may never be feasible to automatically determine a deep match, but software can assist users by ruling out sources that lack appropriate evidence in their favor. Assisting users with a deep match requires a tight and curated link between data sources and scientific publications that document their successful (and unsuccessful) uses.

6.3.2 READINESS FOR UTILITY

Unlike readiness for discovery – which considers whether data sources are known and understood – readiness for utility considers the difficulty of using resources the form they are made available. A central theme in data utility is whether standards are defined, supported, and governed for the fostering of cross-domain research. Questions about data utility include the following:

1) Standards: do standards for data format encourage cross-domain science?

- a) Are data provided in standardized formats that encourage cross-domain use and reuse?
- b) Are standard formats sufficiently documented, curated, and supported?
- c) Do standard formats include provision for sufficient documentation of the encoded information?

2) Flexibility: are data provided in formats that maximize utility and encourage reuse?

- a) Are data stored at the maximum available resolution (to enable maximum flexibility and accuracy in sampling at lower resolutions)?
- b) Are resolution and other quality factors documented and discoverable?
- c) Are underlying uncertainty distributions in the data documented and discoverable?

3) Governance: are the standards appropriately governed by the scientific community?

- a) Are standards accepted by the community as appropriate to enable science?

- b) Is there periodic community review of the appropriateness and effectiveness of standards?
- 4) **Compliance:** are data providers complying with standards?
 - a) Is there data of sufficient form, quality, and resolution in available data products to provide them in standardized form?
 - b) Is there current infrastructure that conforms to standards?
 - c) Are there mechanisms for validating conformance to standards?
- 5) **Infrastructure:** is cyber-infrastructure sufficient to support standards?
 - a) Is there software infrastructure to provide and manipulate standards-compliant data products?
 - b) Is the software infrastructure mature, robust, and supported?

6.3.3 PRODUCT METRICS

The above quality factors lead to natural measures of whether resources are ready for cross-domain use, based on the extent to which data sources exhibit the quality factors or not. In turn, the cross-domain interoperability of a collection of resources as a whole can be characterized as answers to the following questions:

1. To what extent are the resources reusable across envisioned uses?
2. To what extent are resources employable in answering new cross-domain scientific questions?
3. To what extent do documented cross-domain uses inspire and cross-fertilize new uses?
4. To what extent do documented cross-domain uses collectively encourage and drive standards for interoperability?

6.4 FUTURE WORK ON SOLUTIONS

There are many tasks needed to refine the approach above to the point where it becomes a useful tool for guiding interoperability development.

1. Deepen criteria and metric in this section – e.g., incorporate degree to which standards are used in different solutions – see 5. Status
2. Add Solution Category specific metrics – what makes one data aggregation method superior to another – see 5. Status
3. Incorporate some of the metrics here in the design of the Interoperability Test Bed
4. Develop criteria for individual communities
5. Incorporate criteria from other EarthCube Working groups

7. PROCESSES FOR MATURATION

7.1 KEY PROCESSES TO MATURE IN EARTH CUBE

There is much writing in the literature – both inside and outside the geosciences – about how to mature a process. The output of our concept area is a continual process of learning and adaptation, and not a simple product. Although there are currently some products with proven cross-domain utility – and a general idea of their attributes – no general pattern has emerged as yet to define the ideal characteristics of such a product. One key roadblock to determining those characteristics is that “fitness for use” of data and models is difficult to define in a portable way that applies across all domains. Data and models within and across multiple domains can have varying requirements for data precision, quality, documentation, etc. **Determining optimal methods for documenting and combining data for cross-domain utility is a “grand challenge” research problem.**

The processes that must mature are the communication processes described in Section 4, in which cross-domain successes lead to patterns that inform scientific governance in refining ideas suitable for general use. However, **the outputs of that process can never fully mature**, in the sense that the bottom-up and top-down processes must continue indefinitely in order to discover and respond to new trends, and define new practices. All of the controlling factors of the process – including technical feasibility, success stories, lessons learned, future work recommended, and other outreach – are subject to change over time, and the end product of our roadmap is a continual process that copes with these changes. Thus it is the process – and not the product – that we must mature.

The approach we favor would be to institute an organizational framework for conducting a series of discrete interoperability test beds, each one focusing on a manageable scope of work (one or more use cases for science scenarios, as described previously), that could advance our science knowledge and technology. So there are really two processes to describe:

- a) Building a framework for conducting cross-domain interoperability test beds to mature EarthCube standards and practices; and
- b) Applying the framework to study a selected set of use cases for a given test bed.

These processes will depend very much on decisions for governance process(es) to be made by the EarthCube Governance team. Both of these processes will require virtual and face-to-face meetings for collaboration in the preparation and performance of the tasks needed. The output of the first process will be documented procedures developed to plan and conduct individual test beds. The output of each test bed would be one or more reports of the study and knowledge gained, and any recommendations to evolve the interoperability testbed framework.

The most important processes to mature for EarthCube include:

- 1) **Governance** of:
 - a) Choices for data products (to use recognized standard encodings when possible)
 - b) Standards for:
 - i) Metadata, information models and encodings (to follow guidelines enabling determination of fitness for use)
 - ii) Semantic descriptions (to follow community conventions, and semantic mediation mechanisms in trans-disciplinary applications)

- iii) Data Delivery and model/workflow execution (service interfaces, access control, rights management, intellectual property rights protection)
- 2) **Curation** of:
 - a) Standards (e.g., specification versioning, schema namespace management, ontology management)
 - b) Data products (selection criteria and methodologies for long-term access and archiving)
 - c) Data and resource catalogs for discovery purposes.
 - d) Publications that document utility and reusability.
 - e) Change history.
- 3) **Infrastructure** provision, including:
 - a) Reusable data products and processing/modeling services and components.
 - b) Search and discovery services.
 - c) Software tools that aid in data publication, discovery and download.
 - d) User training and documentation.

7.1.1 ASSESSING MATURITY LEVELS: THE CAPABILITIES MATURITY MODEL

With change control processes defined, it is appropriate to assess the maturity of those processes, in terms of their ability to cope with changing needs, priorities, and purposes. For this topic, some groundwork has been done by UKOLN, University of Bath, and Microsoft Research in defining a “Community Capability Model” for data-intensive research. In software engineering, engineering process maturity is assessed according to the following five-point scale, sometimes called the “Capabilities Maturity Model” or CMM:

Based upon the above diagram, the UKOLN/Bath/Microsoft study proposes a general maturity scheme for data-intensive projects in terms of five levels of maturity:

- 1) **Initial:** processes are ad-hoc.
- 2) **Repeatable:** processes are repeatable (but the repetition is based upon undocumented resources).
- 3) **Defined:** processes are documented so that others can repeat them.
- 4) **Managed:** processes are assured through some over-arching management or governance.
- 5) **Optimized:** the management process makes improvements over time.

Applying this rubric to the processes we have defined above gives a matrix of capability attainment, as follows:

	Initial (1)	Repeatable (2)	Defined (3)	Managed (4)	Optimized (5)
Governance	Governance processes are ad-hoc.	Governance processes function, but without defined processes.	Documented processes for governance are created.	Documented processes are implemented and assured.	Documented processes are periodically reviewed and improved.
Curation	Curation is ad-hoc.	Curation achieves scientific goals but without documented processes	Effective curation processes are documented.	Documented curation processes are implemented and managed.	Curation processes are periodically reviewed and improved.

Infrastructure	Data provision is ad-hoc.	Data are provided as desired, but processes remain undocumented.	Processes for data provision are defined.	Definitions are assured.	Data provision processes are reviewed periodically and improved.
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It is this matrix – together with the definitions above – that captures the rest of the definition of cross-domain readiness. However, given the constantly-evolving nature of the Internet, social networks, observation sensor technology (and hence scale/size/frequency of data collection), and many other aspects of technology and the environments in which it is used, we recognize that prototyping, testing and improvement of standards and procedures will be necessary, ongoing activities.

7.1.2 METRICS FOR ASSESSING TECHNOLOGY READINESS AND COMPLIANCE

In addition to the above model, there are several possible metrics to evaluate compatibility and compliance. A set of metrics called *Compliance Measures* is used by database vendors to ensure compliance with the SQL specification. A second one we reviewed, *Technology Readiness Levels*, is an approach used to assess maturity of evolving technologies by several US federal agencies (NASA, in particular) and companies. Both systems of measures can be revised for EarthCube.

COMPLIANCE MEASURES

The ANSI SQL community uses compliance levels to signify compatibility. There are three compliance levels: Entry, Intermediate, and Full: they reflect whether a system implements specific commands, data types and functionality. It is noted by vendors that it is difficult to maintain compliance with the full standard.

We may adopt such database compliance levels to assess EarthCube readiness. The compliance levels will be especially useful in assessing brokering and workflow solutions. The table below shows examples.

Compliance Level	Description	Sample Brokering Compliance
Entry	Core features to which every implementation must comply	Data of interest is transformed from format A into format B. Broker output complies with a domain standard. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information loss is expected. No Semantic translation.
Intermediate	Meets functionality requirements of some set of functionality, e.g. "ISO/IEC 9075-14 XML-related specifications (SQL/XML)"	Meets entry-level compliance. In addition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimal information loss is allowed. Broker filters information so non-compliant or low quality data are removed from data. Minimal semantic translation.
Full	Functionality complies with all specifications	Meets intermediate-level compliance. In addition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No information loss Transformation is fully reversible. Broker filtering can be utilized.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full semantic translation is implemented.
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TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVELS

The Technology Readiness Levels model was developed by NASA in the 1970's (Wikipedia: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level). Basically, technologies mature through a set of stages. The jumps between stages can be small or large. A report from the DoD (Graettinger, 2002) discussed technology readiness of hardware and software (see **Table 7.3** for levels of software maturity). In case of EarthCube, this approach could be applied to assess EarthCube software components and can be also extended to evaluate social and governance arrangements of cross domain readiness – however the latter would require a precise specification developed jointly with Governance and other groups.

Table 7.3. Technology Readiness levels (from Graettinger, 2002)

Technology Readiness Level	Description
1. Basic principles observed and reported	Lowest level of software readiness. Basic research begins to be translated into applied research and development. Examples might include a concept that can be implemented in software or analytic studies of an algorithm's basic properties.
2. Technology concept and/or application formulated	Invention begins. Once basic principles are observed, practical applications can be invented. Applications are speculative and there may be no proof or detailed analysis to support the assumptions. Examples are limited to analytic studies.
3. Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof of concept	Active research and development is initiated. This includes analytical studies to produce code that validates analytical predictions of separate software elements of the technology. Examples include software components that are not yet integrated or representative but satisfy an operational need. Algorithms run on a surrogate processor in a laboratory environment.
4. Component and/or breadboard validation in laboratory environment	Basic software components are integrated to establish that they will work together. They are relatively primitive with regard to efficiency and reliability compared to the eventual system. System software architecture development initiated to include interoperability, reliability, maintainability, extensibility, scalability, and security issues. Software integrated with simulated current/legacy elements as appropriate.

<p>5. Component and/or breadboard validation in relevant environment</p>	<p>Reliability of software ensemble increases significantly. The basic software components are integrated with reasonably realistic supporting elements so that it can be tested in a simulated environment. Examples include “high fidelity” laboratory integration of software components.</p> <p>System software architecture established. Algorithms run on a processor(s) with characteristics expected in the operational environment. Software releases are “Alpha” versions and configuration control is initiated. Verification, Validation, and Accreditation (VV&A) initiated.</p>
<p>6. System/subsystem model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment</p>	<p>Representative model or prototype system, which is well beyond that of TRL 5, is tested in a relevant environment. Represents a major step up in software demonstrated readiness. Examples include testing a prototype in a live/virtual experiment or in a simulated operational environment. Algorithms run on processor of the operational environment are integrated with actual external entities. Software releases are “Beta” versions and configuration controlled. Software support structure is in development. VV&A is in process.</p>
<p>7. System prototype demonstration in a operational environment</p>	<p>Represents a major step up from TRL 6, requiring the demonstration of an actual system prototype in an operational environment, such as in a command post or air/ground vehicle. Algorithms run on processor of the operational environment are integrated with actual external entities. Software support structure is in place. Software releases are in distinct versions. Frequency and severity of software deficiency reports do not significantly degrade functionality or performance. VV&A completed.</p>
<p>8. Actual system completed and qualified through test and demonstration</p>	<p>Software has been demonstrated to work in its final form and under expected conditions. In most cases, this TRL represents the end of system development. Examples include test and evaluation of the software in its intended system to determine if it meets design specifications. Software releases are production versions and configuration controlled, in a secure environment. Software deficiencies are rapidly resolved through support infrastructure.</p>
<p>9. Actual system proven through successful mission operations</p>	<p>Actual application of the software in its final form and under mission conditions, such as those encountered in operational test and evaluation. In almost all cases, this is the end of the last “bug fixing” aspects of the system development. Examples include using the system under operational mission conditions. Software releases are production versions and configuration controlled. Frequency and severity of software deficiencies are at a minimum.</p>

7.2 CITATION AND PUBLICATION

This process is based first and foremost on direct scientific evidence of data fitness for use, including success stories, the papers that document them, and the processes those papers use for scientific discovery. Thus, it is particularly important to have reliable and mature **mechanisms for data and model citation and cross-referencing** with which to unambiguously link data sources and necessary tools with scientific successes (and failures) that demonstrate their utility. It is particularly important to link data with the models with which it has been successfully used; many of our group believe that the separation between models and data are artificial and that data and models should be handled similarly.

Data or model citation depends upon the assignment of a persistent, unique identifier to a data product or collection. A data product or collection that has a persistent and unique identifier can be cited in a publication without risk of the identifier no longer pointing to a data set, or worse yet, pointing to a different data set. The process choice involved in data citation begins with identifying a solution for assigning and resolving persistent identifiers. There are a number of approaches in use in the national and international scientific community including DOI, URN, ARK, and PURL. The advantages and drawbacks of each of these conventions are still being debated, so an effort has begun by members of the NSF DataNet/INTEROP community to illuminate the differences so choices can be understood. The process we suggest following is to have team members following efforts such as this persistent ID issue. Chances are good that a solution allowing interoperability between persistent IDs will emerge, such as to use DOI for identifying whole datasets, and ARK for identifying subsets, e.g., individual granules within a satellite imagery scene. EarthCube infrastructure will need to either choose one persistent ID solution and adopt it uniformly, or choose to support interoperable persistent ID resolvers. This important form of interoperability cannot be done within a single working group, but this working group, charged with interoperability, can make informed recommendations from its unique expertise and engagement in this issue. Focusing on identifier management in cross-domain context in one or more of the pilot projects would lead to a mature solution.

7.3 FITNESS FOR USE

It is unlikely that replacing a data set traditionally used in a model, with a new dataset, will be ever fully automated. Until those new sources are well documented and trusted they will not be utilized to their fullest extent. These are aspects of a dataset's "fitness for use", which is an assessment of its applicability for specific uses based on the measurement characteristics, spatio-temporal scales and frequencies, data quality and quality control procedures, sufficiency of metadata including provenance, presence of community annotations, availability of references to successful previous uses, and resultant publications. An additional measure of a "reusable dataset" is how the results from using a new dataset compare to the result from using an old dataset in the same or similar context. Fitness for use is a dynamic concept: it changes over time as QA/QC procedures are applied, community annotations and references are added, and the dataset is validated in a growing number of scenarios. We may be able to automate the process of evaluating fitness for use via a collection of "**fitness for use workflows**", but we need to be able to extract the constraints from the scientists as part of these workflows.

Given the distinction between strategic and opportunistic data and model re-use that we introduced in Section 1 with respect to data lifecycle, we would also distinguish between fitness for strategic re-use and fitness for opportunistic re-use. In the former case, we refer to data and model re-use in a specific

targeted context, i.e. within a defined research study or use case. Fitness for use workflows as envisioned here are built for such cases, and document successes and failures of specific interoperability designs. As a result of such workflows, datasets and models get annotated as described above. The annotations are appended to the resource metadata and included in resource registries. In turn, availability of such additional descriptions and standardization of data and model discovery, access and interpretation make possible fitness for opportunistic re-use, where discovered datasets and models can be interpreted as useable for a wider range of applications not necessarily envisioned when the dataset or model were constructed, registered or annotated. A key recommendation of this Roadmap is that fitness for use workflows are developed for commonly used datasets and models (prioritized with input from EarthCube governance and based on the assessment processes described in Section 4) and that annotations are added to registered resources so make their fitness for use assessment possible for a range of unanticipated applications.

A sample fitness for use workflow is demonstrated as part of the hypoxia use case outlined in earlier sections. The demonstration is at <http://earthcube.ning.com/groups/interop/pages/demos>.

7.3.1 FITNESS FOR USE OF OBSERVATIONAL DATA: DATA QUALITY ISSUES

Quality of observations is a critical component of their fitness for use. It is determined and communicated differently for different types of data; e.g., where satellite observations often have an associated processing level, in situ or ex situ ground observations or samples typically do not. In addition, when individual observations – each potentially with individual quality metadata – are combined into a dataset for model use, this information is often lost. An additional complication is that different measurement components may have different accuracy/quality expectations: for example, standards for temporal accuracy are generally much lower for ground water level measurements than for surface water discharge. Such discrepancies that stem from the nature of measured phenomena may not be obvious for users in other domains. Adding data quality information to observational values and datasets, defining rules for representing data quality in combined datasets and propagating quality information through brokering are indicators of mature data quality management. An associated community curation process would manage changes of quality flags (e.g. from “Bad” or “Suspect” to “Corrected”.) To mature the data quality subsystem of readiness evaluation we propose that one or several use cases have data quality and accuracy propagation in cross-domain scenarios as its specific theme.

7.3.2 FITNESS FOR USE OF MODELS

A different question is whether science models are fit for being linked together. One-run models are common practice for science, but increasingly, multiple models are being connected in sequential workflows, or use integrated frameworks such as OpenMI, ESMF, CCA, or CSDMS (reviewed in the roadmap by the EarthCube Earth Science Modeling (ESM) group). Reliance on such frameworks is particularly important for supporting cross-domain use cases. Registries and tools facilitating model discovery and linking are emerging. This will further raise the importance of model identity, citation and other provenance metadata mentioned above as factors in evaluating model quality and fitness for use in a given application. For a mature model integration environment it would be important to experiment with model identity and provenance metadata in a joint cross-disciplinary pilot work with the ESM group.

7.4 ORGANIZATIONAL FRAMEWORK AND USE CASES

To implement and mature these processes, we propose an organizational framework and a series of activities (described in more detail in sections 8-9) that will be conducted in collaboration with other EarthCube groups, geoscience researchers, decision makers and other stakeholders.

On the organizational/institutional side, these activities will include defining a structure for an entity supporting multi-disciplinary interoperability test beds. We refer to this organization as the **Geosciences Interoperability Institute (GII)**. It will be responsible for managing governance, curation and infrastructure provision processes defined above, as well as for continuous outreach and community engagement activities and collaborations with stakeholders and the public. In particular, it will manage iterative evaluation of standards and interoperability technologies, including brokering and grid approaches, in the context of several cross-domain pilots. It will also house advisory committees and development teams, and interact with domain data management systems to harmonize data management policies.

Several use cases that would be the basis for pilot projects and create the context for prototype infrastructure development have been described earlier (Chapter 3). We also are collaborating with other EarthCube groups on defining additional use cases to explore. From the cross-domain perspective, we are looking for use cases that highlight common cross-domain challenges and can be used to distill requirements and needed capabilities, as described in Section 4 (see “use case templates”).

8. TIMELINE

Cross-domain Interoperability is not a new issue. Use cases, capabilities and tools supporting discovery and reuse of data and processing across disciplines have been outlined in multiple papers and presentations prior to this document. The central principle of this roadmap, and of the timeline presented here, is to **leverage the advances and infrastructure already created** within geoscience research and development projects, presenting a smooth iterative transition to community-guided CI supporting standards-based publication, discovery and integration of geoscience data and models. This timeline envisions several sub-projects focused on specific interoperability pilots, as well as development of conceptual, organizational and technical frameworks for EarthCube. An EarthCube **cross-domain interoperability platform**, a key component of this roadmap, will be developed and user-tested to support a range of integration strategies for both research groups already engaged in CI projects and for a broad audience of geoscience researchers typically associated with the “long tail of science.” This will be accomplished through spiral and agile (where appropriate) software development, interoperability readiness assessments and education and engagement programs coordinated by a **Geosciences Interoperability Institute**. The latter is envisioned as a virtual organization supporting multiple EarthCube activities and committees, conducting cross-domain interoperability test beds, managing software development and adoption and interacting with other geoscience stakeholders. Section 9 will elaborate on a management structure to implement the timeline outlined here. Below we present our plan for execution of the roadmap as it translates into the timeline components organized thematically, and by years of the project.

8.1 KEY ACTIVITIES, ORGANIZED THEMATICALLY

8.1.1 INVENTORY OF AVAILABLE GEOSCIENCE DATA AND OTHER RESOURCES

This activity focuses on inventorying, organizing and annotating available domain and cross-domain resources, including catalogs, vocabularies, services and information models, and organizing community input and curation of these inventories. **This activity has started**, with the development of an online inventory accessible from the project’s web site⁴, and will be significantly extended in Year 1 when we plan to participate in end user workshops being organized by NSF. In the future development, the inventory will be expanded to include the relevant NSF programs as an organizing factor, recognizing the differences between communities in levels of centralization and standardization of data management. For example, the Surface Earth division has 4 programs with different types of data and patterns of interoperability maturity: (a) Hydrologic Sciences, with a focus on time series data collected at points; developed controlled vocabularies and taxonomies; and a community data center about to be established; (b) Geochemistry and Geobiology, emphasizing long-tail science projects with some standardization defined by EarthChem and a weaker tradition of data sharing, but with the Integrated Earth Data Applications (IEDA) data facility to lead community inventory and standardization efforts; (c) Sedimentary Geology and Paleobiology, with some standardization provided by USGS but no community data center; and (d) Geomorphology and Land Use Dynamics, with a similar lack of community data center (with the exception of OpenTopography and NCALM for LIDAR.)

⁴ <http://earthcube.ning.com/group/interop>

ACTIVITY MILESTONES:

- A white paper documenting inventory construction, organized by domains and by NSF programs (Year 1)
- An online searchable catalog of domain and cross-domain resources (Years 1-2, then ongoing) – with input from and in collaboration with geoscience domain data systems
- A system of inventory annotation and update by the community, and respective governance arrangements (Years 1-2, then ongoing) – in collaboration with the Governance team and the Geoscience Commons
- Community workshops focused on inventories of domain and cross-domain resources (Years 1-2) – in support of activities of the Stakeholder Alignment team

8.1.2 READINESS ASSESSMENT OF DOMAIN INFRASTRUCTURES AND RESOURCES

This activity **has started**, with the development of a readiness conceptual model and initial readiness assessments of domain system components we inventoried. This work will be extended in years 1-3, and will include the following components:

- Conceptual modeling of a “certified reusable resource”, which includes sufficient metadata and provenance information to assess its applicability in a different domain and research context, as well as user annotations and links to documents and publications (years 1-2)
- Development of fitness-for-use workflows to assess available resources and generate additional annotations and metadata (year 2)
- Making such annotated resources discoverable in a resource catalog (Year 3)
- Conducting readiness assessments on resources in the expanded inventories (ongoing)
- Gap analysis triangulating inventories, readiness assessments, and requirement generated in the course of use case analysis and pilot implementation (ongoing)

ACTIVITY MILESTONES:

- A white paper documenting the readiness assessment process and the curation of metadata and readiness annotation (Years 1-2)
- An information model or a reusable resource (Years 1-2)
- Online gap assessment reporting (Year 2)
- Prototype curated catalogs of certified reusable resources, with appended readiness assessments (Year 3)

8.1.3 CROSS-DOMAIN PILOTS AND USE CASES

This activity **has started**, and will significantly expand in years 2-3, culminating in the first series of interoperability test beds. The test bed activities will be conducted in collaboration with other EarthCube teams. Previous sections of the roadmap document have described several motivating cross-domain use cases that served as source of challenges and interoperability requirements. These include existing funded research projects that transcend geoscience domain boundaries – the Global River Observatory and the Critical Zone Observatory – as well as specially selected research scenarios that highlight cross-domain challenges:

- the hypoxia in the Gulf use case, jointly explored with the Layered Architecture group (see section 3);
- the carbon cycle use case - jointly explored with the Brokering group (described in the Brokering group roadmap);
- the weather radar data in hydrologic modeling use case (see section 3);

- the volcanism case proposed by the semantics group and now being explored by several teams (see the semantics group roadmap).

As discussed in sections 3 and 4, additional use cases have been identified during the July 2012 meeting of Concept group PIs. These use cases will serve as the basis for pilot implementations demonstrating the use of advanced technologies in solving specific science problems, which in turn may be further developed into components of operational EarthCube infrastructure by the end of the project period.

As an adjunct to the use cases themselves, experiments will be conducted using a brokering tier to facilitate discovery and access via standard interfaces for datasets that will be relevant to several of the use cases. In particular the brokering layer will provide access to metadata and data from servers of real time weather forecast output from a Unidata server and climate prediction processed products from a server hosted by the NCAR GIS project. For the "radar data in hydrological modeling" use case, these experiments will make real-time weather forecasts of precipitation available to hydrological models to complement the radar data for flooding scenarios. Similarly, real-time forecasts of winds and precipitation will be important in the volcanism use case for predicting the behavior of the volcanic plume. It will also be valuable to determine whether predictions of climate anomalies prove useful in the carbon cycle use case.

Each pilot project will include a sequence of steps:

- analyzing the use case to identify science challenges and cross-domain integration challenges, such as mismatches between catalogs, vocabularies, services and protocols, information models (as reflected in use case templates); to be carried out by a small multi-disciplinary team of experts;
- assembling existing tools and CI components to address the challenges, attempting to use them and documenting the experience;
- identifying conceptual and technical gaps and interoperability barriers, and distilling new capabilities needed to resolve interoperability challenges; establishing development priorities;
- iteratively developing software, with evaluations from both domain experts and tool experts;
- distilling lessons learned and developing best practice documents and learning materials;
- iterating with a larger community on potential consensus building about additional community standards needed to scale the pilot implementation, in collaboration with multiple EarthCube stakeholders and professional societies;
- in coordination with OGC and ESIP, bringing the worked use cases and pilots for consideration by standards bodies, jointly developing of standards change requests, and integrating pilot work into OGC and ESIP interoperability experiments and test beds;
- testing and validating the developed prototypes and deciding on their further development into components of operational EarthCube infrastructure

In addition, this activity will include an ongoing process for collecting and elaborating on research scenarios that have the potential to be developed into use cases and pilots. This will be done in collaboration with other EarthCube teams, and in particular with the Geoscience Commons and the Stakeholder Alignment teams.

ACTIVITY MILESTONES:

The schedule for each pilot will be aligned with the schedules of the collaborating science projects. We expect that several pilots may be executed in parallel by distributed teams of researchers and developers from the science projects and from development teams organized under the umbrella of EarthCube interoperability test bed. The expected milestones for the pilot projects will include:

- Definitions of use cases underlying pilot projects, including a science case, potential technologies and data to explore, and cross-domain issues to evaluate
- Establishing the pilot sub-projects, assembling project team, establishing relationships and liaisons with collaborating projects and agencies
- Reporting on technology testing and identified gaps
- Development of specification documents, lessons learned, best practice documents
- Evaluating developed software and its conversion to EarthCube infrastructure components, following software development processes as described in the following subsection.

8.1.4 REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE AND CROSS-DOMAIN INTEROPERABILITY PLATFORM DEVELOPMENT

That activity **has started** with an inventory of existing domain systems architectures (available online, some reviewed in Chapter 5). It has several components:

- finding commonalities and establishing relationships with existing data and modeling initiatives, including CUAHSI Water Data Center, CZOData, Unidata, OOI, NEON, IEDA and others, building on the experience and engagement of the interoperability team's members as well as on connections with other teams (Years 1-2)
- interacting with other EarthCube projects to create an integrated reference architecture and implementation plan to avoid duplication of effort and assure an integrated system (Years 2-3)
- selecting pilot projects to drive architecture development; large-scale multi-group efforts will be targeted so that the work can be broken into pieces that can be handled by designated sub-groups (Years 1-2)
- conducting software development projects implementing EarthCube CI components. The plan is to follow the spiral development model that emphasizes iterative and incremental planning, development, testing and validation. It will include a combination of development iterations of different lengths, from hackathons (specifically advocated by the Brokering group), to rapid prototypes that take between 2-8 weeks development time, to the 1-year test bed development cycle. In addition, where appropriate we will follow the agile development approach, as it is well suited for situations where priorities and requirements change often, and emphasizes small interdisciplinary team effort. A mandatory aspect of the development will be continuous collaboration with geoscience end-users to ensure that developed software is regularly validated against science goals, and that trust is built between users and developers. Such development iterations usually work better when small teams of experts are at the same physical location, though other arrangements are possible (Years 2-5).

At this early stage, we anticipate developing a cross-domain platform with a dashboard component to assist users with searching, interpreting and accessing data and processing routines from different disciplines, executing fitness-for use workflows, and publishing, curating and annotating data and other

resources. It will therefore contain several subsystems including: search; semantic mediation; dataset or model publication (from Dataspace upload to the cloud, to vocabulary and other semantic mapping), registration and documentation; resource evaluation/exploration to assess fitness for use, and resource annotation with best use practices and papers. This development shall be concluded in Year 5.

This activity will also include outlining the functions, structure, participation (membership) and operational procedures for the Geosciences Interoperability Institute, which will present an organizational structure enabling the CI development, maintenance and adoption. We expect that the Geoscience Institute will ramp up between Years 2-3, leveraging from the outcomes and lessons learned from the first interoperability testbeds.

ACTIVITY MILESTONES:

- EarthCube implementation plan as an online interactive document. It will identify which groups will develop which components (Year 2)
- Reference architecture (Year 2, then ongoing), including
 - elaborated functional specification, prioritized development, and defined milestones
 - user centered design studies with target users and focused groups, and emphasize integrating community knowledge and community input across geoscience domains
- Prototype implementation (Years 2-5);, including the cloud deployment mechanisms and subsystems for:
 - Testing and validation of interoperability components
 - Deployment system for interoperability platform-- an installable software stack to support discovery and data access
 - Annotation, to support documentation of datasets for cross-domain interoperability
 - Curation, to support registration, documentation, and archiving of datasets
 - Readiness assessment, to support analysis of a dataset to evaluate readiness for cross-domain use
 - EarthCube-compliant data publication system
- EarthCube organizational plan and a Geosciences Interoperability Institute charter, in conjunction with the Governance and other teams (Year 2)

8.1.5 OUTREACH/DISSEMINATION, GOVERNANCE AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

The goal of this activity is to ensure that broad geoscience audience is closely involved in all phases of EarthCube CI design and development, from feeding the development with use cases and providing feedback on implementation to participating in software development teams. The components include:

- Identifying and nurturing EarthCube communities of practice (CoP), in particular:
 - CoP meetings to inform development priorities;
 - CoP meetings for User Interface design feedback and user input for incremental releases;
 - Road shows at professional meeting
 - Organizing a bi-annual EarthCube Interoperability Conference, and interoperability workshops (twice a year) focused on pilots and use cases, as well as technology demonstrations
- Developing governance plans, in collaboration with the EarthCube Governance team:
 - Elaborating charters for Cross-domain advisory board and committees

- Implementing the governance structure, in particular the establishment of separate technical and scientific committees
- Ensuring that the governance processes are in place and active, and evaluate efficiency
- Establishing a web presence, including:
 - Defining policies for participation, initiation and management of blogs, wikis, mail lists, etc.
 - Website development and maintenance
 - Development of online tools for user annotation and crowdsourcing, integrated across EarthCube subdomains
- Creating documentation, tutorials, and workshops, and setting up a help desk
- Conducting annual reviews of emerging solutions
 - assessing them in terms of interoperability capacity, technical and community sustainability
 - making recommendations for priorities in interoperability research
 - refining and adapting capacity and sustainability metrics
- Developing business plans for data preservation and data/model management (in particular, in conjunction with NSF-mandated Data Management Plans)
- Developing curricular materials; accepting and curating contributions of relevant educational materials
- Developing international collaborations.

ACTIVITY MILESTONES:

As listed above. Most activities are expected to start in year 1 and continue on an ongoing basis.

8.1.6 INTERCHANGE FORMATS, PROTOCOLS AND VOCABULARIES

This activity is closely related to pilot projects (8.1.3) and EarthCube CI platform development (8.1.4), and will feed into the milestones listed under those sections. Specific components include:

- Developing specifications of necessary interchange formats, services and vocabularies
- Developing and documenting interchange profiles as information model and service profile specifications, and vocabulary specifications, as per set priorities
- Developing, documenting, and deploying vocabularies in vocabulary services
- Establishing consensus on community interchange formats, protocols and vocabularies, developing white papers, working with domain CIs to ensure that these community standards are recognized
- Communicating with standards bodies on specifications

8.2 KEY ACTIVITIES: GANTT CHART

The Gantt chart and the source Excel Microsoft Project files are also posted at <http://earthcube.ning.com/group/interop/page/roadmap>

ID	Roadmap Timeline for Cross-Domain Interoperability Workgroup	2013				2014				2015				2016				2017				2018				2019	
		Qtr 4	Qtr 1	Qtr 2	Qtr 3	Qtr 4	Qtr 1	Qtr 2	Qtr 3	Qtr 4	Qtr 1	Qtr 2	Qtr 3	Qtr 4	Qtr 1	Qtr 2	Qtr 3	Qtr 4	Qtr 1	Qtr 2	Qtr 3	Qtr 4	Qtr 1	Qtr 2			
1	8.1.1 Inventory of available geoscience data and other resources - PLANNING																					Milestone: (Possible) subsystems or components that would support 8.1.2 - 8.1.4					
2	Develop cross domain readiness assessment																					Milestone: White paper documenting readiness assessment process					
3	Inventory available resources																					Milestone: Open system for (ongoing) community use					
4	Online community inventories system																					Milestone: Mapping document (potentially an XML schema of a resource)					
5	8.1.2 Readiness assessment of domain infrastructures and resources - PLANNING																					Milestone: Mapping document (potentially an XML schema of a resource)					
6	Create a conceptual model of a resource from the perspective of readiness for cross-domain data use																					Milestone: Populate resource description, in a curated online system					
7	Conduct readiness assessment on resources in inventory (2)																					Milestone: Compilation summary for Gap analysis, COP face to face review					
8	Collect and elaborate example scenarios (use cases) [Ongoing]																					Milestone: Ongoing gap assessment and reporting					
9	Gap analysis for required capabilities; compare inventory, readiness assessment, and use cases																					Milestone: Deliver report with recommendations for demonstration scenarios to implement					
10	Establish priorities for capabilities development (2)																					Milestone: Metadata profiles for standard metadata formats (ISO19139, ISO ebRIM, FGDC, EML...)					
11	Create a conceptual model of fitness for use (2)																					Milestone: Report and initial metadata profile(s) to support cross-domain interoperability					
12	Specification of readiness assessment and fitness-for-use workflow (2)																										
13	8.1.3 Cross-domain pilots - - PLANNING																					Milestone: Project-specific Required Components Specifications					
14	Specification for components required for a specific project (2)																										
15	Find appropriate large-scale multi-group model																										
16	Summarize and Evaluate lessons learned to feed back into ongoing pilots [Ongoing]																										
17	8.1.4 Reference Architecture and Cross-Domain Interoperability Platform Development - PLANNING																					Milestone: EarthCube implementation plan					
18	Interact with other EC projects to create integrated reference architecture and implementation (2)																					Milestone: Foundation Documents for Interoperability Institute					
19	Select a testing framework, leveraging other interop testbeds (at OGC and elsewhere) (2)																					Milestone: Interoperability Institute Founded					
20	Outline functions, structure, participation and operational procedures for EC interoperability institute (2)																										
21	Establish Interoperability Institute																										
22	Development cycle 8.1.2 - 8.1.4																					Milestone: Functional Specifications Document					
23	Define functional specification, prioritize development, set milestones (2)																					Milestone: (Possible) subsystems or components that would support 8.1.2 - 8.1.4					
24	[Optional] Deployment system for interoperability platform																					Milestone: (Possible) subsystems or components that would support 8.1.2 - 8.1.4					
25	[Optional] Annotation system																					Milestone: (Possible) subsystems or components that would support 8.1.2 - 8.1.4					
26	[Optional] Curation system																					Milestone: (Possible) subsystems or components that would support 8.1.2 - 8.1.4					
27	[Optional] Readiness assessment system																					Milestone: Comprehensive Use Case studies					
28	User centered design studies with target users (2)																					Milestone: Cross-Domain Pilot Systems, Interoperability Test Bed					
29	Code, test, feedback, iterate (2)																					Milestone: Data publications, Demonstration to EC community					
30	Fitness for use workflows, inventories, EC-compliant components, broker tuning (2)																										
31	8.1.5 Outreach/dissemination, Governance and community engagement																					Milestone: Website operational					
32	Website development and maintenance [ongoing]																					Milestone: Community engagement mechanisms					
33	Identify community of practice (COP). Road shows at professional meeting [Ongoing]																					Milestone: COP meeting to inform prioritization					
34	COP meetings to inform Prioritizations (2)																					Milestone: COP meetings for UI design feedback, user input for incremental releases					
35	COP meetings for UI design feedback, user input for incremental releases (2)																					Milestone: Elaborate charter for Cross-domain advisory board					
36	Development of governance plan in EC governance framework [GOVERNANCE]																					Milestone: Governance process in place and active					
37	Implement governance structure [GOVERNANCE]																					Milestone: Bi-annual COP workshops, start					
38	Documentation, tutorials, workshops, help desk, outreach [Ongoing]																					Milestone: Recommendations for sustainable Interoperability research prioritization					
39	Annual Sustainability Review (3)																					Milestone: Sustainable Business Plan					
40	Data preservation, system maintenance/business plan																										
41	8.1.6 INTERCHANGE FORMATS, PROTOCOLS AND VOCABULARIES																					Milestone: Specifications Reports					
42	Specification of necessary interchange formats and vocabularies (2)																					Milestone: Profile specifications established					
43	Develop and document interchange profiles [Ongoing]																										
44	Develop, document, deploy vocabularies in vocabulary service(2)																					Milestone: Vocabulary specifications established as part of process					

8.3 RESOURCE ESTIMATE

Our estimates of available resources are preliminary. We expect the activity to ramp up, in particular, in years 2 and 3, with the establishment of the Institute (year 2), expansion of the training/workshops program (year 3), and expanded test bed activities (years 3-5). We expect that by the end of the 5-year period the basis of the EarthCube cross-disciplinary platform will be constructed and processes and governance arrangements will be in place to ensure continuous community-guided EarthCube development. We expect that the prototyping and initial construction phases will require the following resource commitments:

- The pilot implementations will require several developer FTEs with complementary expertise (software architect, pilot managers, software developers, UI experts, cloud deployment experts);
- Additional personnel is needed to support outreach, community engagement and coordination, in particular community consensus building and coordination with standards bodies;
- The Geosciences Interoperability Institute will require experts in interoperability technologies, web development, information modeling and information model mapping, service interfaces, semantic mappings and catalog federation, workflows, metadata profiles and standards, curation services and inventory and catalog management, best practice documentation, as well as liaisons with different communities. This expertise is distributed within the community; the role of the Institute would be to maintain resources and involve community experts as needed;
- Domain system CI projects would receive funding to work with the pilot teams and the interoperability institute experts;
- Cloud resource allocations and hardware provisioning. It is best to build the Geosciences Interoperability Institute entirely in the cloud, to avoid hardware cost of ownership and encourage collaboration.

9. MANAGEMENT

The management and governance model will be critical to a successful Interoperability Readiness effort within Earth Cube, and will require coordination across the multiple science communities, projects, domains, and institutions. The Cross-Domain Interoperability management program must be in sync with the broader vision and status of EarthCube development, responsive to input from disparate sources, and focused on creating community consensus. This calls for flexible structure, to manage processes and evolution, not focused on specific technologies, but on long-term trends and challenges identified earlier in the roadmap. As described in section 4.6, the goal is to supplement and leverage from existing efforts, not to replicate or replace ongoing work of organization such as OGC, ESIP, ISO, etc. To meet these requirements, we propose a management model based on an executive committee, two advisory and liaison committees – one focused on science topics, and one on technology – and a series of working group addressing each of the key deliverables (Fig. 9.1).

9.1 EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE

The Executive Committee will have overall responsibility for the Geosciences Interoperability Institute and its outcomes. It will be composed of the PIs and co-PIs of funded Geosciences Interoperability Institute grants, i.e. those with a contractual obligation to produce results, as well as ex-officio representatives of the Science and Technical committees, and any additional members that are determined to be key. However, it is recognized that the Interoperability Institute must be a community-driven enterprise, and that the Science and Technical Advisory and Liaison Committees should have strong roles in setting direction and priorities.

9.2 SCIENCE ADVISORY AND LIAISON COMMITTEE

A standing science committee will have the overall charge of determining the needs and priorities of the user communities. The Science committee should set overall science directions and priorities. Its responsibilities also include advising those working groups most focused on meeting science needs, or most requiring input from science users, e.g. readiness assessments, cross-domain pilots, and outreach and engagement. The committee will draw membership from a broad spectrum of geoscience projects, disciplines, organizations, and domains.

9.3 TECHNICAL ADVISORY AND LIAISON COMMITTEE

The technical committee will decide on implementation plans, including standards for data formats, services, and discovery aspects. Its responsibilities include advising the Executive Committee and those working groups most focused on technology: reference architectures and cross-domain interoperability platform development, outreach and education (along with the Science committee), and interchange formats, protocols, and vocabularies. The committee will draw membership from a broad spectrum of technical projects, disciplines, organizations, and domains.

Figure 9.15. Management Functions for Cross-Domain Interoperability Project

9.4 WORKING GROUPS

Working groups will be organized to address each of the key outcomes defined and described in the Timeline section:

- Readiness assessment of geosciences infrastructures and resources (see section 8.1.2)
- Cross-domain pilots (see section 8.1.3) – these will be carried out by small, multi-disciplinary teams of experts;
- Reference architectures and cross-domain interoperability platform development (see section 8.1.4)
- Outreach/dissemination and community engagement (see section 8.1.5), in conjunction with the Technical Committee
- Interchange formats, protocols and vocabularies (see section 8.1.6).

9.5 EARTH CUBE INTERACTIONS

Coordinating and collaborating with the overall EarthCube effort will be critical to the success of the Geosciences Interoperability Institute. Liaisons will be named to each of the other EarthCube projects (see Communications for a listing). Some of the working groups will have a tight relationship with specific EarthCube effort; in these cases a direct line is indicated in figure 9.1. Other Earth Cube groups will interact and inform several aspects of the Interoperability effort, such as the Geoscience Commons, Workflows, Brokering, Layered Architecture, and Data Discovery Mining and Access.

Designated liaisons will find the multiple touchpoints and potential synergies between EarthCube projects. As an example, we consider the Semantic EarthCube group. Clearly, the Vocabulary and Semantics working group of the Interoperability effort will need to work directly with the EarthCube Semantics and Ontology (S&O) group. In addition, the S&O group proposes to develop case templates; though the aims of the S&O use cases are somewhat different from the Interoperability use cases, it should at least be investigated whether a common use case template can be developed that meets the needs of both groups. Further, the S&O group proposes user surveys to assess science needs and priorities; it may be more efficient and less burdensome on the community if Interop and S&O (as well as other EC groups) could coordinate on survey efforts. Finally, the S&O group suggests an effort to catalog existing ontologies and semantic technologies, just as Interop proposes to catalog interoperability technologies and projects. One well-constructed approach to cataloging might efficiently serve both needs. The potential interactions between the S&O and Interop groups serves as just one example of what NSF terms the “mesh” of connection between the EarthCube groups. To maximize efficiency, and minimize the burden on the community (how many surveys, or catalog forms, will any one scientist want to fill out?), strong liaisons between all the Earth Cube projects are critical.

Multiple liaisons to both science and technical projects and organizations, as described in the Communications section, are also planned; these are too numerous to specify, but are represented by the “OGC, ESIP, etc.” box on figure 9.1.

An additional important connection is with the Digital Government Strategy recently released by the White House (Executive Office of the President, 2012). Architecting government systems for interoperability and openness is the key tenet of the Strategy, and the approaches and technologies it emphasizes include cloud computing, web APIs and open standards, cross-agency catalogs of digital resources – i.e. the themes that are also core to EarthCube interoperability. On the governance side, the central component of the Strategy is an inter-agency Digital Services Innovation Center. The functions of this center include identifying shared solutions and helping agencies develop Web APIs to unlock valuable data – which parallel key functions of the Geosciences Interoperability Institute described earlier. Cross-agency sharing and adoption of solutions and best practices will be led by a Digital Services Advisory Group, which will be also responsible for identifying gaps in policies and standards. The common focus on interoperability, standard services and shared technological solutions, as well as parallel governance structure, create the potential for collaboration between the Digital Services Innovation Center and the GII, in particular with agencies and API’s dealing with the Earth Sciences.

10. RISKS

The primary risks inherent in this effort include:

1. **Conflict of interest** between data center domains and owners and the goal of enabling cross-domain data reuse.
2. **Insufficiency of solutions**, leading to lack of cross-domain data use due to remaining difficulties.
3. **Misuse of cross-domain data**, leading to inaccurate scientific conclusions.
4. **Lack of trust** in cross-domain data solutions, regardless of efficacy.

10.1 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

First, there is an inherent conflict of interest between data centers whose mission is enabling particular kinds of domain science and the goal of cross-domain use. Enabling cross-domain use involves significant resources in a fixed-resource situation, and could be perceived as siphoning effort and resources away from critical domain projects. For example, the data centers might not have sufficient staffing to support cross-domain use of the kind envisioned in this report; we are recommending repackaging and relabeling data in a way never before envisioned by the data centers. The extra effort of repackaging data could be infeasible without extra staffing, and even infeasible given the existing mission-centered governance structures of the data centers and how they measure their effectiveness. Additional coordination between data centers is also expected, in particular with respect to coordinated data life cycle and retention policies.

To mitigate this risk, we take the problem outside of the existing data centers. By creating a new Geosciences Interoperability Institute we have a center of expertise whose mission is to enable reuse, and no conflict of interest. This new data center has no data of its own, but instead concentrates on software and brokering solutions to translating data into cross-domain form. The solutions implemented by the center are proven before being proposed to the data centers for in-domain adoption and support. Thus, the restrictions to be imposed upon the existing data centers are driven by successful reuse stories, and not simply by abstract concepts of reuse. In addition, the center develops and presents coordinated data management policies and best practices for potential adoption by other data centers and the larger community.

10.2 INSUFFICIENCY OF SOLUTIONS

Another inherent risk is that the solutions for cross-domain use (hampered by conflict of interest, as discussed above) could be insufficient to enable cross-domain science. Insufficiency takes several forms:

1. **Insufficiency of metadata and/or provenance:** not enough is known about data to confidently apply the data in a modeling situation.
2. **Insufficiency of sampling:** not enough data are gathered originally to either apply the data or to down-sample it appropriately for a specific reuse.
3. **Lack of sufficient quality:** the data are not gathered to sufficient accuracy or precision to support reuse.
4. **Lack of trust:** the assumptions, conditions, and environments in which data are gathered or generated are not sufficiently documented (either in metadata or in another form) for the cross-domain scientist to trust the measurements.

5. **Inadequacy of standards to ensure interoperability:** various “compliant” implementations of the relevant standards for encodings and/or service interfaces in a given application may not be interoperable, due to different handling of optional aspects in the standard, use of incompatible profiles of a given standard, rapid pace of change in underlying technology; and other possibilities.

One way to mitigate these situations is to drive cross-domain use with specific, proven use cases so that there is high confidence that the repackaged data will be usable, trustable, and sufficiently documented to enable some uses. Cross-domain use is not an abstract goal; it must be grounded in specific success stories.

The most effective approach to reduce the potential and impact of finding compliant yet non-interoperable standards is to conduct interoperability projects (experiments, testbeds, pilots) that specifically address known issues. These form the basis for high-quality case studies, best practices, and other kinds of recommendations.

Another mitigating strategy is to support direct connections between scientists and/or data and model providers in different domains, via social networking and similar means. An additional approach to maintaining trust is to technically enable and reward community annotation of insufficiently documented data and other resources.

10.3 MISUSE OF DATA

Another risk – intimately related to the previous ones – is that data misuse will lead to inaccurate scientific conclusions. While the previous risk was that of trusting data too little, this is instead a mistake of trusting data too much, including the possibilities that scientists will assume that:

1. Data are collected according to differing assumptions and methods than actually used.
2. Data are recorded at a higher precision than actually occurred.
3. Data are suitable for models that are too sensitive to its inaccuracies and ambiguities.

So far, we have carefully designed a plan for sufficiently documenting what is known about data. Mitigating this risk requires carefully documenting what is not known and cannot be assumed about each kind of data. Also, a collection of misuse cases as part of data annotation would be instructive. It could help prevent further misuses, and also point to insufficiencies in documentation models.

10.4 LACK OF TRUST

A final risk is that – regardless of how carefully we mitigate the previous risks – scientists will simply not trust cross-domain data solutions to do what they claim to do. Potential sources of mistrust are documented above. Trust is about “knowing enough about data” to be confident that it is appropriately applicable to a problem. Thus, mitigating this problem is a matter of careful data documentation, including documentation of successful scientific uses of cross-domain data. Trust can only be grounded in successes.

A related risk is that data products generated for typical domain use or even typical cross-domain use may be not trusted or not suitable for applications in certain domains. Inside a domain, users may be

knowledgeable enough to calculate a data product themselves, or use a pre-built data product with known semantics and provenance. However, it is unclear whether standard data product will be trusted in non-domain uses. For example, a “precipitation by watersheds” data product may be useful for hydrologists, or they may rather produce it themselves. If such a product would be useful, it may be created to the standards of the hydrologic community but it is unclear whether it would also meet the needs of other communities (e.g. the biology community may need the data organized by watershed or by stream reach.) Such patterns of trust in specific products intended for cross-domain reuse are yet unknown. To mitigate this risk, it is important to monitor and annotate product reuses in different contexts, and also engage with sociologists to better understand requirements for specific products in different communities before much effort is expended on building them.

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